

Journal for
Formal Linguistics and Philosophy

FLAP FIRST

Founded 2024
Volume 1
Released May 2025

Kaixin ZHAO (editor-in-chief)
Yoyo PY TSANG
Tommy YC WONG

Table of Contents

Preface and Thanks	ii
MOHANAN, K P & Tara MOHANAN “Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language”	1
KULKARNI, Rahul & K P MOHANAN “Further Discussions on “Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language””	11
YIP, Ka-Fai “Inner Aspect in Cantonese”	15
SIO, Joanna Ut-Seong “Comments for Yip’s “Inner Aspect in Cantonese””	37
YIP, Ka-Fai “Response to Sio’s Comments for “Inner Aspect in Cantonese””	39
LI, Mingxing “Vowel Epenthesis in Sibe: A Perceptual Account”	45
SHEN, Xinlei “The Phonological Study of Monosyllabic Tones and Reduplication Tone Sandhi in Chongqing Mandarin”	56
DU, Sirui & Daai-Syut YEUNG “Phonological Profile of Gyersgang Tibetan: An Endangered Eastern Tibetic Language Spoken in Thebo, Western China”	63
WEE, Lian-Hee “The Prosodic Status of the Sentence Final Particle in Hong Kong Cantonese”	101
CHEN, Yi Jen “Comments for Wee’s “The Prosodic Status of the Sentence Final Particle””	108
WONG, Tommy YC “Review of N. Otre Le Vant’s <i>On Progress in Physics and Subjectivity Theory: An Amateur’s Meanderings as Inspiration for Actual Physicists</i> ”	109
About <i>FLaP FIRST</i>	112
Submission information	116

Preface

FLaP FIRST was initiated in 2024 in celebration of the 12th year of the founding of the HKBU Phonology Lab. Since its establishment in 2012, the lab has supported academic research by students and researchers, locally and internationally. In particular, it has been a place where young researchers obtain knowledge and skills, share their ideas, get support and encouragement from their peers and teachers, and step forward on their journey in linguistics. Although primarily concerned with supporting the students and teachers at the Hong Kong Baptist University, the lab had served as a nucleating site for scholars beyond its university walls. Mingxing Li received help from the lab when he was a PhD student at the University of Kansas. The research enabled through the lab contributed to his later research so that he was eventually hired as a professor at HKBU where he now serves as the lab's director, inheriting the mantle from Lian-Hee Wee who founded it. Other notable alumni of the lab include Suki SY Yiu, now a tenured lecturer at Amsterdam University. Suki was a HKBU undergraduate before the lab was built, but also found support at the lab when she was doing her PhD research at the University of Hong Kong.

With the founding of the lab, two reading groups came to meet regularly there. The first was PUFF (Phonological Undertakings for Fun) where typically a teacher leads students to study a paper or a concept. PUFF had been around since 2006 and came under the lab's wing. As one of the lab's main aims was to enhance student research, students came to use the lab very frequently, often in imaginative ways that went beyond phonology. The lab had hosted a radio show advocating animal welfare, and been a venue for a literary symposium (Backreading Hong Kong 2019), among others. In 2017, a group of advanced undergraduates soon founded the Formal Linguistics and Philosophy reading group (FLaP) with Lian-Hee Wee as their advisor. Some of these undergraduates went on to different careers, but a few of them went further and established this journal: *FLaP FIRST*. From student-led reading group to student-led research curation: a very bold move in itself, but the valour did not end here.

These students conceived *FLaP FIRST* to be revolutionary in a few aspects. *FLaP FIRST* experiments with new ways to balance originality of scholarship with the rigours of reviewership. It endeavours also to give reviewers the recognition they deserve by offering to publish the reviews. In many ways, *FLaP FIRST* is inspired by *Radical: a Journal of Phonology*, although they have added their own twists to include enough flexibility so that rigorous thoughts and ideas that might not easily find a suitable journal would find a more welcoming venue here.

Consider, for instance, the manifesto by Mohanan & Mohanan and the ensuing discussion by Kulkarni & Mohanan. Such a piece would not easily find a place in most journals. Yet, it is important because it addresses the issue of what "formal" means, why it is important, and how it can be cultivated. Most university programmes have become so focussed on problem solving and skill development as to become almost a vocational training institute. This is not saying that problem-solving is not important, but we do need a balance. Problem-solving inherently implies a hidden value matrix. After all, a problem exists only if there is a mismatch between reality and the ideal, and *ideal* implies value judgment. If universities do not value thinking more profound than just skills and problem solving, there are no other institutions left in society that could rise to this task.

FLaP FIRST is daring because it is so idealistic in its conception. The founding students have no funding. Yet, they devised a plan to keep the journal free with open accessibility. They want authors to retain full rights. They want to preserve author originality while recognizing valid reviewer critique publicly. They want to trigger conversation by featuring such conversations in their journal. More interestingly, they did not want to keep power for themselves, and wrote into their constitution that the editorial and advisory boards shall change hands and leadership with each volume. They created *FLaP FIRST* and then want to give it to the world so that no one, and no institution shall own it. It will roll from hand to hand and allow others to take positions of leadership in the field. Already, the current chief editor, Kaixin Zhao, has identified a successor in

Tommy YC Wong, who is currently a member of the editorial. And Tommy has started to build his own editorial team that would include young scholars from other universities in preparation for the next volume.

There are so many odds against *FLaP FIRST*. But Kaixin Zhao, Yoyo PY Tsang, and Tommy YC Wong have taken that leap forward. Many people have been very supportive. Among them, the international panel of scholars who generously agreed to serve on the advisory board. Also, we saw how other scholars had willingly given time to help with reviews. Many who were not able to help, wrote back promptly and encouragingly. Most of all, the people who contributed the high-quality submissions seen in this inaugural volume of a fledgling journal. Consider, for instance, the exceptional piece by Du & Yeung. It brings fieldwork to bear on theorizing, providing fresh perspectives on the relation of Tibetan languages, essentially demonstrating a kind of speciation akin to biology. Equally exciting is Yip's work on Cantonese syntax. It is the first systematic study on the structural properties of inner aspect in Cantonese, of which 14 such aspectual elements are identified. Shen's work on Chongqing reduplicative morphology provided evidence that underlying tones may be much simpler than one might think, thus accounting for a surface inexplicable complexity where there are only contoured tones and no level tones. The originality and substance of these works would have easily qualified them for publication in well-known journals. And yet the authors have found it in their hearts to support the ideals underlying *FLaP FIRST*. We shall not comment on the pieces by Li and by Wee, since that would be shameless as writers of this preface. We shall leave you with an invitation to read them.

Our young heroes always had gratitude. They found creative ways to publicize the good work of the contributors. When a paper received acceptance, they made announcements on social media, featuring the author(s) and their research interests. They consulted us frequently and regularly, always asking how to do better, and what else may be done for those who had given support so freely. From our front-row seats, watching how our intrepid young editors navigate these unfamiliar waters had us constantly biting our nails while rooting for them.

We could write paragraphs on the hardship endured by the editors who are struggling also with their own research, and many other challenges that plague the lives of youths today. There were some who looked askance at their efforts, scorning their naivete. Fortunately, there haven't been any yet who had tried to usurp the enterprise that had been intended to be free from institutional KPI tyranny. Our young editors drew strength from those who understood them, and found it in their hearts to actively become part of the solution to the challenges that academics face regarding publication and dissemination. They embody the adage, "The someone is me, the time is now."

If *FLaP FIRST* endures, it would be a victory for the innocence of scholarship. Success will depend on all of us. Please keep a lookout and follow their webpage and other social media, and support them by reading the papers, citing them, and sharing them. Most importantly, please contribute to the journal with your papers or by encouraging others. We certainly look forward to reading many subsequent volumes.

We are very proud to be part of this very beautiful vision. We are grateful that as our students create independence, they had also honoured the lab that was their first meeting place. From them, we find hope.

Lian-Hee Wee
Chair, *FLaP FIRST* advisory
&
Mingxing Li
Director, HKBU Phonology Lab

Post scriptum: We were even more impressed to discover that, out of academic integrity, these editors had relied entirely on their own resources (personal computers, free google storage and email accounts, free social media, etc) in the operation of *FLaP FIRST*. They had made it so to

keep the journal free and independent. In their own words “*FLaP FIRST* owns itself and is not the property of anyone.”

The editorial board would like to thank the following people for their expertise as reviewers (in alphabetical order):

Yi Jen CHEN
Hui-shan LIN
Joanna U.-S. SIO
SRINIVAS Sampath Kumar

Some reviewers had preferred to remain anonymous, and we too send them our deepest gratitude.

Although unusual, and certainly not flippantly, we would also like to thank future sponsors, reviewers, and other people who would help us continue. We hope it would be you, and that we would be able to proudly list your name here among our benefactors.

In joined hands, sincerely,
Kaixin Zhao
Yoyo PY Tsang
Tommy YC Wong

Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language

K P Mohanan
mohanan.kp@gmail.com

Tara Mohanan
tara.mohanan@gmail.com

This is the first draft of a manifesto for a specific strand of education. A manifesto is a public declaration of an ideal future state of affairs in the world, written with the hope that the articulation of that dream would inspire like-minded people to invest time and effort to form a revolutionary grassroots movement in the direction it points to. We expect this manifesto to evolve beyond the initial drafts, and branch into multiple manifestos with a common core.

1. The Origins
2. Level 1: Drawing Inferences
3. Level 2: Using a Natural Language to Draw Inferences
4. Level 3: Logic
5. Level 4: Formal Logic
6. Level 5: Epistemic Semiotics
7. Level 6: Evolution of Formalisms for Reasoning
8. Evolution of Formalised Reasoning in Mathematics

1. The origins

We (TM and KPM) have recently embarked on a project that involves designing learning materials for a course on *Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language* (KRL) for 8th and 9th grade students. We are hoping to expand the project into a larger one of KRL from secondary school to undergraduate and graduate levels. Here is a brief description of the expanded project.

The transmission of **KNOWLEDGE** from one generation to subsequent ones is an important function of educational institutions, both at the school level and in higher education. The knowledge that is transmitted in this way is **Academic Knowledge**, as distinct from other forms of knowledge such as folk knowledge, ethnic knowledge, traditional knowledge, and so on.

In addition to the transmission of knowledge, institutionalised education also has a responsibility to help students develop the capacity to:

- (a) acquire academic knowledge on their own from documented sources,
- (b) critically evaluate the credibility of what is transmitted as academic knowledge, and
- (c) construct academic knowledge

Central to these capacities is the ability to use **academic LANGUAGE** for **communication, critical thinking, and inquiry**. At the core of these abilities is REASONING. Hence the title, *Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language*.

Parallel to designing KRL, KPM has also been exchanging thoughts on this with John Goldsmith. One of the central threads in the conversations has been the role of an understanding of the evolutionary history of knowledge in designing curricula. Before the conversations with John, KPM's position was that a historical perspective was not essential till after learners have an adequate competence in inquiry abilities, and a grounding in the current state of knowledge (e.g., in the third or fourth year of a bachelor's program). But John's position was that in order to gain a meaningful understanding of current knowledge and inquiry, even learners in high

school need to get at least a glimpse of the history. KPM is now convinced of John's position¹ (which is more in harmony with TM's).

In recent conversations, we (TM and KPM) have jointly been trying to figure out how to weave a transdisciplinary evolutionary history of academic knowledge and inquiry into a curriculum that spans secondary school to the undergraduate level, also including the evolutionary history of logic as the study of reasoning. We must confess that we have been groping in the dark, experimenting with different ways of sequencing the material, structuring it as concentric circles that increase both in breadth and depth, in terms of levels ranging from introductory, through semi-intermediate, intermediate, and semi-advanced, to advanced, and so on.

In what follows, we share an idea for structuring that has emerged in the course of conversations over the past few days, as a solution to the problem of structuring and sequencing the KRL curriculum from Primary School to PhD.

2. Level 1: Drawing inferences

The processes of experiencing and drawing inferences are the backbone of cognition, which is a central attribute of animate entities. All living creatures from bacteria to two-year old human children make inferences. This suggests that an introduction to reasoning must begin with tasks that call for making inferences without the use of language, though to communicate them to others, we would need to use a natural language.

Such conscious exposure to the practice of reasoning is analogous to activities in which children practice origami, carpentry, playing with shadows, and so on, in early childhood education, as preparation for geometry and the sciences at a later stage.

3. Level 2: Using a natural language to draw inferences

Reasoning is *a form of inferencing, using premises and conclusions expressed in a natural language*. Just as the capacity to learn 'natural' languages (e.g., English, Hindi, Japanese, ...) is unique to humans, so is the process of inferring through reasoning (unlike other ways of arriving at inferences).

Within level 2, we may identify several sub-levels:

Level 2A uses the structure of *premises* and *conclusions* (without the steps of deriving the conclusions from the premises), expressed in a natural language. Even in primary school, it is feasible to help learners acquire the capacity for reasoning, as is evidenced in the pedagogy of P4C (Philosophy for Children).

Level 2B goes beyond level 2A, to include the *steps of derivation*.

Level 2C supplements 2B with a *diagrammatic language*. To do this, we can use geometry as a form of *scientific inquiry*: children make inferences of shapes on the basis of their experience of real life objects like circular plates, rectangular table tops, triangular paper cut-outs, and so on.

Level 2D (Grades 6 and 7 onwards) uses the structure of premises, steps of derivation, and conclusion, expressed in a natural language, supplemented with a diagrammatic

¹ KPM met John Goldsmith when he joined the PhD program in Linguistics at MIT, where John was a few years his senior. After MIT, they continued interacting for a decade or so. Then after a few years of not being in touch, they resumed their interaction in 2021, and have had regular conversations since then, initially through email exchanges, and now via online meetings.

- g. If Zeno is an insect and Plato is a rabbit, then Aristotle is a mouse.
Zeno is an insect.
Therefore, Aristotle is a mouse.
- h. If Zeno is an insect or Plato is a rabbit, then Aristotle is a mouse.
Plato is not a rabbit.
Aristotle is a mouse.
Therefore, Zeno is an insect.

Even though it may not be obvious at a cursory reading, an astute reader can see that the pattern of reasoning in examples in (3e)–(3h) is flawed, in contrast to that in (3a)–(3d). The rules of inference that capture this result can be found in introductory logic textbooks.

We propose the following sublevels for level 3:

Level 3A is that of Aristotelean syllogistic reasoning as an example of the Ancient Greek lineage, based on categories, subcategories, and category membership. (E.g., Zeno is a mammal, mammals have vertebrae, therefore Zeno has vertebrae.) This form of reasoning is a special case of *correlational deductive reasoning*.

Level 3B is that of a simplified version of the Ancient Indian lineage, based on what is common to Buddhist Logic, Jainist Logic, and Nyaya Logic. This form of reasoning is difficult to classify (because most texts are in Sanskrit, and the English translations are generally confusing, as the translators are not sufficiently grounded in systems of modern logic). Nevertheless, it is clear that the Ancient Indian lineage is not restricted to correlations and deduction: it includes causal reasoning (*hetu*: cause) and non-deductive reasoning from experience (*pratyaksha*: perception of what appears to us; *anumaana*: inference; *upamaana*: comparison, analogy; and *s'abda*: word, testimony).

The oft-cited example of the Ancient Indian lineage is (4).

- (4) Fire causes smoke. [Causal generalization]
I see fire on the hills. [Particular cause]
Therefore, it is reasonable to infer that there is smoke on the hills.

(4) is an example of *deductive causal reasoning* from *cause to effect*. [Note: This is our formulation of what we find in the literature on Ancient Indian logic, not how the literature presents the example.]

Here is an example of *abductive causal reasoning* from *effect to cause*, in (5).

- (5) Fire causes smoke. [Causal generalization]
I see smoke on the hills. [Particular effect]
Therefore, unless there is an alternative cause or a counter example, it is reasonable to infer that there is fire on the hills.

Abductive causal reasoning, needed in many other domains of personal, public, and professional lives, is also needed within academic disciplines including biology, medicine, law, engineering, management, and so on. The bulk of ‘real life’ reasoning is abductive causal reasoning.

[Note: TM and KPM have been looking, in the Ancient Indian literature, for examples of abductive causal reasoning, but have not found any in the English translations. We would need help from those who are literate in Sanskrit to look for examples in the Sanskrit literature.]

5. Level 4: Formal logic

Formal logic replaces the formulation of premises, conclusions, and rules of inference with algebraic symbols. Take, for instance, the following premises and conclusion in (6).

- (6) If Zeno is a mammal, then Zeno is a vertebrate.
 Zeno is a mammal.
 Therefore, Zeno is a vertebrate.

If we use the symbol P for “Zeno is a mammal,” and the symbol Q for “Zeno is a vertebrate,” we can express the premises and conclusion in (6) as (7).

- (7) If P, then Q
 P
 Therefore Q

The formal system called Propositional Calculus uses the *arrow* symbol \rightarrow for “if...then” (called ‘implication’) and the *turnstile* symbol \vdash for “therefore” (called ‘entailment’). (7) can be expressed in Propositional Calculus as (8).

- (8) $P \rightarrow Q$
 P
 $\vdash Q$
 [In arithmetic, the symbol for “entailment” is *three dots* (\therefore).]

Other symbols that Propositional Calculus uses are the tilde symbol \sim for “not” (called negation), \wedge for “and” (called “conjunction”), and \vee for “or” (called “disjunction”).

Boolean Algebra is another name for Propositional Calculus. You can see why it is called ‘calculus’ and ‘algebra’, even though it is not the same as calculus and algebra taught in math courses.

Now consider a slightly more complex use of natural language reasoning in (9).

- (9) a. Premise 1: Mammals have vertebrae.
 b. Premise 2: Zeno is a mammal.
 c. Conclusion: Therefore, Zeno has vertebrae.

Premises (9a) and (9b) can be rephrased as premises (10a) and (10b).

- (10) a. Premise 3: All members of the category of mammals have vertebrae.
 b. Premise 4: Zeno is a member of the category mammal.
 c. Conclusion: Therefore, Zeno has vertebrae.

To express (10) in a formal language, we need a symbol for “all”. Predicate calculus uses the symbol \forall (upside down A) for “all”, called “universal quantifier”. Corresponding to the universal quantifier, predicate calculus also has the symbol \exists (backward facing E) for “there exists”, called “existential quantifier”. Its use is illustrated in example (11).

- (11) a. Premise 1: All mammals are vertebrates.
 b. Premise 2: Zeno is a mammal.
 c. Conclusion: Therefore, there exists at least one vertebrate.

Predicate Calculus is the system of formal logic that we have seen in examples (11).

6. Level 5: Epistemic semiotics

Semiotics is the study of symbols/signs. A sign/symbol is a pairing of *form* (called signifier) and *meaning* (called signified).

To take an example from English, the word *city* is a symbol. Its written form is a sequence of four letters $c > i > t > y$. Its spoken form is a sequence of four ‘sounds’ (phonemes) $/s/ > /i/ > /t/ > /i/$. The word signifies (it means/ refers to/ denotes) a geographical region in a country. Similarly, the phrase, “the capital of England,” and the sentence, “London is the capital of England,” are also signs/symbols, and so is the first paragraph of this document that begins with “We (TM and KPM) have recently embarked on ...” and ends with “...a brief description of that project.”

English, Hindi, Malayalam, etc. are **natural languages**. Equations with the *equality* symbol “=” are part of **formal languages**. For example, consider (12).

- (12) a. $4 \times 5 = 9$
 b. $4 \div 5 = 4/5$
 c. $(X + Y)^2 = X^2 + Y^2 + 2XY$
 d. $E = mc^2$

Mathematics and physics use such equations to assert that the quantitative value of the formula on the left of the *equality* symbol is the same as the quantitative value of the formula on its right. Chemistry expresses chemical equations with the *arrow* symbol \rightarrow , which asserts that the number and category of atoms to the left of the arrow is the same as the number and category of those on its right. These are also part of a formal language. Finally, the arrow symbol in formal logic, in graph theory, in function theory, and so on are also part of formal languages. Semiotics includes the study of formal languages as well.

Epistemic semiotics is the study of the form and meaning of natural languages and formal languages such that we can tell whether or not the propositions expressed in these languages are true. This is similar to, but not the same as, what is called *truth conditional semantics*.

To take a few examples, consider the problem of constructing a formal system (whether in mathematics or in formal logic) to express the contrast between the following pairs of arguments in (13), one valid and the other invalid.

- (13) a. i. Zeno is taller than Tron.
 Tron is taller than Aristotle.
 Therefore, Zeno is taller than Aristotle. *Valid*
 ii. Zeno admires Tron.
 Tron admires Aristotle.
 Therefore, Zeno admires Aristotle. *Invalid*
 b. i. Zeno is Tron’s sibling, and Tron is Plato’s sibling.
 Therefore, Zeno is Plato’s sibling. *Valid*
 ii. Zeno is Plato’s father, and Plato is Tron’s father.
 Therefore, Zeno is Tron’s father. *Invalid*
 c. i. Zeno killed an ant.
 Therefore, we can conclude that Zeno killed a living organism. *Valid*
 ii. Zeno killed a living organism.
 Therefore, we can conclude that Zeno killed an ant. *Invalid*

- | | | | |
|----|-----|---|----------------|
| d. | i. | Zeno killed Tron at 10:15 am on 20/12/1934.
Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Tron was not alive at 10:20 am on 20/12/1934. | <i>Valid</i> |
| | ii. | Zeno killed Tron at 10:15 am on 20/12/1934.
Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Tron was not alive at 10:10 am on 20/12/1934. | <i>Invalid</i> |
| e. | i. | Zeno assassinated Tron at 10:15 am on 20/12/1934.
Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Zeno killed a socio-politically prominent person at 10:20 am on 20/12/1934. | <i>Valid</i> |
| | ii. | Zeno killed Tron at 10:15 am on 20/12/1934.
Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Zeno killed a socio-politically prominent person at 10:20 am on 20/12/1934. | <i>Invalid</i> |
| f. | i. | Zeno arranged the furniture again at 10:15 am on 20/12/1934.
Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Zeno had arranged the furniture at least once prior to 10:20 am on 20/12/1934. | <i>Valid</i> |
| | ii. | Zeno rearranged the furniture at 10:15 am on 20/12/1934.
Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that Zeno had arranged the furniture at least once prior to 10:20 am on 20/12/1934. | <i>Invalid</i> |

These examples belong in the discipline we have called *Grammatical Semantics* (Mohanan & Wee 1999). Epistemic Semiotics is a special case of both Grammatical Semantics and Semiotics.

A full-fledged formalism specifically for the expression of the premises, conclusions, steps of reasoning, and rules of inference is yet to be invented.

7. Level 6: Evolution of formalisms for reasoning

In the context of education, both mathematics and logic can be thought of as providing training grounds for rigorous reasoning. In the Western lineage, we think of Euclid as the father of axiomatic proofs in mathematics, and Aristotle as the father of logic as the study of reasoning. The Indian Lineage in mathematics includes names like Aryabhata, Brahmagupta, Bhāskara, Varāhamihira, and Mādhava; and in logic, schools of epistemology and logic called Buddhist logic, Jainist logic, and Nyāya logic. Eminently valuable resources on the evolution of these lineages include *Mathematics in India* (Plofker 2009) and *In Pursuit of the Unknown: 17 Equations that Changed the World* (Stewart 2012).

It took several centuries for people to express these forms of reasoning in terms of algebraic symbols in mathematical equations and formal logic. We will not say much about that history except by way of pointing to some of the landmarks.

Mathematical reasoning has four strands, listed in (14).

- (14)
- a. *Proof type 1*: Reasoning from axioms and definitions to yield theorems.
 - b. *Proof type 2*: Reasoning from theorems to yield other theorems, using mathematical equations for calculation.
 - c. *Derivation type 1*: Reasoning from mathematical equations to formulae and other equations.
 - d. *Derivation type 2*: Reasoning from equations and formulae to the numerical values of variables.

Borrowing the term from computer science, let us use the term *computation* to include both numerical and non-numerical operations. (15) is an example of calculation (numerical computation).

- (15) Given the numerical values of the angles of a triangle and the numerical value of the length of one of the sides, we can compute the numerical values of the lengths of the other two sides.

Computation includes algorithms to arrive at non-numerical values of a variable; it also includes algorithms for categorial values of a variable, as in mathematical linguistics and computational linguistics. Formal Logic and discrete mathematics are the backbones of computation in computer science.

8. Evolution of formalized reasoning in mathematics

Finally, we outline below the landmarks in the evolution of formalized reasoning in Mathematics.

The history of mathematics begins with arithmetic. According to the entry on Arithmetic in *Kids Britannica*:

The foundation of all other branches of mathematics is arithmetic, the science of calculating with numbers. [...] The term arithmetic comes from arithmos, the Greek word for number; but people began doing arithmetic long before the Greeks invented the word, even before anyone invented numbers. Historians believe that as early as 10,000 years ago, when prehistoric people started farming, they began to use arithmetic. They needed to know such things as how many sheep they owned, or how many rows of grain they planted, or how long it would be before harvest season arrived.

(Rose, n.d.)

In the evolutionary history of academic knowledge, there is a sense in which we can discern a strand that can be called the evolution of the imperialism of arithmetic in academic culture. In his celebrated 1959 REDE Lecture, “The Two Cultures”, C P Snow talked about the distinction between the science culture (the term covering mathematics culture as well) and the humanities culture (essentially covering those academic pursuits that do not use mathematics for representing information or explaining phenomena).

In hindsight, what Snow was pointing to is perhaps best described as the distinction between the culture that relies on arithmetic (in addition to natural languages) and the culture that relies only on natural languages (eschewing arithmetic). Clearly, the dominant culture is that of arithmetic, as seen in (16).

- (16) a. theoretical laws that use equations to express correlations in terms of the equality of numerical values.
b. research that crucially use statistics — measurement and arithmetic operations — in gathering and organizing data.

For the purposes of the design of a curriculum for KRL, all the information we need for the evolutionary history of arithmetic can be found in the *Kids Britannica* article mentioned above.

From arithmetic and geometry as applied sciences emerged geometry and number theory as mathematics. Euclid’s *Elements* introduced into mathematics reasoning of types A and B (axiomatic reasoning), without formalization. Formal reasoning entered mathematics

with mathematical equations, that had its origins in Algebra. The formalization program received a further impetus with the emergence of formal logics in the second half of the nineteenth century, and with Hilbert's program ("Hilbert's program", 2024), and the publication of Whitehead and Russell's *Principia Mathematica* in the early twentieth century, which initiated the quest for the formal foundations of mathematics.

Very soon, the 'barber paradox' and Gödel's theorems demonstrated that Hilbert's dream (like Descartes's dream) was unattainable. To quote Gödel,

*It is to be regretted that this first comprehensive and thorough-going presentation of a mathematical logic and the derivation of mathematics from it [is] so greatly lacking in formal precision in the foundations (contained in *1–*21 of Principia [i.e., sections *1–*5 (propositional logic), *8–*14 (predicate logic with identity/equality), *20 (introduction to set theory), and *21 (introduction to relations theory)]) that it represents in this respect a considerable step backwards as compared with Frege. What is missing, above all, is a precise statement of the syntax of the formalism. Syntactical considerations are omitted even in cases where they are necessary for the cogency of the proofs...*

(Gödel 1944)

Turning to logic as a study of reasoning, it began with two values: 'true' / 'false' (Aristotle's Law of Excluded Middle). The nineteenth century saw the emergence of logics with three values: 'true' / 'false' / 'neither'. The twentieth century saw the emergence of logics with four values, including quantum logic. Chances are that the Nyāya systems of logic were three-valued, and that Nāgārjuna's *Catuskoṭi* has four values, which, in modern terminology, is called *tetralemma*.

Aristotelian logic captures correlational deductive reasoning. Indian logics cover causal deductive reasoning as well. The twentieth century saw the emergence of probabilistic logics, defeasible (non-monotonic) logics, inductive logics, and abductive logics. Deductive and abductive causal logics are still more recent.

Resources for Ancient Systems

- Arithmetic (see <https://kids.britannica.com/students/article/arithmetic/272946>)
- Algebra (see History of Algebra at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_algebra)
- Numerals (see History of Ancient Numeral Systems at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_ancient_numeral_systems)
- Logic (see History of Logic at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_logic)

REFERENCES

- Gödel, Kurt (1944) Russell's Mathematical Logic. In Paul Arthur Schilpp (ed.), *The Philosophy of Bertrand Russell*, pp.123-154. Evanston and Chicago: Northwestern University Press.
- Hilbert's Program (2024, August 18) In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hilbert%27s_program

- Mohanan, K P & Tara Mohanan (2024) *Constructing Theories of Geometry with Excursions into Biology*. ThinQ. <https://www.thinq.education/post/constructing-theories-a-case-study-in-geometry-with-an-extension-to-biology>
- Mohanan, Tara & Lionel Wee (1999) *Grammatical Semantics: Evidence for Structure in Meaning*. Stanford, California: CSLI Publications.
- Plofker, Kim (2009) *Mathematics in India*. Princeton and Oxford: Princeton University Press.
- Rose, Kenneth (n.d.) *Arithmetic*. In *Britannica Kids*. Retrieved from <https://kids.britannica.com/scholars/article/arithmetic/272946>
- Stewart, Ian (2012) *In Pursuit of the Unknown: 17 Equations that Changed the World*. New York: Basic Books.

Copyright 2025. KP Mohanan and Tara Mohanan.

Date received: 20 March 2025

To cite:

Mohanan, K P & Tara Mohanan (2025) Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:1-10.

FLaP FIRST

Facebook

Website

Further Discussions on “Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language”

Rahul Kulkarni
rahul@godonew.com

K P Mohanan
mohanan.kp@gmail.com

[Editor’s note: This article presents an excerpt from an email exchange between Rahul Kulkarni and K P Mohanan discussing the manifesto “Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language”. The discussion provides an example of how the manifesto evolves into a collection of research programs.]

- ✧ Rahul Kulkarni is a co-founder of DoNew. (<https://www.godonew.com/>)
- ✧ K P Mohanan is a co-founder of ThinQ. (<https://www.thinq.education/>)

1. Excerpted comments from Rahul Kulkarni

I thought notation even exists for defeasible logic. What is missing is this notation turning into operations. Consider example (1).

- (1)
- | | |
|---------------------|----------------------------|
| a. P(roposition) 1: | Humans have bones. |
| b. P2: | Humans are mammals. |
| c. P3: | Mammals are living beings. |
| d. P4: | Plato has bones. |
| e. C(onclusion)1: | Plato is a living being. |

Now I can put (1) into a graph with N and relations R as (2) and (3) respectively.

- (2)
- | | |
|--------------|---------------|
| a. N(ode) 1: | bones |
| b. N2: | humans |
| c. N3: | mammals |
| d. N4: | living beings |
| e. N5: | Plato |
- (3)
- | | |
|-----------------|---------------------|
| a. R(elation)1: | $N1 \rightarrow N2$ |
| b. R2: | $N2 \rightarrow N3$ |
| c. R3: | $N3 \rightarrow N4$ |
| d. R4: | $N1 \rightarrow N5$ |

Questions: using reasoning math operations, prove that $N5 \rightarrow N4$.

Answer:

- (4)
- | | |
|----|---|
| a. | $N1 \rightarrow N2$ AND $N2 \rightarrow N3$ == $N1 \rightarrow N3$ |
| b. | $N1 \rightarrow N3$ AND $N3 \rightarrow N4$ == $N1 \rightarrow N4$ (newly created ‘compressive’ property) |
| c. | $N1 \rightarrow N4$ AND $N1 \rightarrow N5$ == $N4 \rightarrow N5$ (newly created ‘associative’ property) |

Does this make sense? Can we not invent a matrix equivalent for reasoning?

2. K P Mohanan's response to Rahul Kulkarni

#1#

KULKARNI: I thought notation even exists for defeasible logic.

MOHANAN: That made me pause and reflect. A few points.

- (5a) I am using the term Defeasible Reasoning (DR) and Defeasible Logic (DL) to include not only defeasible noncausal deductive reasoning (non-monotonic reasoning) but also defeasible inductive reasoning and defeasible causal reasoning (both deductive and inductive).
- (5b) The primary purpose of my exploration of DR is education: to develop a system, including notation, to help students (from secondary school to PhD) acquire the capacity to engage in inquiry/research and critical thinking-and-reading across multiple domains of knowledge (transdisciplinary).
- (5c) For this purpose, we need to draw upon epistemology (philosophical investigation of Human knowledge), cognitive science (both human and non-human).
- (5d) If the above attempt is successful, the algorithmizable parts of it can be built into an AI tutor in online courses that aim at (5b) and its discipline specific versions (e.g. research in the sciences of health and illness in Ayurveda and Modern Mainstream medicine).
- (5e) If (5d) is successful it can make a contribution to Artificial Intelligence as an implementation of cognitive science, granted that all parts of cognition can be algorithmized.
- (5f) Given (5a)–(5c), the preexisting notation for Defeasible Logic will not be useful for our pursuit. We will have to create the notation ourselves.
- (5g) Unlike the current notations in mathematics and formal logics, the notation for (5f) cannot afford to be too 'technical': it needs to be used by undergrad students in the health and illness sciences, in the life sciences, in history, in law, and so on. It will be a combination of (a) a simplified algebraic notation and (b) diagrammatic notation, such that the learner can reason better and critically think about issues simply by looking at the diagrams, and the computer can provide the equivalent of pocket calculator in the application of the logic.

Points (5a)–(5g) will have to be made clear at the beginning of the article meant for publication.

#2#

KULKARNI: What is missing is this notation turning into operations.

MOHANAN: More than that. The distinction between relations and operations is important, but not crucial for our purposes. What is missing in example (1) you give is a distinction between propositional implications and what might be called category and subcategory-based reasoning (propositional logic vs syllogism).

#3#

KULKARNI: Consider example (1).

- (1) a. P(roposition) 1: Humans have bones.
- b. P2: Humans are mammals.
- c. P3: Mammals are living beings.
- d. P4: Plato has bones.
- e. C(onclusion)1: Plato is a living being.

MOHANAN: This reasoning in (1) is sloppy, Try (6).

- (6) a. P1: Plato is a human.
- b. P2: Humans are mammals.
- c. P3: Mammals are vertebrates.
- d. P4: Vertebrates have bones.
- e. C1: Therefore, Plato has bones.

The conclusion that (1e) “Plato is a living being” can be validly arrived only on the basis of a definition of living being, combined with propositions about Plato.

Central to the example I have given in (6) are:

- (7) a. Statements about categories and subcategories,
- b. A statement about some property of the highest mother category in (i), and
- c. The principle of Logical Inheritance that says that the properties of the mother category are inherited by the properties of her daughter categories.

Together, (7a)–(7c) constitute the structure of syllogism. Take the oft quoted example from Aristotle in (8).

- (8) Humans are mortal. (type (7b) statement)
- Socrates is human. (type (7c) statement)
- Therefore, Socrates is mortal.

Example (8) does not appeal to type (7a) statements, but it is easy to see that (7a)–(7c) is needed in biology.

The kind of logic that Russell and Whitehead were trying to develop for mathematical proofs was that of sets and subsets, as distinct from categories and subcategories. The Russell and Whitehead’s formalism is not sufficient for the kinds of reasoning needed in biology illustrated in my examples. It also leads to problems like the barber paradox.

Categorial reasoning is necessary but not sufficient in classical deduction, Consider examples (9) and (10).

- (9) Zeno is taller than Plato
- Plato is taller than Socrates.
- Therefore, Zeno is taller than Socrates.

- (10) If Plato is had wine yesterday, then Socrates killed an insect the day before.
- Plato had wine yesterday.
- Therefore, Socrates killed an insect the day before yesterday.

Neither example (9) nor example (10) has sets or categories.

We need to develop pedagogically accessible notations for both categorial reasoning and implicational reasoning.

#4#

KULKARNI: Now I can put (1) into a graph with N and relations R as (2) and (3) respectively.

- (2)
- | | |
|--------------|---------------|
| a. N(ode) 1: | bones |
| b. N2: | humans |
| c. N3: | mammals |
| d. N4: | living beings |
| e. N5: | Plato |

- (3)
- | | |
|-----------------|---------------------|
| a. R(elation)1: | $N1 \rightarrow N2$ |
| b. R2: | $N2 \rightarrow N3$ |
| c. R3: | $N3 \rightarrow N4$ |
| d. R4: | $N1 \rightarrow N5$ |

MOHANAN: Since your reasoning in (1) is flawed, (2) and (3) won't work either.

#5#

KULKARNI:

Questions: using reasoning math operations, prove that $N5 \rightarrow N4$.

Answer:

- (4)
- | | |
|----|---|
| a. | $N1 \rightarrow N2$ AND $N2 \rightarrow N3$ \implies $N1 \rightarrow N3$ |
| b. | $N1 \rightarrow N3$ AND $N3 \rightarrow N4$ \implies $N1 \rightarrow N4$ (newly created 'compressive' property) |
| c. | $N1 \rightarrow N4$ AND $N1 \rightarrow N5$ \implies $N4 \rightarrow N5$ (newly created 'associative' property) |

MOHANAN: Same comment as before.

KULKARNI: Does this make sense? Can we not invent a matrix equivalent for reasoning?

MOHANAN: I can see what you seek to do, but we need to create our own notation, given points (5a)–(5f).

Copyright 2025. Rahul Kulkarni and KP Mohanan.

Date received: 21 March 2025

To cite:

Kulkarni, Rahul & K P Mohanan (2025) Further Discussions on “Designing Learning Materials for Knowledge, Reasoning, and Language”. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:11-14.

Inner Aspect in Cantonese

Ka-Fai Yip
Yale University
kafai.yip@yale.edu

Abstract

The paper provides the first systematic study on the structural properties of inner aspect in Cantonese. In total 14 postverbal inner aspectual elements have been identified (e.g., completive *gyun* in *sik-gyun* ‘finish eating’). It is shown that they occupy a middle position: above resultative verbal complements (e.g., *baau* ‘full’ in *sik-baau* ‘eat and become full’), but below outer aspectual elements (e.g., perfective *-zo* in *sik-zo* ‘ate’). Syntactically, they are lower than *vP* but may be either higher or lower than *VP*. Furthermore, while some of them are phase complements, some others have already become or on their way to becoming verbal suffixes.

Keywords: inner aspect, phase complements, verbal suffixes, Cantonese

1. Introduction

Aspect refers to “different ways of viewing the internal temporal constituency of a situation” (Comrie 1976:3) denoted by the predicate. Aspect may be divided into situation aspect and viewpoint aspect (Smith 1991, 1997; see Smith 1994 and Soh 2014 for Chinese). The former is usually known as eventualities (“Aktionsart”), including states, activities, accomplishments, and achievements; and the latter includes the familiar perfective and imperfective aspects.

Structurally speaking, there are at least two aspectual projections on the clausal spine: above *vP*, the outer aspect; and below *vP*, the inner aspect (i.e., “the split aspect approach”, MacDonald 2008, Travis 2010; for Mandarin and/or Cantonese, see Gu 1995, Tsai 2008, Huang, Li & Li 2009, Sybesma 2017, Lu, Lipták & Sybesma 2019, Yip 2020a, Tang 2022, Lee & Pan 2024). While attempts have been made to map outer aspect to viewpoint aspect and inner aspect to situation aspect (e.g., Lu, Lipták & Sybesma 2019), these two classifications do not exactly align. It is possible for viewpoint aspects to be encoded in both inner and outer aspect positions (see the recent study in Yan & Yuan 2024). This study maintains that the situation-viewpoint split is semantic and the inner-outer split is structural/syntactic, and there is no one-to-one mapping between them. The focus of this paper will be the inner-outer split.

Cantonese is rich in postverbal elements pertaining to aspect. There has been a fruitful of work on outer aspectual elements such as perfective suffix *-zo* (咗), experiential suffix *-gwo* (過), progressive suffix *-gan* (緊), durative suffix *-zyu* (住), among others (Lin 1963, Cheung 1972/2007:§4, Gao 1980:34–59, Matthews & Yip 1994:210–221, Zhi 1994, Li et al. 1995:418–424, 552–565, Chan 1996, Chang 1996, Cheng 2001, Chor 2004, Peng 2010; see the comprehensive review in Tang 2015:§7).¹ There is, however, very little attention on the **inner aspect** in Cantonese. Canonical inner aspectual elements include *hou* (好) in *so-hou* (鎖好) ‘locked properly’ or *zoek* (著) in *fan-zoek* (瞓著) ‘slept’, which express the phase/stage of an action and have been called phase complements (PCs) (時相補語) (Chao 1968: 446–450).

¹ Cantonese examples are transcribed in *Jyutping* (the Linguistic Society of Hong Kong Cantonese Romanization Scheme in 1993), and tones (1–6) are only represented for SFPs. The glossing abbreviations adopted in this paper: 1, 2, 3=first, second, third person respectively; CL=classifier; PL=plural; SG=singular; PFV=perfective aspect; PROG=progressive aspect; COMPL=completive aspect; ACHV=achievement aspect; CONT=continuative aspect; EXP=experiential aspect; DUR=durative aspect; SFP=sentence-final particle.

Some of them have been documented in some of work cited above, but there is, to the best of my knowledge, no systematic study on them.

The primary goal of this paper is to provide a comprehensive description of the structural properties of the inner aspectual elements in Cantonese. As will be discussed in Section 2, they are grammatically different from resultative verbal complements (RVCs), such as *baau* (飽) ‘full’ in *sik-baau* (食飽) ‘eat and become full’, and from outer aspectual elements such as perfective *-zo* (咗). Morphologically, RVCs are the closest to the verbal root, then inner aspect, and further, outer aspect, and the furthest one is the universal quantificational suffix *-saai* (晒) (see Zhan 1958, T. H. T. Lee 1994, Tang 2003, P. Lee 2004, 2012, *i.a.*), as schematized in (1).

- (1) The verbal template in Cantonese
 VERBAL ROOT < RVCs < inner aspect < outer aspect < *-saai*

I will proceed to discuss the grammatical status of inner aspectual elements with formal diagnostic tests in Section 3: whether they are phase complements or aspectual suffixes. Section 4 sketches a formal syntactic analysis. I propose that outer aspects are *vP*-external and inner aspects are *vP*-internal, and further suggest that the formal distinction between verbal complements and suffixes is whether they are base-generated within *VP*-internally or not. Section 5 concludes.

2. Defining inner aspect

Let us begin with an operational definition of (postverbal) inner aspectual elements in Cantonese, given in (2). (2b) and (2d) set them apart from RVCs; and (2c) sets them apart from outer aspectual suffixes.

- (2) The operational definition of (postverbal) inner aspectual elements
- A morpheme following the verbal root; which (\rightarrow postverbal)
 - Contributes to aspectual meaning; (\rightarrow aspectual)
 - Can be followed by the perfective suffix *咗 -zo*; and (\neq outer aspect)
 - Cannot undergo verb doubling alone and/or together with the verbal root. (\neq RVCs)

The definition in (2) gives 14 inner aspectual elements, listed in (3) with the aspectual contribution briefly described. I will go through each part of the definition below.

- (3) Postverbal inner aspectual elements in Cantonese
 (Cheung 1972/2007:113–115, Matthews & Yip 1994:210–221, Tang 2015:71–89)
- dou* (in tone 2) (到/倒) ‘arrive’: Achievement
 E.g., *wan-dou* (搵到) ‘found’ (Fang 2003, Huang 2021, Lai & Pang 2023)
 - zoek* (著) ‘be on target’: Achievement
 E.g., *fan-zoek* (瞓著) ‘slept’
 - gin* (見) ‘see (vs. look)’: Achievement, successful perception
 E.g., *teng-gin* (聽見) ‘heard (vs. listened)’
 - seng* (成) ‘succeed’: Achievement, successful action
 E.g., *joek-seng* (約成) ‘succeeded in making an appointment’

- e. *can* (親) ‘(lit.) intimate’: Achievement, with adversative results
E.g., *daa-can* ‘injured by hitting’ (Gu & Yip 2004, Sio 2020)
- f. *jyun* (完) ‘finish’: Completive
E.g., *sik-jyun* (食完) ‘finished eating’
- g. *hou* (好) ‘good’: Completive with a “properly-finished” flavor
E.g., *zou-hou* (做好) ‘done’
- h. *dim* (掂) ‘all right’: Completive with a “properly-finished” flavor
E.g., *gaau-dim* (搞掂) ‘finished, settled’
- i. *hei* (起) ‘finish, ready, (lit.) lift’: Completive with a “ready” flavor
E.g., *waak-hei* (畫起) ‘finished drawing’ (Chor 2007)
- j. *lok* (落) ‘finish (a long time ago), (lit.) fall’: Completive, temporally distant
E.g., *gaau-lok* (教落) ‘taught way back then’ (Cheng 1998)
- k. *zyu* (住) ‘hold’: Continuative states, for verbs of attachment
E.g., *kam-zyu* (冚住) ‘cover still’
- l. *sat* (實) ‘firm’: Continuative states
E.g., *mong-sat* (望實) ‘keep looking’
- m. *ding* (定) ‘(lit.) steady’: Doing something in advance
E.g., *zyu-ding* (煮定) ‘cook in advance’ (Wong 2018)
- n. *gwo* (過) ‘(lit.) pass’: Doing something again to fix undesirable outcomes
E.g., *cungsan se-gwo* (重新寫過) ‘write again’ (Chen & Lin 2006, Liu & Yip 2023)

First, all these elements are postverbal (= (2a)). They encode aspectual meaning (= (2b)) by either indicating the eventuality or imposing a viewpoint on it, including achievement (3a-3e), completives (3f-3j), and continuation of states (3k-3l).² Some come with additional flavors (mostly from the literal meaning of the morpheme), such as the “properly done” flavor of *hou* (好) ‘(lit.) good’ or the “successfully done” flavor of *seng* (成) ‘(lit.) succeed’.

There are two special cases: *ding* (定) in (3m) with an “in advance” meaning, and *gwo* (過) in (3n) with an “again” meaning (to be distinguished with the experiential *-gwo* 過). Both of them presuppose some situation/event other than the current one: a prospective event for *ding* (定), for example, cooking in advance of going to work in (3m); and a previous event for *gwo* (過), which is also a writing event in (3n). They do not seem to impose a particular viewpoint on the event structure. Nevertheless, they both have requirements on the

² How completives can be distinguished from achievement markers as well as perfective aspect is a non-trivial issue. As well-known, perfective aspect in Chinese only indicates endpoints rather than completion of an event as in (i), unlike English. Similarly, achievement markers like *dou* (到) in (ii) also do not indicate completion. A thorough discussion is however beyond the scope of this paper, and readers are referred to Smith (1994).

(i) 我寫咗一封信，但未寫完。

Ngo se-**zo** jat-fung seon, daan mei se-**jyun**.
1SG write-PFV one-CL letter but not.yet write-COMPL

Lit.: ‘#I wrote a letter, but haven’t finished writing (it).’ (infelicitous in English)

(ii) 我聽到一首歌，但未聽完(全首)。

Ngo teng-**dou** jat-sau go, daan mei teng-**jyun** (cyun-sau).
1SG hear-ACHV one-CL song but not.yet hear-COMPL whole-CL
‘I heard a song, but haven’t finished hearing/listening (the whole song).’

eventualities of the predicates they attach to: [+durative] and [+dynamic] for *ding* (定) (Wong 2018), and [+dynamic] for *gwo* (過). Thus, I regard them as aspectual elements as well.³

Note that a number of elements in (3) have other uses or homophonous counterparts. For example, *dou* (到) has a capacity modal use, as in *co-dou ng-go jan* (坐到五個人) ‘able to have 5 people sitting’ (e.g., Huang 2021). *Zoek* (著) has a suffixal use with unintentionality (Lai & Chin 2018), as in *m-siusam jyu-zoek keoi* (唔小心遇著佢) ‘met him/her unintentionally’. Also, there is another *-can* (親) expressing universal quantification on events like *juk-can zau tung* (郁親就痛) ‘feel hurt once (you) move’ (Zhan 1958, P. Lee 2017, Yip 2020b, 2022). *Zyu* (住) is usually regarded as a durative aspect suffix as in *sik-zyu faan* (食住飯) ‘eating rice’, but it is a phase complement when with “verbs of attachment”, like *kam* (冚) ‘cover’ and *pou* (抱) ‘hug’ (a distinction dated back to Cheung 1972/2007:158-162).⁴ *Hei* (起) has a special converbal use requiring a following clause as in *gong-hei zau nau* (講起就癲) ‘become mad once mentioning it’ (see Tang 2018, 2022; Yip 2019, 2022 for converbal suffixes in Cantonese), where *hei* indicates inchoative aspect. Similarly, *lok* (落) conveys inchoative aspect when used in middle-like constructions like *sik-lok m-co* (食落唔錯) ‘it tastes (lit. eats) good’ (Cheng 1998, Shi 2003, N. Lee 2016). Moreover, both *hei* (起) and *lok* (落) have a directional complement use, as in *ling-hei* (拎起) ‘pick up’ and *sik-lok tou* (食落肚) ‘(lit.) eat down (to) stomach’. On the other hand, *ding* (定) has a RVC use as in *kei-ding(-ding)* (企定/企定定) ‘stand steadily’ (Wong 2018). Lastly, it is well known that *gwo* (過) is also an experiential suffix as in *lai-gwo* (嚟過) ‘have come before’, an outer aspectual element. This paper only focuses on the inner aspectual use and remains neutral to whether these other uses are polysemous (i.e., still the same morpheme) or homophonous (i.e., already a different morpheme).

The definitions (2a-b) (postverbal elements with aspectual contribution) are necessary conditions rather than sufficient ones for inner aspectual elements. While the primary meaning RVCs is the lexical meaning, such as *baau* (飽) ‘full’ in *sik-baau* (食飽) ‘eat and become full’ and *sei* (死) ‘die’ in *daa-sei* (打死) ‘beat to death’, they have a (secondary) aspectual restriction [+telic] (either accomplishment or achievement). The restriction, however, stems from the very nature of resultatives: having a result entails a natural endpoint of the event. The restriction is also related to the eventualities of the RVCs themselves. For example, since *sei* (死) is an instant event (or a change of state), *daa-sei* (打死) is achievement, as opposed to accomplishment *sik-baau* (食飽) where *baau* (飽) is a stative predicate. In contrast, the inner aspectual elements in (3) do not lexically encode a (clear) result of the event (even for *can* 親, whose result is underspecified), but they primarily indicate the temporal structure of a situation. There is hence a principled difference between the aspectual contribution by inner aspect and by RVCs.

Second, regarding definition (2c), all inner aspectual elements can be followed by the perfective suffix *-zo* (咗), just like RVCs, such as *sik-baau-zo* (食飽咗) ‘ate and became full’ (see Cheung 1972/2007). What (2c) differentiates is the position of inner aspect from that of outer aspect: they occupy different postverbal slots, which structurally correspond to different syntactic positions. The examples are given in (4).⁵

³ In traditional grammar (e.g., Cheung 1972/2007, Gao 1980, Chang 1996), “again” is often regarded as a type of aspect, termed “repetitive aspect” (重行體/多回體), and relatedly “resumptive aspect” (回復體), such as *-faan* (翻). For a comparison between *-faan* (翻) and repetitive *gwo* (過), see Liu & Yip (2023).

⁴ There is a similar split for Mandarin *-zhe* (著), see Yuan (1993) and Tsai (2008).

⁵ The source URL links of the internet examples are provided below, accessed on 2022-6-23. (4c):<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=57s8tFuEXbU>

- (4) -*Zo* (咗) suffixation
- a. 阿明攞到咗一個 offer。 (Huang 2021:4)
 Aaming lou-**dou-zo** jat-go ofa.
 Ming get-ACHV-PFV one-CL offer
 ‘Ming got an offer.’
- b. 佢瞓咗。 (Cheung 2007:114)
 Keoi fan-**zoek-zo**.
 3SG sleep-ACHV-PFV
 ‘He has slept.’
- c. 佢係夢見咗自己係一隻蝴蝶嗎? (Video caption, 2021-2-10)
 Keoi hai mung-**gin-zo** zigei hai jat-ze wudip maa3?
 3SG be dream-ACHV-PFV self be one-CL butterfly SFP
 ‘Did he dream that he became a butterfly?’
- d. 又係一個傾下傾下又傾成咗嘅 Project 啦。 (Social media, 2020-10-8)
 Jauhai jat-go king-haa-king-haa jau king-**seng-zo** ge pozek laa1.
 again.be one-CL talk-PROG-talk-PROG again talk-ACHV-PFV GE project SFP
 ‘Just another (business) project that we managed to strike over time.’
- e. 你嚇親咗佢。 (Matthews & Yip 1994:228)
 Nei haak-**can-zo** keoi.
 2SG scare-ACHV-PFV 3SG
 ‘You scared her.’
- f. 食完咗飯好耐嘍! (Cheung 2007:149)
 sik-**jyun-zo** faan hou-noi lo3!
 eat-compl-PFV rice very-long SFP
 ‘(I) have finished my meal for quite some time!’
- g. 以為做好咗心理準備。 (Social media, 2021-6-23)
 Jiwai zou-**hou-zo** samlei zeonbei.
 think do-COMPL-PFV mental preparation
 ‘(I) thought (I was) mentally prepared.’
- h. 單 case 我搞掂咗嚟嘞。 (Words.hk)
 Daan case ngo gaau-**dim-zo** gaa3 laak3.
 CL case 1SG tackle-COMPL-PFV SFP SFP
 ‘I have finished this case.’

(4d):<https://www.facebook.com/stationerylo/photos/a.852095568464119/1314818108858527/?type=3>

(4g):<https://pages.facebook.com/1835535343424298/photos/a.1856762237968275/2779070852404071/?type=3&source=48>

(4h):<https://words.hk/zidin/%E6%8E%82>

(4i):https://m.facebook.com/szetosifu/photos/a.276853775694116/1097213856991433/?type=3&locale2=zh_CN

(4j):https://maylibibi.blogspot.com/2009/07/bibi_2573.html

(4k):<https://www.am730.com.hk/%E5%A8%9B%E6%A8%82/%E6%BB%95%E9%BA%97%E5%90%8D%E8%B7%8C%E6%96%B75%E6%A2%9D%E8%82%8B%E9%AA%A8-%E9%9D%A0%E9%A3%9F%E5%97%8E%E5%95%A1%E6%AD%A2%E7%97%9B%E9%96%8B%E5%B7%A5-/39339>

(4l):https://m.facebook.com/szetosifu/photos/a.276853775694116/1097213856991433/?type=3&locale2=zh_CN

(4m):<https://es.restaurantguru.com/%E6%99%AE%E6%B4%B1-Hong-Kong>

- i. 我幅畫終於畫起咗。 (Social media, 2016-3-17)
 Ngo fuk waak zungjyu waa-**hei-zo**.
 1SG CL drawing eventually draw-COMPL-PFV
 ‘My painting is finally done.’
- j. 我返工之前 (...) 煮落咗湯底。 (Blog, 2009-7-12)
 Ngo faangung zicin (...) zyu-**lok-zo** tongdai.
 1SG go.to.work before cook-COMPL-PFV soup.base
 ‘Before going to work, I have already cooked the broth.’
- k. 肋骨插住咗個肺。 (News, 2020-2-6)
 Laakgwat caap-**zyu-zo** go fai.
 rib puncture-CONT-PFV CL lung
 ‘a rib punctured the lung and got stucked.’
- l. 難以置信咁望實咗自己部手機。 (Creative writing, 2021-12-26)
 Naanjiziseon-gam mong-**sat-zo** zigei bou saugei.
 unbelievable-ly stare-CONT-PFV self CL cell.phone
 ‘(He) stares at his cell phone unbelievably.’
- m. 同埋好夠熱，唔會好似煮定咗好耐。 (Food guide, 2022-4-27)
 Tungmaai hou gau-jit, m-wu houci zyu-**ding-zo** hou-noi.
 and very enough-hot not-will seem.like cook-in.advance-PFV very-long
 ‘It’s also hot enough and doesn’t look like being prepared a long time ago.’
- n. 重新寫過咗《拜仁頌》嘅第三段歌詞。 (Liu & Yip 2023:101)
 Cungsan se-**gwo-zo** Baaijanzung ge daisaam dyun goci.
 again write-again-PFV *Bayernhymne* GE third line lyrics
 ‘Rewrote the third line of the lyrics of *Bayernhymne*.’

Outer aspectual suffixes, on the other hand, cannot be stacked (Cheung 1972/2007). Progressive *-gan* (緊) cannot be suffixed by *-zo* (咗) (for obvious reasons of aspectual conflicts), as well as experiential *-gwo* (過), as shown in (5a-b).⁶ Recall that *-zyu* (住) has an outer aspectual counterpart—this durative *-zyu* (住) also resists *-zo* (咗) suffixation, as in (5c).

(5) Failure of *-zo* (咗) suffixation

- a. *佢已經睇緊咗呢本書。
 Keoi jiging tai-**gan-zo** ni-bun syu.
 3SG already read-PROG-PFV this-CL book
 Int.: ‘S/he has been already reading this book.’
- b. *佢已經睇過咗呢本書。
 Keoi jiging tai-**gwo-zo** ni-bun syu.
 3SG already read-EXP-PFV this-CL book
 Int.: ‘S/he has been already read this book.’

⁶ This is different from Mandarin, where experiential *-guo* (過) can be followed by (suffixal) perfective *-le* (了):

(i) 他已經看過了那本書了。
 Ta yijing kan-**guo-le** nei-ben shu le.
 3SG already read-EXP-PFV that-CL book SFP
 ‘S/he has already read that book.’

(Gu 1995:52)

- c. *佢已經食住咗飯。
 Keoi jiging sik-zyu-zo faan.
 3SG already read-DUR-PFV rice
 Int.: ‘S/he has been already eating.’

Last but not least, the definition (2d), verb doubling, serves as an extremely powerful tool to tease inner (and outer) aspectual elements apart from RVCs. To begin with, verbs in Cantonese may be doubled for contrastive topicality (T. T.-M. Lee 2022, 2024a).

- (6) 做, 佢係會做嘅。
Zou, keoi hai wui **zou** ge2.
 do 3SG be will do SFP
 ‘As for doing, s/he will do.’ (T. T.-M. Lee 2024a:43)

The doubled verbs must be “bare” and cannot carry the outer aspectual suffix *-zo* (咗) along in (7a-b) (T. T.-M. Lee 2024b). In contrast, RVCs can be carried along, as in (7b).

- (7) Contrast in verb doubling: outer aspect vs. RVCs
- a. {食/*食咗}, 佢係已經食咗個碗飯嘅。
 {**Sik/ *sik-zo**}, keoi hai jiging **sik-zo** go-wun faan ge2.
 eat eat-PFV 3SG be already eat-PFV that-CL rice SFP
 ‘As for eating, s/he has already eaten that bowl of rice.’
- b. {食/食飽/*食飽咗}, 佢係已經食飽咗嘅。
 {**Sik/ sik-baau/ *sik-baau-zo**}, keoi hai jiging **sik-baau-zo** ge2.
 eat eat-full eat-full-PFV 3SG be already eat-full-PFV SFP
 ‘As for eating (and becoming full), s/he has already eaten and become full.’

Importantly, inner aspectual elements are degraded to be doubled along. This is illustrated with *dou* (到) (for achievement), *jyun* (完) (for completives), *zyu* (住) (for continuatives), *ding* (定), and *gwo* (過) in (8). Some of them are arguably more acceptable than doubling with suffixes, but the crucial point is that they are still not as natural as doubling with RVCs in (7b).

- (8) Failure of doubling along with the verb
- a. {執/??執到}, 佢尋日係執到一張銀紙嘅。
 {**Zap/ ??zaap-dou**}, keoi camjat hai **zaap-dou** jat-zoeng nganzi ge2.
 pick pick-ACHV 3SG yesterday be pick-ACHV one-CL bill SFP
 ‘As for picking up, s/he has picked up a money bill yesterday.’
- b. {食/*食完}, 佢係已經食完個碗飯嘅。
 {**Sik/ *sik-jyun**}, keoi hai jiging **sik-jyun** go-wun faan ge2.
 eat eat-COMPL 3SG be already eat-COMPL that-CL rice SFP
 ‘As for eating, s/he has finished eaten that bowl of rice.’
- c. {抱/?抱住}, 個媽媽係抱住個 B 嘅。
 {**Pou/ ?pou-zyu**}, go mama hai **pou-zyu** go bi ge2.
 hold hold-CONT that mother be hold-CONT CL baby SFP
 ‘As for holding, the mother is holding the baby.’

- d. {行/??行定}, 佢係有行定入去先嘅。
 {**Haang/??haang-ding**}, keoi hai jau **haang-ding** japheoi sin1 ge2.
 walk walk-in.advance 3SG be have walk-in.advance inside SFP SFP
 ‘As for walking, s/he has walked inside (there) in advance.’
- e. {寫/*寫過}, 佢係已經重新寫過篇文嘅。
 {**Se/ *se-gwo**}, keoi hai jiging cungsan **se-gwo** pin man ge2.
 write write-again 3SG be already again write-again CL paper SFP
 ‘As for writing, s/he has already written the article again.’

An even more striking contrast is whether the postverbal elements may be doubled alone without the verbal roots.⁷ While it is possible for RVCs as in (9a), it is clearly impossible for inner aspectual elements in (9b), let alone outer aspectual suffixes in (9c).

(9) Contrasts in doubling alone without the verb

- a. 飽, 佢係已經食飽咗嘅。
Baau, keoi hai jiging **sik-baau-zo** ge2.
 full 3SG be already eat-full-PFV SFP
 ‘As for becoming full, s/he has already eaten and become full.’
- b. *完, 佢係已經食完嗰碗飯嘅。
 ***Jyun**, keoi hai jiging **sik-jyun** go-wun faan ge2.
 COMPL 3SG be already eat-COMPL that-CL rice SFP
 ‘As for eating, s/he has finished eaten that bowl of rice.’
- c. *咗, 佢係已經食咗嗰碗飯嘅。
 *-**Zo**, keoi hai jiging **sik-zo** go-wun faan ge2.
 PFV 3SG be already eat-PFV that-CL rice SFP
 ‘As for eating, s/he has already eaten that bowl of rice.’

Note that the failure to be doubled alone is a general property of all inner aspectual elements regardless of their grammatical status. As will be discussed in Section 3, some of them (e.g., *zoek* 著) are verbal complements rather than suffixes. As shown in (10), however, all the inner aspectual elements cannot be doubled alone without the verb.

(10) Failure to double alone without the verb

- a. {夢/*到/*見}, 佢係尋晚夢{到/見}老豆嘅。
 {**Mung/*dou/*gin**}, keoi hai cammaan **mung{-dou/gin}** loudau ge2.
 dream ACHV 3SG be last.night dream-ACHV dad SFP
 ‘As for dreaming, s/he dreamt of Dad last night.’
- b. {瞓/*著}, 佢係瞓著咗嘅。
 {**Fan/*zoek**}, keoi hai **fan-zoek-zo** ge2.
 sleep ACHV 3SG be sleep-ACHV-PFV SFP
 ‘As for sleeping, s/he has fallen asleep.’
- c. {傾/*成}, 佢係傾成咗個 project 嘅。
 {**King/*seng**}, keoi hai **king-seng-zo** go pozek ge2.
 talk ACHV 3SG be talk-ACHV-PFV CL project SFP
 ‘As for bargaining, s/he has successfully bargained for the project.’

⁷ I thank Kiki Liu and Fulang Chen for drawing my attention to this contrast in Mandarin.

- d. {嚇/*親}, 我係嚇親咗佢嘅。
 {**Haak/*can**}, ngo hai **haak-can-zo** keoi ge2.
 scare ACHV 1SG be scare-ACHV-PFV 3SG SFP
 ‘As for scaring, I have scared him/her.’
- e. {做/*好/*掂/*起}, 佢係已經做{好/掂/起}呢樣嘞。
 {**Zou/*hou/*dim/*hei**}, keoi hai jiging **zou{-hou/dim/hei}** ni-joeng laak3.
 do COMPL 3SG be already do-COMPL this-CL SFP
 ‘As for doing, s/he has already done this.’
- f. {教/*落}, 老豆係一早有教落嘅, 但係.....
 {**Gaau/*lok**}, loudau hai jatzou jau **gaau-lok** ge2, daanhai...
 teach COMPL dad be early have teach-COMPL SFP but
 ‘As for teaching, Dad did teach about this long time ago, but...’
- g. {望/*住/*實}, 佢係有望{住/實}你嘅, 但係.....
 {**Mong/*zyu/*sat**}, keoi hai jau **mong{-zyu/sat}** nei ge2, daanhai...
 watch CONT CONT 3SG be have watch-CONT 2SG SFP but
 ‘As for staring, s/he is staring at you, but ...’
- h. {行/*定}, 佢係有行定入去先嘅。
 {**Haang/*ding**}, keoi hai jau **haang-ding** japheoi sin1 ge2.
 walk in.advance 3SG be have walk-in.advance inside SFP SFP
 ‘As for walking, s/he has walked inside (there) in advance.’
- i. {寫/*過}, 佢係已經重新寫過篇文嘅。
 {**Se/ *gwo**}, keoi hai jiging cungsan **se-gwo** pin man ge2.
 write again 3SG be already again write-again CL paper SFP
 ‘As for writing, s/he has already written the article again.’

Table 1 summarizes the contrasting properties of inner aspectual elements with RVCs and outer aspectual elements.

Postverbal elements	Attached to a verbal root?	Primarily aspectual meaning?	-Zo (咗) suffixation?	Doubling (alone and/or with the verb)?
RVCs	YES	NO (only secondary)	YES	YES
Inner aspect	YES	YES	YES	NO
Outer aspect	YES	YES	NO	NO

Table 1: Contrasting properties of inner aspect with RVCs and outer aspect

3. Phase complements or verbal suffixes?

After identifying the inner aspectual elements, the next question is what their grammatical status is. As elements attaching to the verbal root, there are at least two possibilities: verbal complements or verbal suffixes. Usually, most inner aspectual elements are regarded as the former as phase complements, PCs. Nevertheless, as we will see below, some should be treated (and even have been treated so in the literature) as verbal suffixes.

The traditional criteria for verbal suffixes are listed in (11), which are from Cheung (1972/2007) and have been influential in Cantonese linguistics (e.g., adopted by P. Lee 2004,

2012 and Tang 2015). Note that some of the criteria might be questionable, such as (11d). Suffix stacking is indeed possible in Cantonese with *saai* (晒) (Tang 2003, 2015), such as *sik-gwo-saai* (食過晒) ‘has eaten all’. I thus discard this criterion.⁸

- (11) The traditional criteria for verbal suffixes from Cheung (1972/2007)
- a. Productivity/flexibility: suffixes can combine with a wide range of verbal roots.
 - b. Boundness: suffixes are bound morphemes.
 - c. Vacuity: suffixes lack lexical meaning.
 - d. Exclusivity: suffixes cannot be stacked. *(not considered in this paper)*
 - e. Potential form: suffixes cannot participate in V-*dak/m-X* forms.
 - f. Following VO and VR compounds: suffixes can attach to Verb-Object and Verb-Resultative compounds. (i.e., suffixes may follow RVCs.)

Let us begin with (11a). Some inner aspectual elements like *dou* (到), *jyun* (完), *ding* (定) and *gwo* (過) can attach to almost any [+dynamic] and/or [+durative] predicates (i.e., excluding stative *hung* 紅 ‘be red’ and instant *sei* 死 ‘die’). *Hou* (好) and *dim* (掂) are also quite productive, but cannot attach to non-volitional or uncontrollable predicates: compare *fan-jyun* (瞓完) ‘finished sleeping’ and **fan-hou/dim* (*瞓好/掂). *Hei* (起) and *lok* (落) only attach to transitive verbs, but not all of them; **ji-hei/lok* (*醫起/落) ‘(Int.) healed someone’ is not acceptable.

Other elements are however very restricted. For example, *gin* (見) only attaches to verbs of perception such as *tai-gin* (睇見) ‘saw’, *mong-gin* (望見) ‘saw’, *teng-gin* (聽見) ‘heard’, and even reject some other perceptual verbs like **man-gin* (*聞見) ‘(Int.) smelled’. *Zoek* (著) similarly is very limited and almost only attaches to verbs of sleeping. *Zyu* (住) and *sat* (實) only combine with a few verbs of “attachment” as discussed above. Some are not as unproductive as these four, but still quite limited. *Seng* (成) is also an achievement marker like *dou* (到), but it cannot attach to some of the verbs that *dou* (到) can attach to, like **zap-seng* (*執成) ‘(Int.) successfully pick something up’. *Can* (親) usually attaches to verbs with a specific manner like *zuk-can* 濁親 ‘choked’ (see Gu & Yip 2004). The inner aspectual elements are roughly classified into four groups according to their productivity in (12).

- (12) Productivity of inner aspectual elements
- a. Very productive (4): *dou* (到), *jyun* (完), *ding* (定), *gwo* (過)
 - b. Relatively productive (4): *hou* (好), *dim* (掂), *hei* (起), *lok* (落)
 - c. Relatively unproductive (2): *seng* (成), *can* (親)
 - d. Very unproductive (4): *gin* (見), *zoek* (著), *zyu* (住), *sat* (實)

Now consider (11b), whether inner aspectual elements are bound morphemes. It is not an easy question. Even though some elements have a free counterpart, it is not clear whether that is the same morpheme or a different one. There are however several clear cases. *Jyun* (完) clearly can be a free morpheme with exactly the same “finish” meaning, as in *tou hei jyun-zo* (套戲完咗) ‘the movie has ended’. In contrast, *dou* (到/倒) in tone 2, which probably comes from *dou* (到) ‘arrive’ in tone 3 with the tone changed, no longer can stand alone. *Seng* (成)

⁸ While (11e) holds almost across-the-board, there is a potential counter-example to it: *-saai* (晒) can participate in potential forms, such as *sik-dak/m-saai* (食得/唔晒) ‘can/cannot eat (them) all’. Nevertheless, *-saai* (晒) is arguably a verbal suffix (see extensive arguments in P. Lee 2012:26-30).

comes from *sing* (成) in *singgun* 成功 ‘success’, but *sing* (成) itself is also bound. It is also clear that *zoek* (著), *can* (親), *hei* (起), *lok* (落), *zyu* (住), *ding* (定) and *gwo* (過) lack free forms of the same meaning. Cases fall in the middle are *gin* (見), *hou* (好), *dim* (掂), and *sat* (實), which seem to retain some but not all the lexical meaning of their free forms.

(13) Boundness of inner aspectual elements

- a. Free (1): *jyun* (完)
- b. Maybe free or bound (4): *gin* (見), *hou* (好), *dim* (掂), *sat* (實)
- c. Bound (9): *dou* (到), *zoek* (著), *seng* (成), *can* (親), *hei* (起), *lok* (落), *zyu* (住), *ding* (定) and *gwo* (過)

As for (11c) vacuity, we have already established that inner aspectual elements are different from RVCs in that the former conveys lexical meaning, but the latter conveys aspectual meaning. It is however true that some inner aspectual elements may retain a certain extent of the original lexical meaning, such as *seng* (成) from *singgun* 成功 ‘success’. *Jyun* (完), unfortunately, is simply untestable: it has aspectual meaning even in its free form.

(14) Vacuity of inner aspectual elements

- a. Aspectual, with little or no lexical meaning (9): *dou* (到), *zoek* (著), *jyun* (完), *can* (親), *hei* (起), *lok* (落), *zyu* (住), *ding* (定), and *gwo* (過)
- b. Retaining some lexical meaning (5): *gin* (見), *seng* (成), *hou* (好), *dim* (掂), *sat* (實)

Criterion (11d) exclusivity is not considered as a valid one for the reasons discussed above. Moreover, all the inner aspectual elements, as their defining property in (2), can be followed by perfective suffix *-zo* (咗). We will see however that some should be verbal suffixes.

Criterion (11e) refers to whether the verbal root and the postverbal element can be “infixated” by *-dak/m-* (得/唔) ‘able/not’ to form the so-called potential forms (能性式/可能補語), which is possible for verbal complements but not for verbal suffixes. As shown in (15), most inner aspectual elements allow *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation. The few that reject it are *hei* (起), *lok* (落), *ding* (定), and *gwo* (過). It is thus quite strong evidence that these four are verbal suffixes. The other 10 elements, in contrast, are more verbal-complement-like.

(15) Potential forms (*-dak/m-* 得/唔 ‘able/not’ infixation)⁹

- a. 有時都攞唔到，好似今日咁多人，就未必攞得到。(Video caption, 2021-2-10)
 Jausi dou lo-m-**dou**, houci gamjat gam-do jan,
 sometimes also get-not-ACHV like today that-many person
 zau meibit lo-dak-**dou**.
 then uncertain get-able-ACHV
 ‘Sometimes (you) cannot get it. When there are as many people like today, it’s not certain that (you) can get it.’

⁹ The source URL links of the internet examples are provided below. (15a) and (15k) were accessed on 2022-6-23, and (15g) was accessed on 2024-12-24.

(15a): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=57s8tFuEXbU>

(15g): <https://www.dcard.tw/f/hkmacgirl/p/254459847>

(15k): <https://www.facebook.com/HKBusChannel/posts/2078493698854987/>

- b. 佢瞓{得/唔}著
Keoi fan-**{dak/m}**-**zoek**
3SG sleep-able/not-ACHV
'He can(not) sleep.'
- c. 睇{得/唔}見
Tai-**{dak/m}**-**gin**
see-able/not-ACHV
'can(not) see'
- d. 我估今晚去得成。 (Matthews & Yip 1994:221)
Ngo gu gammaan heoi-**dak-seng**.
1SG guess tonight go-able-ACHV
'I think we'll manage to go tonight'
- e. 嚇唔親你添。
Haak-**m-can** nei timl.
scare-not-ACHV 2SG SFP
'(I) couldn't scare you.'
- f. 食{得/唔}完
Sik-**{dak/m}**-**jyun**
eat-able/not-COMPL
'can(not) finish eating'
- g. 話我一定鎖唔好隻門 (Discord, 2024-1-19)
Waa ngo jatding so-**m-hou** zek mun
say 1SG definitely lock-not-COMPL CL door
'Say that I definitely cannot lock the door properly.'
- h. 搞{得/唔}掂
Gaau-**{dak/m}**-**dim**
do-able/not-COMPL
'can(not) settle'
- i. *畫{得/唔}起幅畫¹⁰
*Waak-**{dak/m}**-**hei** fuk waa
draw-able/not-COMPL CL drawing
Int.: 'can(not) finish the drawing'
- j. *煮{得/唔}落湯底¹¹
*Zyu-**{dak/m}**-**lok** tongdai
cook-able/not-COMPL soup.base
Int.: 'can(not) cook the broth in advance'
- k. 香港啲公司到呢個年代仲以為可以冚得住啲消息。 (Video caption, 2021-2-10)
Hoenggong di gungsi dou ni-go nindoi
Hong Kong CL.PL company to this-CL era
zung jiwai hoji kam-**dak-zyu** di siusik.
still think can cover-able-CONT CL.PL news
'How could the HK companies think that they can cover up the news nowadays?'

¹⁰ Compare: directional complement *ling*-**{dak/m}**-*hei* (拎{得/唔}起) 'can(not) pick up'.

¹¹ Compare: directional complement *sik*-**{dak/m}**-*lok* (食{得/唔}落) 'can(not) eat/swallow'.

1. 揸{得/唔}實
Gam-**{dak/m}**-**sat**
hold-able/not-CONT
'can(not) hold still'
- m. *煮{得/唔}定餐飯¹²
*Zyu-**{dak/m}**-**ding** caan faan
cook-**{dak/m}**-in.advance CL rice
Int.: 'can(not) cook the meal in advance'
- n. *重新寫{得/唔}過篇文
*Cungsan se-**{dak/m}**-**gwo** pin man
again write-able/not-again CL paper
Int.: 'can(not) write the article again'

Regarding the last criterion (11f), most inner aspectual elements (10 in total) cannot follow an RVC as in (16), a canonical property of being a PC given that verbal complements can never stack (except directional complements).¹³ *Ding* (定) and *gwo* (過) resist *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation, and, as expected, can follow RVCs, further supporting their suffixal status. *Hei* (起) and *lok* (落), however, cannot follow RVCs, although they also resist *-dak/m-* infixation. Yet, it might be due to an independent constraint that *hei* (起) and *lok* (落) only accept monosyllabic verbal roots: compare *cyulei-jyun/hou* (處理完/好) 'finished processing' and **cyulei-hei/lok* (*處理起/落). The puzzling cases are *dou* (到) and *jyun* (完). While they accept *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation (i.e., PC-like), they can also follow RVCs (i.e., suffix-like). Given that they are highly productive and indicate primarily aspectual meaning, it is possible that they are mid-way to verbal suffixes.¹⁴

(16) Following RVCs

- a. 後尾我哋同康華終於打開到話題。 (News, 2022-1-22)
Haumei ngodei tung Hong Waa zungjyu **daa-hoi-dou** waatai.
afterwards 1PL with Akina Hong eventually hit-open-ACHV topic
'We eventually opened up the topic with Akina Hong.'
- b. *瞓寐著
***Fan-lam-zoek**
sleep-deep-ACHV
Int.: 'slept deeply'

¹² Compare: RVC *co-{dak/m}-ding* (坐{得/唔}定) 'can(not) sit firmly'.

¹³ The source URL links of the internet examples are provided below, accessed on 2022-6-23.

(16a): <https://www.singtaousa.com/3894174>

(16f): <https://shorturl.at/aAS79>

(16m): <https://filmot.com/sidebyside/HeWgxZeM1GY/zh-HK/zh->

HK/Chinese+%28Hong+Kong%29/Chinese+%28Hong+Kong%29/%E3%80%90%E8%A9%A6%E7%94%A8%E8%A9%95%E6%B8%AC%E3%80%91%E5%86%87%E4%BA%BA%E8%A7%80%E5%A1%98%E5%AF%A6%E6%B8%ACSIGMA+24mm+f3.5+DG+DN/%E8%86%A0%E6%94%9D%E7%8F%BE%E5%A0%B4

¹⁴ It is even possible that *dou* (到) and *jyun* (完) are verbal suffixes given that another verbal suffix, *-saai* (晒), also allows *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation.

- c. *睇清見
***Tai-cing-gin**
 see-clear-ACHV
 Int.: ‘saw clearly’
- d. *book 爆成呢間餐廳
***Buk-baa-seng** ni-gaan caanteng
 book-full-ACHV this-CL restaurant
 Int.: ‘successfully made this restaurant fully booked’
- e. *打傷親呢個人
***Daa-soeng-can** ni-go jan
 hit-hurt-ACHV this-CL person
 Int.: ‘beat and injured this guy’
- f. 蒸熟完就可以攪碎 (Food guide, 2014-7-18)
Zing-suk-jyun zau hoji gaau-seoi
 steam-cooked-COMPL then may stir-shattered
 ‘after finished steaming it, you can break them into pieces’
- g. ??省靚好個招牌
??saang-leng-hou go ziupaai
 wipe-pretty-COMPL CL sign
 Int.: ‘made the fame better’
- h. *搞清楚掂
***gaau-cingco-dim**
 make-clear-COMPL
 Int.: ‘made it clear’
- i. *寫靚起幅字
***se-leng-hei** fuk zi
 write-pretty-COMPL CL word
 Int.: ‘finished the calligraphy artwork’
- j. *煲滾落個湯底
***Bou-gwan-lok** go tongdai
 boil-boiled-COMPL CL soup.base
 Int.: ‘boiled the broth long time ago’
- k. *揸平住/實張紙
***gam-ping-{zyu/sat}** zoeng zi
 hold-flattened-CONT CL paper
 Int.: ‘held and flattened the paper’
- l. 拆走定個書架 (Tang 2015:78)
Caak-zau-ding go syugaa
 remove-away-in.advance CL book.shelf
 ‘removed the book shelf in advance’
- m. 真係可以再放大過呢啲位置。 (Video, 2020-12-27)
 Zanhai hoji zoi **fong-daai-gwo** ni di waizi.
 really may again zoom-big-again this CL.PL position
 ‘We really can re-enlarge these positions.’

Table 2 summarizes the results of the above five tests on the 14 inner aspectual elements. I take *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation to be a hallmark property for phase complements, and the ability to follow RVCs for verbal suffixes. There are in total 4 verbal suffixes and 8 PCs, and 2 intermediate cases: *dou* (到) and *jyun* (完). The results of these two tests are generally consistent with their productivity (lower for PCs; higher for suffixes). For boundness and vacuity, there seems to be a one-way correlation: suffixes are all bound and all lack lexical meaning, whereas bound elements without lexical meaning are not necessarily suffixes (e.g., *can* 親).

Inner aspect	Productivity	Bound?	Vacuous?	<i>-dak/m-</i> infixing?	Following RVCs?	Status
<i>ding</i> (定)	High	YES	YES	*	OK	Suffix
<i>gwo</i> (過)	High	YES	YES	*	OK	Suffix
<i>hei</i> (起)	Mid-high	YES	YES	*	*	Suffix
<i>lok</i> (落)	Mid-high	YES	YES	*	*	Suffix
<i>dou</i> (到/倒)	High	YES	YES	OK	OK	In-between
<i>jyun</i> (完)	High	NO	YES	OK	OK	In-between
<i>hou</i> (好)	Mid-high	Maybe	NO	OK	*	PCs
<i>dim</i> (掂)	Mid-high	Maybe	NO	OK	*	PCs
<i>seng</i> (成)	Mid-low	YES	NO	OK	*	PCs
<i>can</i> (親)	Mid-low	YES	YES	OK	*	PCs
<i>zyu</i> (住)	Low	YES	YES	OK	*	PCs
<i>zoek</i> (著)	Low	YES	YES	OK	*	PCs
<i>sat</i> (實)	Low	Maybe	NO	OK	*	PCs
<i>gin3</i> (見)	Low	Maybe	NO	OK	*	PCs

Table 2: The grammatical status of inner aspectual elements

4. A formal analysis

This section offers a formal syntactic analysis of inner aspectual elements. First, I assume the split-aspect approach where there are two aspectual projections: one above νP , one below νP (Gu 1995, Tsai 2008, Huang, Li & Li 2009, Sybesma 2017, Lu, Lipták & Sybesma 2019, Yip 2020a, Tang 2022, Lee & Pan 2024; for other languages, see MacDonald 2008, Travis 2010).

(17) The split-aspect approach

[TP ... [AspP-outer **Asp**_{outer} [νP ... [AspP-inner **Asp**_{inner} [νP ...

Second, I assume the non-lexicalist approach where suffixes host a functional head and project a phrase, rather than being base-generated with the verb on big V (Tang 1998, 2003, 2006, Tsai 2001, 2008, T. T.-M. Lee 2024b; against the lexicalist approach in Gu 1993, 1995, Huang, Li & Li 2009). In other words, suffixes are not part of the verb in the lexicon. The suffixation is achieved by verb movement in the syntax. For example, the verbal root *sik* (食)

‘eat’ is base-generated at V and moves up to perfective *-zo* (咗) at Asp_{outer} to form the verb *sik-zo* (食咗) ‘ate’, as illustrated in (18).

- (18) Suffixation by syntactic verb movement
- a. [TP ... [AspP-outer **-zo** [vP ... v [AspP-inner **Asp_{inner}** [VP *sik* ‘eat’ ...]]]] (baseline)
 - b. [TP ... [AspP-outer *sik-Asp_{inner}-v-zo* [vP ... [AspP-inner [VP ...]]]] (syntax)
-
- c. *sik-∅-∅-zo* = *sik-zo* (PF)

Third, I propose that RVCs do not form a compound with the verbal root in the lexicon either. They are small clauses (SCs) taken by the verb, and undergo head movement to the verb (in a manner like V-to-V incorporation). The RVC assigns a theta-role to the silent pronoun big PRO at the specifier, which is controlled by (and thus co-referential with) the subject. To derive the *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation, I follow Cheng & Sybesma (2004) in assuming a VP-internal Modal Phrase (ModP) hosted by *-dak/m-* (得/唔). Head movement goes up in a “snowball” fashion, as in (19). I further assume the infixal status of *-dak/m-* (得/唔) so they always get inserted between RVCs and the verbal root.

- (19) RVCs as small clauses

To capture the verb doubling contrasts, I propose that only lexical heads may be doubled. Functional projections, on the other hand, cannot be doubled (see T. T.-M. Lee 2024a:41 for the failure of modals to undergo topic doubling). This explains why verbs and RVCs (i.e., lexical projections such as A or V) can be doubled, whereas aspectual elements (i.e., Asp_{inner}/Asp_{outer}) cannot.

Now, we can discuss how inner aspectual elements are represented in the syntax. As for the suffixal elements, I assume that they are base-generated at the Asp_{inner} head and attract head movement. In the case with RVCs, V moves up to Asp_{inner} and carries along the RVC. Hence, the inner aspectual suffixes follow the RVCs. When the object is present, it is base-generated at the specifier of the SC, and receives theta-roles from both the RVC and the V. The derivation is illustrated in (20).

(20) Inner aspectual suffixes follow RVCs

On the other hand, inner aspectual suffixes are within *vP*. When outer aspectual suffixes are also present, the V moves along with *AspP_inner* all the way up to *AspP_outer* above *vP*. Hence, inner aspect necessarily precedes outer aspect, capturing *-zo* (㗎) suffixation.

(21) Inner aspectual suffixes precede outer aspectual suffixes

The question that remains is how phase complements like *zoek* (著) are derived. One straightforward option is to treat them like RVCs as an SC and base-generate the SC under VP. There are however two problems. First, SCs are lexical projections like VP and AP, but PCs should host aspectual projections for their meaning, and to capture the resistance to be doubled (i.e., functional projections cannot be doubled). Second, SCs assign theta-roles to the object and/or a PRO controlled by the subject. PCs nevertheless do not assign any theta-roles.

To resolve this dilemma, I propose that there is a third aspectual projection below VP (see Tsai 2008 for similar ideas). This is illustrated in (22).

(22) Phase complements project a VP-internal AspP

In this way, the PC moves up to Mod and then V to derive the *-dak/m-* (得/唔) infixation. On the other hand, the PC projects an aspectual head and cannot be doubled. Note that for inner aspectual elements that have an intermediate status between suffixes and PCs, I suggest that they may be projected either above VPs (following RVCs) or below VPs (with *-dak/m-* 得/唔 infixation).¹⁵

5. Conclusion

To conclude, this paper has provided a detailed and systematic description of the properties of the inner aspectual elements in Cantonese. In total 14 such elements have been identified, supported by diagnostics including *-zo* (咗) suffixation and the failure to undergo verb doubling. With comprehensive investigation of the properties of these elements, including productivity, boundness, vacuity, potential forms (*-dak/m-* 得/唔 infixation) and ability to follow RVCs, it is concluded that 4 of them are verbal suffixes: *ding* (定), *gwo* (過), *hei* (起), and *lok* (落); 8 of them are phase complements: *zoek* (著), *gin* (見), *seng* (成), *can* (親), *hou* (好), *dim* (掂), *zyu* (住), and *sat* (實); and 2 of them have an intermediate status: *dou* (到) and *jyun* (完).

I also offered a formal syntactic analysis. Adopting a non-lexicalist approach, neither verbal complements nor suffixes are base-generated with the verbal root in the lexicon, but they enter syntax as different units. Suffixes host functional projections above VP, where two aspectual projections are available: Asp_{outer} above vP and Asp_{inner} below vP . The verb undergoes syntactic head movement to the aspectual suffix to form a suffixed verb. On the other hand, resultative verbal complements form small clauses that are taken by the verb, below VP. Phase complements also project $AspP_{inner}$ below VP. Both RVCs and PCs move to V, and potentially take up the infixal *-dak/m-* (得/唔) on an optional VP-internal modal projection. In this way, we obtain the formal basis for three distinctions of postverbal elements in Cantonese: (i) the verbal complement-suffix distinction: whether they are base-generated VP-internally or externally; (ii) the outer-inner aspect distinction: whether they are base-generated vP -internally or externally; (iii) the resultative-aspectual distinction: whether they head lexical projections or functional (aspectual) projections.

REFERENCES

- Chan, Wing Ming (1996) On the Theory of Aspect and Chinese Aspect Systems. Ph.D. dissertation, Cornell University.
- Chang, Song Hing (1996) Xianggang yueyu de ti [Aspects in Cantonese]. In Song Hing Chang (ed.), *Dongci de Ti [Aspects of Verbs]*. Hong Kong: T.T. Ng Chinese Language Language Research Centre, Institute of Chinese Studies, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, pp. 143–160.
- Chao, Yuen Ren (1968) *A Grammar of Spoken Chinese*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Chen, Xiaojin & Li Lin (2006) Guangzhouhua de dongtai zhuci “guo” [The Particle *gwo3* in Cantonese]. *Journal of Jinan University (Philosophy and Social Sciences)*, vol.4:118–122.

¹⁵ The current structure predicts that PCs may be stackable with inner aspectual suffixes. I leave this issue to further research.

- Cheng, Lisa L-S. & Rint Sybesma (2004) Postverbal ‘can’ in Cantonese (and Hakka) and Agree. *Linguai*, vol.114.4:419–445.
- Cheng, Ting Au (1998) Xi Guangzhouhua dongci shuyu youzhi chengfen “luo” [An Analysis of the Postverbal Element *-lok* in Cantonese]. In Ting Au Cheng & Jianhua Cai (eds.), *Guangzhouhua Yanjiu yu Jiaoxue (Disanji)* [Cantonese Research and Teaching (third volume)]. Guangzhou: Sun Yat-sen University Press, pp. 86–90.
- Cheng, Ting Au (2001) Shuo “mao” —yi Guangzhouhua wei li [On “Aspect”—A Case Study of Cantonese]. *Fangyan [Dialects]*, vol.23.1:53–59.
- Cheung, Hung-nin Samuel (1972) *Xianggang Yueyu yufa de yanjiu [Cantonese as Spoken in Hong Kong]*. Hong Kong: The Chinese University of Hong Kong.
- Cheung, Hung-nin Samuel (2007) *Xianggang Yueyu yufa de yanjiu [Cantonese as Spoken in Hong Kong] (revised edition)*. Hong Kong: The Chinese University Press.
- Chor, Winnie (2004) A Semantic and Pragmatic Analysis of Verbal Particles in Cantonese. MPhil thesis, University of Hong Kong.
- Chor, Winnie (2007) HEI – As a Completive Particle in Cantonese. In H. N. Cheung, S. H. Cheung & H. K. Chan (eds.), *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Yue Dialects*. Beijing: China Social Sciences Press, pp. 335–346.
- Comrie, Bernard (1976) *Aspect*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Fang, Xiaoyan (2003) Guangzhouhua li de dongtai zhuci “dao” [The Dynamic Auxiliary *dao* in Cantonese]. *Fangyan [Dialects]*, vol.4:352–353.
- Gao, Huanian (1980) *Guangzhou fangyan yanjiu [A Study on Guangzhou Dialects]*. Hong Kong: The Commercial Press.
- Gu, Yang (1993) Aspect Licensing and Verb Movement in Mandarin Chinese. *CUHK Papers in Linguistics*, vol.4:68–87.
- Gu, Yang (1995) Aspect Licensing, Verb Movement and Feature Checking. *Cahiers de Linguistique-Asie Orientale*, vol.24:49–83.
- Gu, Yang & Virginia Yip (2004) On the Cantonese Resultative Predicate *V-can*. *Concentric: Studies in Linguistics*, vol.30.2:35–67.
- Huang, Cheng-Teh James, Yen-Hui Audrey Li & Yafei Li (2009) *The Syntax of Chinese*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Huang, Jiahui (2021) An Analysis on the Verbal Suffix *dou2* in Cantonese. Paper presented at The Fourth Forum on Cantonese Linguistics, HKBU, May 29, 2021.
- Lai, Ryan Ka Yau & Michelle Man-Long Pang (2023) Rethinking the Description and Typology of Cantonese Causative–Resultative Constructions: A Dynamic Constructionist Lens. *Languages*, vol.8.2.151:1–48.
- Lai, Yik-Po & Andy Chi-on Chin (2018) Yueyu de dongci houzhui “zoek” [Cantonese Verbal Suffix *zoek*]. In Dah-An Ho, Yuk-man Carine Yiu, Jingtao Sun, Zhongmin Chen & Hung-nin Samuel Cheung (eds.), *Frontiers in Sinitic and Sino-Tibetan Linguistics: Studies in the Languages of China Festschrift in Honor of Professor Ting Pang-Hsin on his 80th Birthday*. Beijing: Social Sciences Academic Press, pp. 697–707.
- Lee, Nga-ting (2016) Yueyu houzhui “luo” de yufa tedian tanjiu [A Study of the Grammatical Properties of Cantonese Suffix *-lok*]. BA thesis, The Chinese University of Hong Kong.
- Lee, Peppina Po-lun (2004) Affix Quantification: A Syntax-Semantics Mapping Approach to Cantonese Suffixal Quantifiers. Ph.D. dissertation, City University of Hong Kong.
- Lee, Peppina Po-lun (2012) *Cantonese Particles and Affixal Quantification*. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Lee, Peppina Po-lun (2017) Quantification in Cantonese. In Denis Paperno & Edward L. Keenan, (eds.), *Handbook of Quantifiers in Natural Language*, vol.2:61–112. Cham: Springer.
- Lee, Thomas Hun Tak (1994) Yueyu ‘saai’ de luojitedian [The Logical Properties of Cantonese

- saai*]. In Sin Chou Yiu (ed.), *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Yue Dialects*. Hong Kong: XianDa Jiaoyu Yanjiush, pp. 131–138
- Lee, Tommy Tsz-Ming (2022) Towards the Unity of Movement: Implications from verb Movement in Cantonese. Ph.D. dissertation, University of Southern California.
- Lee, Tommy Tsz-Ming (2024a) *The Unity of Movement: Evidence from Verb Movement in Cantonese*. Amsterdam and Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing.
- Lee, Tommy Tsz-Ming (2024b) A Derivational View on Verbal Suffixes in Chinese. Paper presented at 2024 Linguistic Society of Hong Kong Annual Research Forum (ARF), Hong Kong Shue Yan University, December 8, 2024.
- Lee, Tommy Tsz-Ming & Victor Junnan Pan (2024) The Privileged Status of Phases: Licensing VP Movement and Ellipsis in Chinese. Manuscript. City University of Hong Kong and The Chinese University of Hong Kong. URL: <https://ling.auf.net/lingbuzz/006662>
- Li, Xinkui, Jiajiao Huang, Qisheng Shi, Yun Mai & Dingfang Chen (1995) *Guangzhou Fangyan Yanjiu [A Study of Guangzhou Cantonese]*. Guangzhou: Guangdong Renmin Chubanshe [Guangdong People’s Publishing House].
- Lin, Lianxian (1963) Yueyu dongci ciwei xuzi yongfa de tantao [A Study of the Uses of Postverbal Particles in Cantonese]. *The Chung Chi Journal*, vol.2.2:181–191.
- Liu, Yuyang & Ka-Fai Yip (2023) High vs. Low ‘again’: Mandarin *you* vs. *zai* and Cantonese *-faan* vs. *-gwo*. In Wei William Zhou, Mineharu Nakayama, Marjorie K.M. Chan & Zhiguo Xie (eds.) *Buckeye East Asian Linguistics*, vol.7:94–104. Ohio State University.
- Lu, Man, Anikó Lipták & Rint Sybesma (2019) A Structural Account of the Difference between Achievements and Accomplishments: Evidence from Changsha Xiang Chinese. *Journal of East Asian Linguistics*, vol.28:279–306.
- MacDonald, Jonathan E (2008) Domain of Aspectual Interpretation. *Linguistic Inquiry*, vol.39.1:128–147.
- Matthews, Stephen & Virginia Yip (1994) *Cantonese: A Comprehensive Grammar*. London: Routledge.
- Peng, Xiaochuan (2010) *Guangzhouhua zhuci yanjiu [Studies in Cantonese Particles]*. Guangzhou: Jinan University Press.
- Shi, Jianguo (2003) Cong Yueyu shichengtai “V luo” kan yuepu duiying ji yuyan jiaoxue [From Cantonese Inchoative Aspect “V lok” to Cantonese-Mandarin Correspondence and language Teaching]. *Asia Pacific Journal of Language in Education*, vol.6.1:115–127.
- Sio, Joanna Ut-Seong (2020) The Dual Identity of the Post-verbal *can1* in Cantonese: A Non-specific Resultative Particle and a Free Choice Item. *Studies in Chinese Linguistics*, vol.41.2:139–159.
- Smith, Carlota S. (1991) *The Parameter of Aspect*. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Smith, Carlota S. (1994) Aspectual Viewpoint and Situation Type in Mandarin Chinese. *Journal of East Asian Linguistics*, vol.3.2:107–146.
- Smith, Carlota S. (1997) *The Parameter of Aspect (second edition)*. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Soh, Hooi Ling (2014) Aspect. In C.-T. James Huang, Y.-H. Audrey Li & Andrew Simpson (eds.), *The Handbook of Chinese Linguistics*, 126–155. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Sybesma, Rint (2017) Inner Aspect. In Rint Sybesma, Wolfgang Behr, Yueguo Gu, Zev Handel, C.-T. James Huang & James Myers (eds.), *Encyclopedia of Chinese Language and Linguistics*, vol.1:186–193. Leiden: Brill.
- Tang, Sze-Wing (1998) Parametrization of Features in Syntax. Ph.D. dissertation, University of California, Irvine.
- Tang, Sze-Wing (2003) Properties of *ngaang* and the Syntax of Verbal Particles in Cantonese. *Journal of Chinese Linguistics*, vol.31.2:245–269.
- Tang, Sze-Wing (2006) Hanyu fangyan shoushi huati ju leixing de canshu fenxi [A Parametric Approach to the Typology of Subtopics in Chinese Dialects]. *Linguistic Sciences*,

- vol.5.6:3–11.
- Tang, Sze-Wing (2015) *Yueyu yufa jiangyi [Lectures on Cantonese Grammar]*. Hong Kong: The Commercial Press.
- Tang, Sze-Wing (2018) Yueyu dongci houzhui yu wanju wenti [Verbal Suffixes and Completeness in Cantonese]. In Dah-An Ho, Yuk-man Carine Yiu, Jingtao Sun, Zhongmin Chen & Hung-nin Samuel Cheung (eds.), *Frontiers in the Study of Sinitic and Sino-Tibetan Languages: Festschrift in Honor of Professor Ting Pang-hsin on his 80th Birthday*. Beijing: Social Sciences Academic Press, pp. 686–696.
- Tang, Sze-Wing (2022) On the Syntax of Incompleteness: Evidence from the Converbial Construction in Cantonese. In Andrew Simpson (ed.), *New Explorations in Chinese Theoretical Syntax: Studies in Honor of Yen-Hui Audrey Li*. Amsterdam & Philadelphia: John Benjamins, pp. 395–427.
- Travis, Lisa deMena (2010) *Inner Aspect*. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Tsai, Wei-Tien Dylan (2001) On Subject Specificity and Theory of Syntax-Semantics Interface. *Journal of East Asian Linguistics*, vol.10.2:129–168.
- Tsai, Wei-Tien Dylan (2008) Tense Anchoring in Chinese. *Lingua*, vol.118.5:675–686.
- Wong, Shing-Kit (2018) Yueyu ciwei “ding” de yufa tedian [Linguistic Properties of Suffix *ding6* in Cantonese]. *Current Research in Chinese Linguistics*, vol.97.1:41–56.
- Yan, Miaocai & Ye Yuan (2024) Three-Layered Hierarchical Structure of Mandarin Chinese Aspectual Projections. *Lingua*, vol.300.103677:1–34.
- Yip, Ka-Fai (2019) Yueyu dongci houzhui de wanju wenti [The Incompleteness Effects of Cantonese Verbal Suffixes]. MPhil thesis, The Chinese University of Hong Kong.
- Yip, Ka-Fai (2020a) On the Position of Perfective Aspect. Paper presented at 2020 Linguistic Society of Hong Kong Annual Research Forum (ARF), The Chinese University of Hong Kong, December 11–12, 2020.
- Yip, Ka-Fai (2020b) Yueyu dongci houzhui “qin” de sange kuangshi jiegou [Three Discontinuous Constructions of Cantonese Verbal Suffix *-can*]. *Current Research in Chinese Linguistics*, vol.99.1:153–169.
- Yip, Ka-Fai (2022) Converbs and Adverbial Clauses: A Case Study in Cantonese. *Studies in Chinese Linguistics*, vol.43.2:143–169.
- Yuan, Yulin (1993) *Xiandai Hanyu Qishiju Yanjiu [A Study of Imperative Sentences in Modern Chinese]*. Beijing: Peking University Press.
- Zhan, Bohui (1958) Yuefangyanzhong de xuci *qin, zhu, fan, mai, tian* [Functional Elements *can1, zyu6, faan1, maai4, tim1* in Cantonese]. *Zhongguo Yuwen [Studies of the Chinese Language]*, vol.3:119–122.
- Zhi, Fulan (1994) Guangzhou fangyan de yuzhui [The Suffixes in the Guangzhou Dialect]. In Chow-Yiu Sin (ed.), *Proceedings of the First International Conference on Yue Dialects*. Hong Kong: Modern Educational Research Society Limited, pp. 145–163.

Acknowledgement

For discussion, I am grateful to Tommy Tsz-Ming Lee, Yuyang Liu, Kiki Liu, Rint Sybesma, and Ellie Xia. Special thanks go to Fulang Chen who witnessed the completion of this paper on Christmas Eve. I also thank the editorial board for help.

粵語的內層體貌

本文為第一個針對粵語內層體貌結構特點的系統研究。本文一共討論十四個動詞後內層體貌成分，如「食完」的完成體「完」。結構上，它們佔據中間位置：比結果補語（如「食飽」的「飽」）高，但比外層體貌後綴（如「食咗」的完整體「咗」）低。句法上，內層體貌比輕動詞短語（*vP*）低，但可以在動詞短語（*VP*）以上或以下。此外，一些內層體貌成分的語法類別屬時相補語，其他成分則或為動詞後綴，或介乎後綴和補語之間。

關鍵詞：內層體貌，時相補語，動詞後綴，粵語

Copyright 2025. Ka-Fai Yip.

Date received: 25 Dec 2024

Date accepted: 28 Feb 2025

To cite:

Yip, Ka-Fai (2025) Inner Aspect in Cantonese. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:15-36.

FLaP FIRST

Facebook

Website

Comments for Yip's "Inner Aspect in Cantonese"

Joanna Ut-Seong SIO
Palacký University Olomouc
Joannautseong.sio@upol.cz

This paper provides a detailed treatment of Cantonese inner aspectual particles, including (i) how to differentiate them from outer aspectual particles and resultative verbal complements, (ii) their syntactic statuses (e.g., complements, vs. suffixes), as well as (iii) syntactic treatments that would distinguish them: inner aspectual particles which are complements (aspectual projection below VP), inner aspectual particles which are suffixes (aspectual projection above VP but below vP), and resultative verbal complements (small clause below VP). The discussion is clear and the analysis is well-motivated. I believe the observations and analysis are valuable for future studies.

I have included some comments below including data questions, and some judgments that are different from my own judgment, as well as some issues that I was puzzled about. I hope these would be useful for the author.

1. Data

- a. Can inner aspectual particles stack? The expectation is no. Can they appear with RVCs?
- b. Initially I am not sure why *jyun4* 完 is not an RVC, but I think the contrast between (9a) and (9b) makes it clear. I wonder if the contrast works equally well for all inner particles in the paper, and if how good/bad it sounds is related to the lexical content of the particle. For example, I think *dim6* 掂 doesn't sound so bad in that position (doubling without the verb).
- c. I am a bit confused regarding what the author intends to show between (8) and (10). Is it the case that (8) shows "V-inner aspectual particle" doubling ranges from marginal to totally bad, while (10) shows that without the verb, it is always totally bad? Would it be correct to say that if it is bad with the verb (in doubling), then it is definitely bad alone?
- d. Page 25, (14): Doesn't *jyun4* 完 have some lexical meaning?
- e. Is (15i) really bad? Imagine a situation where one is given a week to finish a painting, can we then say "一個禮拜我應該畫得起呢幅畫。" ("I should be able to finish this painting in a week.")
- f. I find (16g) pretty acceptable.

2. Theoretical content

- a. Page 15, 2nd paragraph:
"This study maintains that the situation-viewpoint split is semantic and the inner-outer split is structural/syntactic, and there is no one-to-one mapping between them."

It is unclear to me how this applies to the analysis at hand. Does it mean that some of the inner aspectual particles discussed in the paper are actually semantically outer aspectual particles (e.g., encoding viewpoint aspect), and yet they are placed under vP anyway? If so, maybe it can be mentioned in the discussion more explicitly when discussing the particles. The author has mentioned Yan & Yuan (2024), regarding viewpoint aspect being encoded in both the inner and outer aspectual positions. A similar discussion is also presented in Lu, Lipták & Sybesma (2019), regarding placing

the perfective *le* below vP, citing evidence from Cheng (2019).

[Cheng, L. L. S. (2019) On the interaction between modals and aspects. *English Linguistics*, vol.35.2:241-260.]

b. Page 29, first paragraph in section 4

Aren't there 3 Asp projections under vP in Lu, Lipták & Sybesma (2019)?

c. Page 29-32, section 4

How does one determine whether it is left or right adjunction in the snowballing movement? How does the affix status (e.g., infix, suffix) interact with the head movement? It doesn't seem to be consistent in all the trees.

d. Page 31

Should the inner aspectual particle be a different one (one of the PC ones), but not *dou2* in (22)? Otherwise, it is the same particle as in (21), but two different positions.

Copyright 2025. Joanna Ut-Seong Sio.

Date received: 23 Feb 2025

To cite:

Sio, Joanna Ut-Seong (2025) Comments for Yip's "Inner Aspect in Cantonese". *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:37-38.

Response to Sio's Comments for "Inner Aspect in Cantonese"

Ka-Fai Yip
 Yale University
 kafai.yip@yale.edu

First of all, I thank the reviewer for the very detailed and helpful comments. While the journal policy does not involve revision, the review comments are useful and would certainly lead to improvement of the manuscript. Since both the review comments and the response are open access, I respond to the major issues that might be of interest to the general audience below, rather than compiling a point-by-point reply.

1. Whether *jyun* (完) 'finish' is an RVC or an inner aspectual particle

This paper maintains a strict distinction between resultative verbal complements (RVCs) and phase complements, which belong to inner aspect. Some diagnostics have been proposed in Section 2, such as the contrast in verb doubling and the aspectual vs. lexical meaning, but it is true that no comprehensive definition of RVCs has been provided (but see Section 4 which alludes to theta-role assignment). Here, I clarify that RVCs must hold a thematic relationship with one of the arguments (see Huang, Li & Li 2009 and references therein). In the case of objects like *dou mun* (道門) 'the door' in (i), it receives the Theme role from both *daa* (打) 'hit' and *laan* (爛) 'break'.

- | | | |
|-----|--------------------------------|-----------------------|
| (i) | 佢打爛咗道門。 | → 道門爛咗。 |
| | Keoi daa-laan-zo dou mun. | → Dou mun laan-zo. |
| | 3SG hit-break-PFV CL door | CL door break-PFV |
| | 'S/he hit and broke the door.' | 'The door is broken.' |

In contrast, *jyun* (完) 'finish' does not assign a theta-role to any of the arguments. It only has an aspectual reading, namely, the completion of the event. It is a bit tricky to say whether this meaning is "lexical", because *jyun* (完) 'finish' alone can be a verb, which requires an eventive argument (as in *beicoi jyun-zo* 比賽完咗 'the competition is finished'). Indeed, verbs may also denote aspectual meaning, such as *hoici* (開始) 'begin' (see Lee 2024, Lee & Pan 2024 for thorough studies on aspectual verbs in Cantonese and Mandarin). Turning to postverbal particles/complement, I assume verbal complements that denote aspectual meaning to be phase complements, following the characterization by Chao (1968). They lack the ability to assign theta-roles, as shown by the contrast below concerning *jyun* (完) 'finish'.

- | | | |
|------|-------------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| (ii) | 佢食完碗麵。 | → *碗麵完咗。 |
| | Keoi sik-jyun wun min. | → *Wun min jyun-zo. |
| | 3SG eat-finish CL noodles | CL noodles finish-PFV |
| | 'S/he finished eating the noodles.' | Int.: 'The noodles are finished.' |

It is possible that it is only a terminological difference: *jyun* (完) 'finish', in some sense, also denotes the result of an event, i.e., completion. However, it should be appreciated that *jyun* (完) 'finish' has a principled difference from other canonical RVCs in lacking theta-role assignment. I take this to be the cut between lexical categories and functional categories: only the former assigns theta-roles. Since *jyun* (完) 'finish' conveys only aspectual meaning, it projects a functional category, Asp, and cannot undergo verb doubling, under the assumption

that only lexical categories can be doubled (see Section 4). We can see how the different properties of RVCs vs. inner aspect particles neatly fall out from the current analysis with the lexical-functional distinction.

2. The semantic vs. syntactic split of aspect

The distinction between situation aspect and viewpoint aspect is often murky in the literature. In the two-component theory by Smith (1997), situation aspect refers to the temporal properties of dynamism, durativity, and telicity expressed by verb constellation (i.e., a main verb + its arguments); and viewpoint aspect refers to the focus of all or part of a situation expressed by grammatical morphemes. For Smith, completive *wan* (完) in Mandarin conveys perfective viewpoint, in addition to completion (1997:266). On the other hand, experiential *-guo* (過) first contributes to a stative situation type, and then a perfective viewpoint (1997:269). Syntactically, *wan* (完) belongs to inner aspect (below vP) and *-guo* (過) belongs to outer aspect (above vP) (see, e.g., Tsai 2008b). We thus see that inner aspect may encode viewpoint aspect whereas outer aspect may also encode situation aspect, at least according to Smith's (1997) characterization. There is thus no one-to-one mapping between the syntactic position and the type of aspectual meaning encoded.

Note also that viewpoint aspects can be stacked, such as English perfect and progressive:

(iii) John **has been reading** the book for a long time.

Hence, it is semantically possible for inner aspect that conveys viewpoints to be stacked with outer aspect that also conveys viewpoints, such as the *-zo* (咗) suffixation cases in (4) in this paper.

3. How many inner aspectual projections?—and the position of perfective *-le* (了)

Lu, Lipták & Sybesma (2019) propose that there are three aspectual projections below vP, based on Mandarin Chinese and Changsha Xiang: Asp3 (“RealizationP”, cf. Sybesma 1999), the perfective *-le* (了); Asp2, phase complements or Changsha achievement marker *ka⁴¹*; and Asp1 (“TelicityP”), RVCs.

(iv) [vP [Asp3P *-le* ‘PFV’ [Asp2P PCs/*ka⁴¹* [Asp1P RVCs [VP V]]]]]

Below, I discuss how the approach developed in this paper is different from Lu, Lipták & Sybesma's (2019). For the ease of comparison, I schematize the current approach here:

(v) [AspP-outer *-gwo/-zo/...* [vP [AspP-inner1 *-lok/-dou/...* [v1P V1 [v2P/AspP-inner2 RVCs/PCs]]]]]

First, all the Asp projections in Lu, Lipták & Sybesma (2019) are above VP, different from the current approach with a VP-internal AspP. The VP-internal-external distinction is useful to capture the verbal suffixes vs. verb complements distinction regarding *-dak/m-* infixation. Inner aspectual suffixes like *lok* (落) only project AspP-inner1, whereas phase complements like *hou* (好) only project AspP-inner2. *Dou* (到/倒) and *yun* (完) have dual status, and hence may project AspP-inner1 or AspP-inner2 (see Section 4).

Regarding Asp1P, this paper does not take RVCs to project a functional category; rather, they project lexical categories and form small clauses. The telicity requirement is a by-product of the resultative meaning.

Regarding Asp2P, it corresponds to AspP-inner1 (VP-external) and AspP-inner2 (VP-internal) in this paper, depending on whether the inner aspectual particle in question is a verbal suffix or a verbal complement.

Regarding Asp3P, this paper does not place perfective *-le* (了) below vP. I follow Gu (1995) that perfective *-le* (了) should associate with a position higher than experiential *-guo* (過), as evidenced by the following suffix stacking fact (see Yip 2020 for clear scopal evidence from Yangchun Yue concerning a universal quantificational suffix *-cvi2* 齊).

- (vi) 他已經看過那本書了。 [Mandarin]
 Ta yijing kan-**guo-le** nei-ben shu le.
 3SG already read-EXP-PFV that-CL book SFP
 ‘S/he has already read that book.’ (Gu 1995:52)

While Sybesma (personal communication) suggests that this *-guo* (過) in (vi) might be a lower *-guo* (過) and receives lexical tone 4, my three native Beijing Mandarin consultants reported to me that neutral tones are still possible in the *V-guo-le* (V-過-了) sequence. I thus maintain that *-le* (了) should be outside vP.¹

Another piece of evidence that *-le* (了) should be higher than vP comes from aspect lowering (sometimes called experiential lowering for *-guo* 過; see Grano 2014, N. Huang 2018, C.-T. J. Huang 2022, Liu & Yip 2025). As shown by Liu & Yip (2025), only outer aspect suffixes may undergo aspect lowering, but not inner aspect suffixes/complements. Importantly, *-le* (了), as reported by Grano (2014), allows aspect lowering. As shown in (vii), the embedded *-le* (了) takes wide scope and applies to the matrix verb *quan* (勸) ‘urge’, and thus incompatible with a matrix progressive aspect. This contrasts with inner aspect particles like *diao* (掉), which does not allow aspect lowering, as in (viii). Interested readers are referred to Liu & Yip (2025) for a proposal that builds on the size-based approach to finiteness and an agreement analysis of aspectual suffixes.

- (vii) 張三(*在)勸李四[買了一個蘋果]。 [Mandarin]
 Zhangsan (*zai) quan Lisi [mai-**le** yi-ge pingguo].
 Zhangsan PROG urge Lisi buy-PFV one-CL apple
 ‘Zhangsan urged Lisi to buy an apple.’ (Grano 2014, ex. 34a)

- (viii) 我(在)勸(著)他[吃掉這碗飯]。 [Mandarin]
 Wo (zai) quan(-zhe) ta [chi-**diao** zhe-wan fan].
 1SG PROG urge-IPFV 3SG eat-ACHV this-CL rice
 ‘I urge/am urging him to eat up this bowl of rice.’
 NOT: ‘I finished urging him to eat this bowl of rice.’ (Liu & Yip 2025, ex. 97a)

There are potentially two counter-arguments to the high position of *-le* (了), which I address briefly below.

First, Sybesma (2017) argues that *-le* (了) can be placed below *ba* (把) which he analyzes as v (see also Sybesma 1999, Lu, Lipták & Sybesma 2019).

¹ I thank Yuyang Liu, Yitong Luo, and Xuotong Yuan for judgment.

- (ix) 我把他殺了。 [Mandarin]
 Wo **ba** ta sha-**le**.
 1SG BA 3SG kill-PFV.
 ‘I killed him.’ (Sybesma 2017, ex.2b)

This counter-argument relies crucially on the assumption that *ba* (把) realizes v, which is not uncontroversial. For example, in the affective analysis by Li (2006, 2017), *ba* (把) is analyzed as an vP-external projection. See Chen (2023) for a recent Appl/Voice head analysis. Setting aside the debate, it is possible to have other outer aspect suffixes below *ba* (把), such as experiential *-guo* (過) in (x).

- (x) 你曾把不該忘的事情忘過嗎? [Mandarin]
 Ni ceng **ba** bu gai wang-de shiqing wang-**guo** ma?
 2SG ever BA not should forget-DE thing forget-EXP SFP
 ‘Have you ever forgotten matters that should not be forgotten?’ (Li 2017:64)

Second, as pointed out by the reviewer, Cheng (2019) provides an argument for *-le* (了) being lower. Cheng, building on Tsai (2008a), uncovers a very interesting interaction between aspect and the causal reading of *zenme* (怎麼) in Mandarin. While *zenme* (怎麼) is ambiguous between a causal and a manner reading, only the causal reading is possible with perfective *-le* (了).

- (xi) 阿 Q 怎麼去台北? [Mandarin]
 Akiu zenme qu taibei?
 Akiu how go Taipei
 a. ‘How come Akiu is going to Taipei?’
 b. ‘How is Akiu going to Taipei?’ (e.g. by train, by plane)

- (xii) 阿 Q 怎麼去了台北? [Mandarin]
 Akiu zenme qu-**le** taibei?
 Akiu how go-PFV Taipei
 ‘How come Akiu went to Taipei?’ (Tsai 2008a, ex.5b; Cheng 2019:242)

Cheng suggests that *-le* (了) is syntactically below vP but it associates with an outer aspect position above vP, which is intervened by manner *zenme* in the vP layer, explaining the absence of the manner reading. Causal *zenme*, on the other hand, is too high to intervene.

- (xiii) Cheng’s (2019) analysis
 *_{[Asp1P Asp1 [ModP-root [vP zenme_{manner} [V [Asp2P Asp2-**le** VP]]]]]}

While this analysis is insightful and captures the interesting data nicely, there are two complexities. First, the Cantonese counterpart with *dimjoeng* (點樣) ‘how’, which only has a manner reading, is perfectly fine with perfective *-zo* (咗), as in (xiv). Note that Cheng (2019) only discussed *dim* (點) ‘how’.

- (xiv) 後來佢又點解同點樣去咗加拿大?
 Hauloi keoi jau dimgaai tung dimjoeng heoi-**zo** Gaanaadaai?
 later 3SG again why and how go-PFV Canada
 ‘Why and how did s/he later go to Canada?’ (Podcast, 2024-11-2)²

Second, the manner reading of *zenme* (怎麼) is indeed possible with *shi... (de)* (是... (的)), as attested in the following naturally-occurring examples:

- (xv) 山姆的綠豆芽是怎麼去了皮的呢? [Mandarin]
 Shanmu-de lvdouya **shi zenme** qu-**le** pi **de** ne?
 Sam-DE bean.sprout be how peel-PFV skin DE SFP
 ‘How did Sam peel his bean sprouts?’ (Bilibili, 2022-11-27)³
- (xvi) 也回想不起自己是怎麼去了那個地方 [Mandarin]
 ye huixiang-bu-qi ziji **shi zenme** qu-**le** na-ge defang.
 also recall-not-up self be how go-PFV that-CL place
 ‘(S/he) also cannot remember how (s/he) got to that place’ (Steam, 2022-7-13)⁴

I thereby conclude that this counter-argument requires close scrutiny and does not challenge the high position of *-le* (了) in Mandarin and *-zo* (咗) in Cantonese.

Once again, I am grateful to the reviewer for the careful comments, which lead to the fruitful discussion here that I hope is useful for the readers.

REFERENCES

- Chao, Yuen Ren (1968) *A Grammar of Spoken Chinese*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Chen, Fulang (2023) Obscured Universality in Mandarin. PhD dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Cheng, Lisa Lai-Shen (2019) On the Interaction between Modals and Aspects. *English Linguistics*, vol.35.2:241–260.
- Grano, Thomas (2014) Control without Finiteness Contrasts: Aspect and Complement Size in Mandarin Chinese. Manuscript. Indiana University, Bloomington.
- Gu, Yang (1995) Aspect Licensing, Verb Movement and Feature Checking. *Cahiers de Linguistique-Asie Orientale*, vol.24:49–83.
- Huang, Cheng-Teh James, Yen-Hui Audrey Li & Yafei Li (2009) *The Syntax of Chinese*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Huang, Cheng-Teh James (2022) “Finiteness, Opacity, and Chinese Clausal Architecture.” In Andrew Simpson (ed.), *New Explorations in Chinese Theoretical Syntax: Studies in Honor of Yen-Hui Audrey Li*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, pp.17–76.

² <https://creators.spotify.com/pod/profile/chungchichats/episodes/19-e2oltpv>, accessed on 2025-4-2.

³ https://www.bilibili.com/video/BV14R4y1Z7y9/?vd_source=86aa818d47794ee29b5349b088c8b399, accessed on 2025-4-2.

⁴ https://store.steampowered.com/app/916140/The_Tale_of_Bistun/?l=schinese, accessed on 2025-4-2.

- Huang, Nick (2018) “Control Complements in Mandarin Chinese: Implications for Restructuring and the Chinese Finiteness Debate.” *Journal of East Asian Linguistics*, vol.27.4:347–376.
- Lee, Tommy Tsz-Ming (2024) *The Unity of Movement: Evidence from Verb Movement in Cantonese*. Amsterdam and Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing.
- Lee, Tommy Tsz-Ming & Victor Junnan Pan (2024) The Privileged Status of Phases: Licensing VP Movement and Ellipsis in Chinese. Manuscript. City University of Hong Kong and The Chinese University of Hong Kong. URL: <https://ling.auf.net/lingbuzz/006662>
- Li, Yen-Hui Audrey (2006) Chinese *ba*. In Martin Everaert & Henk van Riemsdijk (eds.), *The Blackwell Companion to Syntax*. Malden, MA: Blackwell, pp.374–468.
- Li, Yen-Hui Audrey (2017) Chinese *ba*. In Martin Everaert & Henk van Riemsdijk (eds.), *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Syntax (second edition)*. Malden, MA: Blackwell, pp.1–72.
- Liu, Yuyang & Ka-Fai Yip (2025) Again, Finiteness and Split Aspect in Chinese Languages. Manuscript. Yale University. URL: <https://lingbuzz.net/lingbuzz/008780>
- Lu, Man, Anikó Lipták & Rint Sybesma (2019) A Structural Account of the Difference between Achievements and Accomplishments: Evidence from Changsha Xiang Chinese. *Journal of East Asian Linguistics*, vol.28:279–306.
- Smith, Carlota S. (1997) *The Parameter of Aspect (second edition)*. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Sybesma, Rint (1999) *The Mandarin VP*. Dordrecht: Kluwer.
- Sybesma, Rint (2017) Inner Aspect. In Rint Sybesma, Wolfgang Behr, Yueguo Gu, Zev Handel, C.-T. James Huang & James Myers (eds.), *Encyclopedia of Chinese Language and Linguistics*. Leiden: Brill, vol.I:186–193.
- Tsai, Wei-Tien Dylan (2008a) Left Periphery and How-why Alternations. *Journal of East Asian Linguistics*, vol.17:83–115.
- Tsai, Wei-Tien Dylan (2008b) Tense Anchoring in Chinese. *Lingua*, vol.118.5:675–686.
- Yip, Ka-Fai (2020) On the Position of Perfective Aspect. Paper presented at 2020 Linguistic Society of Hong Kong Annual Research Forum (ARF), The Chinese University of Hong Kong, December 11–12, 2020.

Copyright 2025. Ka-Fai Yip.

Date received: 03 Apr 2025

To cite:

Yip, Ka-Fai (2025) Response to Sio’s Comments for “Inner Aspect in Cantonese”. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:39-44.

Vowel Epenthesis in Sibe: A Perceptual Account

Mingxing Li

Hong Kong Baptist University

mingxingli@hkbu.edu.hk

Abstract

Phonological literature recognizes different functions of and motivations for vowel epenthesis, to satisfy the requirements of syllable structure vs. to enhance the perceptuality of consonants. In Sibe, epenthetic vowels appear between root-final consonants (C_1) and suffix-initial consonants (C_2). The presence vs. absence of the epenthetic vowel depends on the property of C_1 : an epenthetic vowel tends not to occur when C_1 is a sonorant; an epenthetic vowel tends to occur when C_1 is a stop or a non-sibilant ([-strident]) fricative; an epenthetic vowel also tends to occur when C_1 is a sibilant fricative and C_2 an obstruent. Such a distribution property poses challenge to a syllable-based account of vowel epenthesis and lends support to a perceptually based account.

Keywords: vowel epenthesis, perceptuality, consonant cluster

1. Background

Vowel epenthesis is widely observed across languages, where consonant clusters are broken up with the insertion of a vocalic sound (Broselow 1982, Itô 1989, Côté 2000, Lombardi 2002, Hall 2003, 2006, 2011). Phonological literature recognizes different motivations for vowel epenthesis. Vowel epenthesis can be prosodically-driven, i.e., to form well-formed prosodic units such as a syllable or feet (Broselow 1982, Itô 1989) or segmentally-driven, i.e., to break up a particular sequence of segments regardless of their prosodic membership (Broselow 1982). On the other hand, vowel epenthesis can also be perceptually-motivated, i.e., to make an adjacent consonant more perceptible (Côté 2000).

This paper involves a case study of vowel epenthesis in Sibe (aka. Xibe, Xibo, Sibo), in which vowel epenthesis occurs between a root-final consonant (C_1) and a suffix-initial consonant (C_2). The distribution of the epenthetic vowel in Sibe varies according to the different properties of C_1 and C_2 , which is likely to obtain a functional explanation in terms of the relative perceptual salience of its neighboring consonants.

2. Vowel epenthesis in Sibe

2.1 The language

Sibe is a branch of Tungusic languages, which is spoken in Qapqal Autonomous County, Xinjiang, China. The vowels and consonants of Sibe are listed in (1).

(1) Vowels and consonants in Sibe (Li et al. 1984:7-13; Li & Zhong 1986:3-15)

a. Vowels

	<i>Front</i>	<i>Central</i>	<i>Back</i>
<i>High</i>	i y		u
<i>Mid</i>	æ œ	ə	o
<i>Low</i>		a	

b. Consonants

	<i>Bilabial</i>	<i>Labio-dental</i>	<i>Alveolar</i>	<i>Retroflex</i>	<i>Palatal</i>	<i>Velar</i>	<i>Uvular</i>
<i>Stop</i>	p b		t d			k g	q ɢ
<i>Nasal</i>	m		n			ŋ	
<i>Trill</i>			r				
<i>Fricative</i>		f v	s	ʂ ʐ	ç	x	χ
<i>Affricate</i>			ʈ ʣ	ʈʂ ʣʂ	tɕ dʒ		
<i>Lateral</i>			l				
<i>Glide</i>	w				j		

The syllable structure of Sibe is summarized in (2), following Li *et al.* (1984) and Li & Zhong (1986). Note that in (2), the triconsonantal cluster CCC, as in [avχ] ‘leaf’, is allowed only at word-final positions (Li & Zhong 1986:15).¹

(2) Syllable types in Sibe (Li *et al.* 1984:13-14; Li & Zhong 1986:15-18)

<i>V</i>	[y]	‘wheel track’
<i>VC</i>	[if]	‘tomb’
<i>VCC</i>	[avχ]	‘leaf’
<i>VCCC*</i>	[antχ]	‘guest’
<i>CV</i>	[bo]	‘home’
<i>CVC</i>	[sal]	‘beard’
<i>CVCC</i>	[χasχ]	‘scissors’

2.2 Vowel epenthesis in Sibe

In Sibe, vowel epenthesis occurs across a morpheme boundary, more specifically, between a root-final consonant and a suffix-initial consonant (Li & Zhong 1986:21-22).

(3) bos + v → bosuv
‘cloth’ + ACCUSATIVE CASE MARKER

With (3) being the case, vowel epenthesis occurs only when the root-final consonant is an obstruent, not if it is a sonorant.

As for the quality of the epenthetic vowels, there is disagreement in the literature: Chao (2006) recognized it as [ə]. Li & Zhong (1986:21-22) described the vowel as [ə] or [u]; B. Li (1999:304) described it as alternatively an [i] or [u], depending on the roundedness of its preceding vowel. In addition, W. Li (2015) reports more diverse qualities of epenthetic vowels in different contexts.

Regarding the above, the distribution of the epenthetic vowel is related to the property of the root-final consonant. For the epenthetic vowel and the root-final consonants, the following questions are raised: Firstly, what is the phonetic property of the epenthetic vowel, given the diverse description in the literature? Secondly, what is the influence of the root-final consonants on the presence/absence of an epenthetic vowel? To answer these two questions, an empirical case study was conducted on the epenthetic vowels in Sibe, involving

¹ For stress in multi-syllable words in Sibe, Li *et al.* (1984:13-14) and Li & Zhong (1986:15-18) noted that “the first syllable bears a weak stress and the last syllable bears a slightly rising pitch”, whereas Jang (2008:85-87) noted that the primary stress normally falls on the last syllable. The data collected in this study turns out to be consistent with Jang (2008)’s description.

data collected from a native Sibe speaker. An acoustic measurement was performed on the epenthetic vowels, which is followed by an analysis looking for a theoretical understanding of the observed pattern.

3. Materials

To elicit the production of epenthetic vowels in Sibe, the roots and suffixes in (4) were referred to. Particularly, (4i) included roots ending with a vowel (4a), a sonorant (4b), a stop (4c), and a fricative (4d), while (4ii) included suffixes beginning with a sonorant (4e) and an obstruent (4f), or those consisting of a single obstruent (4g).

(4) Wordlist in Sibe (Li et al. 1984:13-14; Li & Zhong 1986:15-18)

i. Roots

	<i>Word</i>	<i>Transcription</i>	<i>Gloss</i>
a.	弟弟	[tu]	‘younger brother’
b.	手	[gal]	‘hand’
	孫子	[ɔmol]	‘grandson’
	山	[ɛlin]	‘hill’
	人民	[kurun]	‘people’
	雪	[nimaŋ]	‘snow’
c.	事情	[pait ^h]	‘event’
	掃帚	[irk ^h]	‘broom’
	手巾	[fuŋk ^w]	‘towel’
	驢	[lyeaq]	‘donkey’
	桌子	[tir]	‘table’
d.	馬腸子	[qas]	‘horse intestine’
	布	[pos]	‘cloth’
	寡婦	[aŋɛ]	‘widow’
	熊	[lif]	‘bear’
	腦袋	[fiχ]	‘head’
	膝蓋	[puχ ^w]	‘knee’
	鉤子	[goχ ^w]	‘hook’

ii. Suffixes

	<i>Word</i>	<i>Transcription</i>	<i>Gloss</i>
e.	和…	[-maq]	‘with…’
	…的	[-nəŋ]	‘of…’
f.	比…	[-tiri]	‘than…’
	向著…	[-te ^h i]	‘towards…’
g.	給…	[-t]	‘to…’
	把…	[-v]	(Oblique case)

The recording materials were 126 words, resulting from the combinations of the 18 roots in (4i) and 7 suffixes in (4ii). For example, 和手 /gal-maq/ ‘with hand’; 比事情 /pait^h-tiri/ ‘than event’; 給馬腸子 /qas-t/ ‘to horse intestine’.

A female native speaker, 25-year old, was invited to produce the 126 words. She grew up in Qapqal Autonomous County, Xinjiang, China, where Sibe is the language of daily use. The speaker used Mandarin proficiently as a second language. The recording was done in a

silent room. The informant read the words to a head-mounted microphone (Philips SHM7410). The recording was done via a Fujitsu SH561 laptop, using the software Adobe Audition 1.5, at the sampling rate of 44100, mono 16-bit. The use of the data was approved by the Institutional Review Board at the University of Kansas (HSCL#20512, 11/7/2012).

4. Results

The acoustic examination of the collected data revealed two properties. First, the existence of an epenthetic vowel varied depending on a root-final consonant (C_1) and a suffix-initial consonant (C_2). Second, the quality of the epenthetic vowels varied with different combinations of C_1 and C_2 . Below, the results are organized in terms of types of C_1 .

4.1 C_1 as vowel and sonorant

When the root ends with a vowel (5a) or a consonantal sonorant (5b), no epenthetic vowels appear, regardless of the suffix-initial consonants (C_2).

(5) Roots ending with sonorants

a.	/tu+v/	→	[tuv]	‘younger brother.OBLIQUE’
b.	/gal+v/	→	[galv]	‘hand.OBLIQUE’
	/ɛlin+tiri/	→	[ɛlintiri]	‘than hill’
	/nimaŋ+te ^{hi} /	→	[nimaŋte ^{hi}]	‘towards snow’

The pattern in (5) is consistent with the descriptions in the literature (Li *et al.* 1984, Li & Zhong 1986, W. Li 2015, etc.).

4.2 C_1 as fricative

When the root ends with a fricative (C_1), vowel epenthesis is generally observed, as illustrated in (6), except for two cases to be noted later. Note that in (6), fricative voicing (Jang 2008:24) is generally involved in most of the items, whereby a fricative C_1 changes to its voiced counterpart.

(6) Roots ending with fricatives

Noun	<i>with ...</i>	<i>of ...</i>	<i>than ...</i>	<i>towards...</i>	<i>to...</i>	<i>Oblique</i>	Glossary
a. lif	livimaq	livinəŋ	livitiri	livite ^{hi} i	livit	liviv	‘bear’
b. fiχ	fiyəmaq	fiyənəŋ	fiyətiri	fiyəte ^{hi} i	fiyət	fiyəv	‘head’
c. qas	qazmaq	qaznəŋ	qazɿtiri	qazɿte ^{hi} i	qazɿt	qazɿv	‘horse’ ‘intestine’
d. aŋɕ	aŋzmaq	aŋɕnəŋ	aŋɕitiri	aŋɕite ^{hi} i	aŋɕit	aŋɕiv	‘widow’

There are two cases of exceptions in (6), as in the four shaded cells: when the root-final consonant (C_1) is a sibilant fricative ([s, ɕ]) and when the suffix-initial consonant (C_2) is a sonorant (i.e. [m, n]), vowel epenthesis does not occur between C_1 and C_2 . In other cells of (6c) and (6d), on the other hand, an epenthetic vowel appears after the [+strident] fricatives [s] and [ɕ].

Put it differently, when C_1 is a [-strident] fricative ([f, χ]), vowel epenthesis occurs, regardless of whether C_2 is a sonorant (e.g., [m/n]) or an obstruent (e.g., [t/te^h/v]). On the other hand, when C_1 is a [+strident] fricative ([s, ɕ]), vowel epenthesis occurs before an

obstruent (e.g., [t/te^h/v]) but not before a sonorant (e.g., [m/n]). A schematic summary of the patterns of vowel epenthesis in (6) is as below in (7).

(7) Distribution of epenthetic vowel when C₁ is a fricative

	C ₂ = [+sonorant]	C ₂ = [-sonorant]
C ₁ = [-strident]	✓ [-strident] __ [+sonorant]	✓ [-strident] __ [-sonorant]
C ₁ = [+strident]	✗ [+strident] __ [+sonorant]	✓ [+strident] __ [-sonorant]

The quality of the epenthetic vowel, as shown in (6), turns out to vary depending on C₁: when C₁ is /f, χ/, the epenthetic vowel is [i, ə] (6a, b); when C₁ is /s/, the epenthetic vowel is the apical vowel [ɿ] (6c); when C₁ is /ç/, the epenthetic vowel is the vowel [i] (6d). In terms of (6c, d) the vowel is homorganic to its preceding fricative. It needs to be noted that in all cases across (6), C₂ does not seem to influence the quality of the epenthetic vowels.

Below, (8) gives sample waveforms and spectrograms of the epenthetic vowels in (6).

(8) Quality of epenthetic vowel when C₁ is a fricative

4.3 C₁ as stop or trill

When the root ends with a stop (C₁), vowel epenthesis is generally observed too, as listed in (9), with two exceptions to be detailed below. Note that in (9b, c), /r/ represents a trill, not an approximant.

(9) Roots ending with stop/trill

Noun	with ...	of ...	than ...	towards...	to...	Oblique	Gloss
a. pait ^h	pait ^h maq	pait ^h nəŋ	pait ^h itiri	pait ^h ite ^h i	pait ^h it	pait ^h iv	‘event’
b. irk ^h	irk ^h imaq	irk ^h inəŋ	irk ^h itiri	irk ^h ite ^h i	irk ^h it	irk ^h iv	‘broom’
c. tir	tirimaq	tirinəŋ	tiritiri	tirite ^h i	tirit	tiriv	‘table’

As shown in the first two shaded cells in (9a), an epenthetic vowel does not appear when C₁ is an aspirated [t^h] and C₂ is a sonorant (e.g., [m/n]). In all other cases, vowel epenthesis appears, whether the root-final consonant (C₁) is an aspirated stop [k^h] or a trill [r]. A comparison between (9a) and (9b) shows that the two aspirated stops [t^h] vs. [k^h] appear in different contexts: [t^h] in (9a) follows the vowel [i] whereas the [k^h] in (9b) follows the trill [r].

Put it differently, when C_1 is an aspirated stop and C_2 an obstruent, vowel epenthesis generally occurs (9a, b); when a C_1 stop is preceded by an /r/ in (9b), vowel epenthesis occurs whatever C_2 is; when C_1 itself is a trill [r], vowel epenthesis appears whatever C_2 is. A schematic summary of (9) is given as (10).

(10) Distribution of epenthetic vowel when C_1 is a stop or a trill

	$C_2 = [+sonorant]$	$C_2 = [-sonorant]$
$C_1 = \left(\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{spread glottis} \end{array} \right)$	$\times V \left(\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{spread glottis} \end{array} \right) _ [+sonorant]$	$\checkmark V \left(\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{spread glottis} \end{array} \right) _ [-sonorant]$
	$\checkmark C \left(\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{spread glottis} \end{array} \right) _ [+sonorant]$	$\checkmark C \left(\begin{array}{l} -\text{continuant} \\ +\text{spread glottis} \end{array} \right) _ [-sonorant]$
$C_1 = [+tap]$	$\checkmark [+tap] _ [+sonorant]$	$\checkmark [+tap] _ [-sonorant]$

The quality of the epenthetic vowels is generally [i], as in (8). Examples of waveforms and spectrograms are given in (11).

(11) Quality of epenthetic vowel when C_1 is a stop

5. Analysis

5.1 A summary of the distribution

The examination in 4.1 to 4.3 indicated that the presence vs. absence of an epenthetic vowel depends on the property of a root-final consonant (C_1) and a suffix-initial consonant (C_2). Below in (12), the distribution pattern is re-summarized, integrating (7) and (10). As shown in (12a), vowel epenthesis occurs in a variety of contexts, which may pose problems to an account that considers only prosodic aspects. As mentioned in (2), for instance, Sibe allows non-final VCC syllables, e.g., [avχ] ‘leaf’, which means that CC cluster is allowed. If this is the case, then it is hard to explain the difference between the presence of epenthetic vowels in (12i) vs. the absence of epenthetic vowels in (12ii). In other words, the ill-formedness of syllable structure is unlikely to be the trigger for the epenthetic vowels in (12i).

(12) Vowel epenthesis in Sibe: a general picture

i. Environments triggering vowel epenthesis

	Pre-C ₁	Root-final C (C ₁)	Suffix-initial C (C ₂)	Example
a.		<i>nonsibilant fricative</i> ([+continuant, –strident])	C ([±sonorant, –syllabic])	livinəŋ, livitiri
b.		<i>trill</i> ([+tap])		tirinəŋ, tiritiri
c.	C	<i>aspirated stop</i> ([–continuant, +spread glottis])		irk ^h inəŋ, irk ^h itiri
d.	V	<i>aspirated stop</i> ([–continuant, +spread glottis])	obstruents ([–sonorant, –syllabic])	pait ^h itiri
e.		<i>sibilant fricative</i> ([+continuant, +strident])		qazɿtɕ ^h i

ii. Environments NOT triggering vowel epenthesis

	Pre-C ₁	Root-final C (C ₁)	Suffix-initial C (C ₂)	Example
f.		<i>sonorant</i> ([+sonorant])	C ([±sonorant, –syllabic])	tumaq, elint
g.		<i>sibilant fricative</i> ([+continuant, +strident])	sonorants ([+sonorant, –syllabic])	qazmaq
h.	V	<i>aspirated stop</i> ([–continuant, +spread glottis])		pait ^h maq

5.2 A perceptual account

To explain the distribution of epenthetic vowels in (12), a perceptual account (Steriade 1994, 2008) is proposed below for the relevant phonological alternation. As a starting point, it is assumed that less salient consonants in particular contexts are more likely to trigger vowel epenthesis than others, following Côté (2000:137).

5.2.1 Vowel epenthesis after aspirated stops

As shown in (12), vowel epenthesis does not occur after the aspirated stop [t^h] when [t^h] is flanked by two [+sonorant] segments (a vowel and a sonorant) as in (12h), e.g., pait^hmaq. This can be attributed to the strong burst release and aspiration in [t^h], which would serve as a relatively strong cue for the perception of the place and manner of the alveolar stop. In addition to the burst release and aspiration, in the [+sonorant] __ [+sonorant] context, it is possible that both the preceding vowel and the following sonorant segment carry external cues for the perception of the stop.

In contrast, vowel epenthesis is triggered when the segment preceding the C₁ [k^h] is not a sonorant, e.g., irk^hinəŋ in (12c), or when C₂ is not a sonorant, e.g., pait^hitiri in (12d). This could be attributed to the fact that, for the stops [k^h] and [t^h], the neighboring segments do not carry sufficient external cues to help the perception of the C₁ stops. More specifically, for a case such as irk^hinəŋ (12c), the aspirated stops are preceded by a non-sonorant [r], which may not provide external cues as strong as a preceding vowel as in pait^hmaq (12h). On the other hand, for a case such as pait^hitiri (12d), the non-sonorant C₂ consonant is likely to be even less efficient in providing external cues for the perception of an aspirated stop such as [t^h].

With vowel epenthesis, the stops [t^h/k^h] in (12c) and (12d) turn out to precede a vowel. In this phonetic context, the stops [t^h] and [k^h] are likely to be much more perceptible, with the presence of vocalic cues in the epenthetic vowels, e.g., in the form of CV formant transition (Côté 2000:136), in addition to the internal cues in [t^h] and [k^h].

Formulating the above analysis in terms of OT, the following constraints can be proposed.

- (13) a. *[-syllabic] [-continuant, +spread glottis] [-syllabic]
 A sequence of aspirated stop flanked by two consonants is disallowed (due to insufficient external cue for the flanked stop). (cf. 12c)
- b. *[-continuant, +spread glottis] [-sonorant, -syllabic]
 A sequence of aspirated stop followed by obstruent is disallowed (due to insufficient external cues for the aspirated stop). (cf. 12d)

These two constraints may interact with the faithfulness constraint Dep(V) to give rise to the observed outputs, as shown below.

- (14) The absence and presence of epenthetic vowels after aspirated stop

Input: /pait ^h -maq/	*[-syllabic] [-continuant, +spread glottis] [-syllabic]	Dep(V)
a. pait ^h maq		
b. pait ^h imaq		*!

Input: /irk ^h -nəŋ/	*[-syllabic] [-continuant, +spread glottis] [-syllabic]	Dep(V)
a. irk ^h inəŋ		*
b. irk ^h nəŋ	*!	

5.2.2 Vowel epenthesis after fricatives

As shown in (12), vowel epenthesis does not occur after a sibilant fricative when C₂ is a sonorant, e.g., qazmaq (12g). In the same environment, i.e., __ [+sonorant], however, vowel epenthesis is triggered if C₁ is a non-sibilant fricative, e.g., livinəŋ (12a). This difference can be attributed to the different robustness of internal cues in a sibilant fricative, such as [s], vs. those in a non-sibilant fricative, such as [v]. More specifically, non-sibilant fricatives are less intense and have less salient internal cues as compared with sibilant fricatives, as sibilant fricatives are mostly resistant to any masking effect (Wright 2004:45). In contrast, even if the following sonorant may provide external cues, the non-sibilant fricatives are still likely to be perceptually weak. This might underly the observation that, even before a sonorant, a C₁ [-strident] fricative still triggers vowel epenthesis, e.g., livinəŋ, presumably to obtain better external cues for its perception.

As shown in (12e), a sibilant fricative as C₁ triggers vowel epenthesis when C₂ is an obstruent, e.g., qazɯtɕ^hi (12e). One potential explanation of this pattern might be found in the avoidance of articulatory gesture overlap. That is, a gesture's recoverability can be compromised when its acoustic cues are weak or absent due to the overlap with other gestures (Jun 1995, Hall 2006). In case of qazɯtɕ^hi in (12e), for example, it might be that the articulatory gesture of the following obstruent (C₂) may overlap with that of the sibilant fricative (C₁), thus undermining its perceptual recoverability.

Formulating the above analysis in terms of OT, the following constraints can be proposed.

- (15) a. ***[+continuant, –strident] [–syllabic]**
 A sequence of non-sibilant fricative and consonant is disallowed (due to insufficient external cue for the non-sibilant fricative). (cf. 12a)
- b. ***[+continuant, +strident] [–syllabic, -sonorant]**
 A sequence of sibilant fricative and obstruent is disallowed (due to the undermining of perceptual recoverability for the sibilant fricatives (cf. 12e)

These two constraints may interact with the faithfulness constraint Dep(V) to give rise to the observed outputs. For example, (16).

- (16) The presence vs. absence of epenthetic vowels after fricatives

Input: / li v i -t i r i /	*[+continuant, –strident] [–syllabic]	*[+continuant, +strident] [–syllabic, -sonorant]	Dep(V)
a. li v i t i r i			*
b. li v t i r i	*!		

Input: /q a z- m a q /	*[+continuant, –strident] [–syllabic]	*[+continuant, +strident] [–syllabic, -sonorant]	Dep(V)
a. q a z m a q			
b. q a z ɿ m a q			*!

Input: /q a z- t e ^{hi} /	*[+continuant, –strident] [–syllabic]	*[+continuant, +strident] [–syllabic, -sonorant]	Dep(V)
a. q a z ɿ t e ^{hi}			*
b. q a z t e ^{hi}		*!	

6. Conclusion

This study has examined the patterns of vowel epenthesis in Sibe, in which the distribution of epenthetic vowels is conditioned by the different types of root-final consonants and the suffix-initial consonant. Generally, the cases in Sibe lend support to a perceptual account of vowel epenthesis (Côté 2000), by which vowel epenthesis is more likely to appear when the perceptual cues of the relevant consonant are undermined or at risk of recovery.

The current study has limitations in various aspects. First, the data were limited to one speaker and the discussions did not cover all the possible consonant clusters in Sibe. Second, the discussion of consonantal perception is based primarily on a conceptual understanding of the robustness of the relevant perceptual cues. Phonetic properties may not directly translate into the robustness of a cue. To discover the relative perceptual salience of different segments, evidence from perceptual experiment is needed. Third, the analysis in this study does not fully cover the complexity of vowel epenthesis in Sibe. For example, when the root-final consonant (C₁) is the uvular stop [q], the pattern is more diverse. As shown in (17), the uvular stop [q] changes to the voiced fricative [ɣ] before an obstruent. Further investigation is needed, for the details in this pattern and the perceptual cues for the uvular stop, to discuss if the pattern is relevant to the perception of /q/.

(17) Roots ending with a stop/trill

Noun	<i>with ...</i>	<i>of ...</i>	<i>than ...</i>	<i>towards...</i>	<i>to...</i>	<i>Oblique</i>	Gloss
lyɛaɕ	lyɛaɕmaq	lyɛaɕnəŋ	lyɛaɕtʰiri	lyɛaɕte ^h i	lyɛaɕət	lyɛaɕəv	‘donkey’

REFERENCES

- Broselow, Ellen (1982) On Predicting the Interaction of Stress and Epenthesis. *Glossa*, vol.16.2:115–132.
- Chao, Ke (2006) *Xiandai Xiboyu Kouyu Yanjiu* [Studies in Modern Oral Sibe]. Beijing: Minzu Chubanshe.
- Côté, Marie-Hélène (2000) Consonant Cluster Phonotactics: A Perceptual Approach. Ph.D. dissertation, MIT.
- Hall, Nancy (2003) Gestures and Segments: Vowel Intrusion as Overlap. Ph.D. dissertation, UMass.
- Hall, Nancy (2006) Cross-Linguistic Patterns of Vowel Intrusion. *Phonology*, vol.23.3:387–429.
- Hall, Nancy (2011) Vowel Epenthesis. In Marc van Oostendorp, Colin J. Ewen, Elizabeth Hume & Keren Rice (eds.) *The Blackwell Companion to Phonology*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Itô, Junko (1989) A Prosodic Theory of Epenthesis. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory*, vol.7:217–259.
- Jang, Taeho (2008) *Xiboyu Yufa Yanjiu* [Sibe Grammar]. Yunnan Minzu Chubanshe, Kunming, China.
- Jun, Jongho (1995) Perceptual and Articulatory Factors in Place Assimilation: An Optimality Theoretic Approach. Ph.D. dissertation, UCLA.
- Li, Bing (1999) Xiboyu Chunzhuang Yuanyinhexi de Congshuyinxixue Fenxi [An Analysis of Labial Vowel Harmony in Sibe: Dependence Phonology]. *Xinjiang Shifan Daxue Xuebao*, 1999, 1.
- Li, Shulan & Qian Zhong (1986) *Xiboyu Jianzhi* [A Short Introduction to Sibe]. Beijing: Minzu Chubanshe.
- Li, Shulan, Qian zhong & Fengqing Wang (1984) *Xiboyu Kouyu Yanjiu* [Studies in Oral Sibe]. Beijing: Minzu Chubanshe.
- Li, Wenxin (2015) Xiboyu Zengyin de Miaoxie yu Fenxi [Sibe Vowel Epenthesis: Description and Analysis]. *Nankai Linguistics*, vol.26.2:44–52.
- Lombardi, Linda (2002) Markedness and the Typology of Epenthetic Vowels. *Rutgers Optimality Archive* #587.
- Steriade, Donca (1994) Licensing by Cue. Unpublished ms., University of California, Los Angeles.
- Steriade, Donca (2008) The Phonology of Perceptibility Effects: The P-map and its Consequences for Constraint Organization. In Kristin Hanson & Sharon Inkelas (eds.), *The Nature of the Word: Essays in Honor of Paul Kiparsky*. The MIT Press.
- Wright, Richard (2004) A Review of Perceptual Cues and Cue Robustness. In Bruce Hayes, Robert Kirchner & Donca Steriade (eds.), *Phonetically-Based Phonology*, Cambridge University Press.

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Prof. Jie Zhang for his comments and suggestions on earlier version of this study. The data collection received great help from Wenxin Li. I would like to thank the speakers of Sibe in this study too.

Date received: 10 Feb 2025

Date accepted: 13 Mar 2025

To cite:

Li, Mingxing (2025) Vowel Epenthesis in Sibe: A Perceptual Account. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:45-55.

FLaP FIRST

Facebook

Website

重慶方言單字調及重疊變調的音系分析

沈新蕾

香港浸會大學

22429069@life.hkbu.edu.hk

摘要

本文基於聲學分析，對重慶話單字和 AA 式重疊詞的聲調進行了描寫，確認重慶話有 [h]、[hl]、[hl] 和 [hlh] 這四種調形，且每個聲調所對應的重疊詞都具有變調的現象。本文認為重慶話的底層聲調是 /l/、/h/、/ll/、/hh/，且調徵在底層無需和載調單位連接。底層聲調在一些普遍音系規則的作用下，經歷調徵的添加和擴散，從而產生了表層的單字調和重疊式變調。

關鍵詞：重慶話，單字調，變調，底層聲調，音系規則

1. 引言

重慶話是西南官話的重要代表，《中國語言地圖集》將其歸入西南官話中的川黔片。近百年來已有很多學者對重慶話的聲調進行研究，達成的共識是重慶話有陰平、陽平、上聲和去聲四個單字調，但是對其調形的描寫沒有達成一致。有人將陰平記成高平調（翟時雨 1996），也有人記成升調（朱曉農 2012）；陽平有人記成低平（範繼淹 1979），也有人記成為降調（翟時雨 1996）。上聲和去聲的描寫較為統一，多記和高降調和凹形調（翟時雨 1996；曾曉渝 1996）。

此外，重慶話中 AA 式重疊詞有變調的情況，但對此的研究較少，且尚未見有研究從音系學角度解釋重慶話重疊變調的規律。

本研究將基於一手的錄音材料，運用實驗語音和音系分析的手段探究重慶話單字調和重疊變調的生成規律。

2. 重慶話單字調和重疊變調的聲學分析

本研究共採集六名發音人（三男三女）的數據，發音人錄音時的年齡在40-50歲之間，長期生活在重慶主城區，能熟練使用重慶話。發音人的發音經過筆者檢驗（筆者母語也是重慶話），均為地道的重慶話。

本研究以「不送氣清塞音+單元音」的形式為最優原則，選取12個實驗例字（每個調類3個字）和20個實驗例詞（每個調類的重疊式5個詞），實驗例字、例詞表見附錄（1）。例字、詞用 PPT 的形式（一頁一個字、詞），無序地呈現在發音人面前，請發音人讀出。用 MacBook 進行錄音，並使用 Praat 語音軟件將其保存為 WAV 格式。

本研究利用腳本 ProsodyPro (Xu, 2013) 測量並提取每單字調上10個等距時間點上基頻值；每個 A₁A₂ 式重疊詞聲調共提取20個（A₁, A₂ 各10個）等距時間點的基頻值。完成各個例字的基頻提取後，按各個聲調計算出每個聲調每個時刻的平均值，然後採用石鋒的 T 值法對基頻值進行歸一，T 值的計算公式見（1）。

（1）T 值計算公式（石鋒 2009）

$$T = \frac{\lg x - \lg (\min)}{\lg (\max) - \lg (\min)} \times 5$$

計算出的 T 值用 Excel 軟件繪製出重慶話單字調語圖和重疊式聲調語圖，如（2）和（3）所示。每個聲調由三條線組成，中間的線是六名發音人 T 值的平均值，上下兩條虛線表示 T 值的平均值加/減 T 值的標準差，由此得到一條 T 值的帶狀曲線圖。

（2）重慶話單字調語圖

調類	聲調語圖	調形	調類	聲調語圖	調形
陰平		升降調			
陽平		降升調			

圖例說明：語圖中的縱坐標表示 T 值，橫坐標表示測量點。

（3）重慶話 AA 式重疊詞語圖

調類	聲調語圖	調形
陰平+陰平		high low 升調 + 高平
陽平+陽平		降調 + 低平
上聲+上聲		升調 + 降調
去聲+去聲		降調 + 升調

為了方便音系分析，本文根據（2）和（3）中的語圖，採用 h(igh) 高調徵和 l(ow) 低調徵對重慶話單字調和重疊詞聲調進行描寫，詳見表（4）和（5）所示。

（4）重慶話單字調四種

調類	T1	T2	T3	T4
單字調	[lh]	[hl]	[lhl]	[hlh]
例字	低	敵	底	弟

（5）重慶話 AA 式重疊詞聲調四種

調類	T1	T2	T3	T4
AA 式重疊	[lh, h]	[hl, l]	[lh, hl]	[hl, lh]
例字	渣渣	盆盆	果果	院院

3. 重慶話聲調配給音節模型及底層調

本研究認為重慶話聲調配給模型如（6）所示，值得注意的是調徵和載調單位莫拉在底層不用提前連接，圖中虛線表示連接線是在一些普遍音系規則，如（i）不允許兩個相同的調徵相鄰；（ii）兩個調徵不能共享一個載調單位；（iii）底層調徵必須和左端相連，的作用下連接起來的。每一次連接的過程都需要遵循（a）載調單位和調徵以一對一的方式從左往右連接和（b）禁止連接線交叉，這兩個連接規約（Durand 1990:249）。

（6）聲調配給音節模型

同時本研究大膽假設重慶話的底層聲調為對稱的平形調 /l/、/h/、/ll/、/hh/。第四、第五節的分析會證明：假設的底層聲調和聲調配給模型可以很精巧地解釋重慶話表層的單字調和重疊詞聲調的生成。

4. 重慶話單字調的生成機製

運用第三節的假設，在一些普遍音系規則的作用下，就可以產生重慶話的單字調。具體來說，由兩個相同調徵組成的 T3、T4 底層聲調 /ll/、/hh/，在制約條件²：（i）不允許兩個相同的調徵相鄰（OCP）的作用下發生異化，即一個與底層調徵相異的調徵將添加在中間，打破底層相鄰相同的格局，分別產生 /lhl/、/hlh/。又因制約條件（ii）不能刪除調徵（即，MAX-t）的排序要高於（iii）兩個調徵不能共享一個載調單位（即，*MULTILINK[μ, t]），所以聲調序列 /lhl/、/hlh/ 不能刪除調徵，有兩個調徵需要共享一

¹ 重慶話中音節選擇一個或者兩個莫拉跟調形有關，與聲調的時間長短和節奏無關。

² 文章出現的所有制約條件定義見附錄（2）。

個莫拉，最終生成 T3、T4 的單字調 [lh] 和 [hlh]。重慶話 T3 和 T4 的生成過程見 (7)。圖中被圈出的是新增調徵，沒被圈出的是底層調徵。

(7) 重慶話 T3、T4 的單字調的生成過程

T1 和 T2 的底層聲調 /l/、/h/ 在音系規則 (i) 兩個載調單位不能共享一個調徵 (此處載調單位是莫拉 μ ，即，*MULTILINK[t, μ]，自 Wee 2019:156) 和 (ii) 底層調徵必須和左端相連 (即，ALIGN-LEFT，自 McCarthy & Prince, 1993: 34) 的共同作用下，在底層聲調的右側添加一個調徵，保證有兩個調徵分別和兩個莫拉相連，從而產生的 T1、T2 的單字調 [lh] 和 [hl]。重慶話 T1 和 T2 的單字調的生成過程如 (8) 所示。

(8) 重慶話 T1、T2 的單字調的生成過程

5. 重慶話疊詞變調的音系機制

本文認為重慶話 AA 式重疊的本質是對音節的複製，且複製的內容不包括底層調徵，所以 AA 式重疊詞的底層是兩個音節和一套對應的調徵。T1、T2 重疊詞底層聲調 /l/、/h/ 在 (i) 音系規則 *MULTILINK[t, μ] 和 ALIGN-LEFT 的作用下，在底層聲調的右側添加一個調徵，分別形成第一個音節的聲調 [hl] 和 [lh]。又由於 (ii) 添加的聲調擴散現象，第一個音節的右端調徵擴散到第二個音節的莫拉上，分別形成 T1 和 T2 第二個音節的聲調 [h] 和 [l]。T1 和 T2 重疊式變調的過程如 (9) 所示。

(9) T1 和 T2 重疊式變調的過程

b. T2 的 AA 式重疊

T3、T4 重疊式的底層聲調是 /l/ 和 /hh/，(i) 受到OCP的影響，調徵序列中間需要插入一個相異的調徵，形成 /lh/ 和 /hlh/；(ii) 新插入的調徵需要通過擴散和兩個音節同時連接，所以 T3、T4 底層中新添加的高調徵、低調徵和中間兩個莫拉連接，底層兩個調徵依據載調單位和調徵以一對一的方式從左往右連接的原則，依次與最左端莫拉和最右邊莫拉連接，形成 [lh, hl] 和 [hl, lh]。T3 和 T4 重疊式變調的過程如 (10) 所示。

(10) T3 和 T4 重疊式變調的過程

a. T3 的AA式重疊

b. T4 的AA式重疊

6. 結語

本文根據六名發音人的語音材料，將重慶話單字調描寫為 [lh]、[hl]、[lhl] 和 [hlh]；AA式重疊詞的聲調描寫為 [lh, h]、[hl, l]、[lh, hl] 和 [hl, lh]。通過對重慶話表層聲調生成過程的分析，我們發現重慶話單字和重疊詞的聲調都可以由具有對稱性的底層調庫 /l/、/h/、/ll/、/hh/ 在 (i) 不允許兩個相同的調徵相鄰；(ii) 兩個調徵不能共享一個載調單位；(iii) 調徵擴散規則，的作用下生成。值得注意的是，本研究還證明在重慶話中，無論是單字調還是重疊式聲調，調徵和載調單位莫拉在底層不用提前連接，連接完全可以通過聲調配給模型和音系規則生成。

附錄

(1) 重慶方言單字調實驗例字、詞

表一：重慶方言單字調實驗例字

調類	例字		
T1	低 [ti]	都 [tu]	他 [t ^h a]
T2	敵 [ti]	讀 [tu]	答 [ta]
T3	底 [ti]	賭 [tu]	打 [ta]
T4	弟 [ti]	度 [tu]	大 [ta]

表二：重慶方言 AA 式重疊實驗例詞

調類	例詞				
T1+T1	絲絲 [si si]	渣渣 [tsatsa]	坡坡 [p ^h o p ^h o]	刀刀 [tau tau]	帶帶 [tæi tæi]
T2+T2	棚棚 [p ^h oŋ p ^h oŋ]	盒盒 [xɛ xɛ]	碟碟 [tiɛ tiɛ]	蚊蚊 [wen wen]	圓圓 [yɛn yɛn]
T3+T3	碗碗 [wan wan]	嘴嘴 [tsuei tsuei]	眼眼 [iɛn iɛn]	舀舀 [iau iau]	姐姐 [te ^h iai te ^h iai]
T4+T4	洞洞 [toŋ toŋ]	壩壩 [pa pa]	院院 [yɛn yɛn]	露露 [lu lu]	串串 [tshuan tshuan]

(2) 分析重慶話所需的普遍制約條件及定義

MAX-t

每一次輸入項中存在的調徵在輸出項沒有出現，就違反此制約條件一次。

ALIGN-LEFT

每一次輸入調徵與輸出項左邊緣之間出現間隔的莫拉，就違反此制約條件一次。

OCP

每一次相鄰且相同的調徵，就會違反此制約條件一次。

***MULTILINK[μ, t]**

每一次一個莫拉和超過一個調徵相連，就會違反此制約條件一次。

***MULTILINK[t, μ]**

每一次一個調徵和超過一個莫拉相連，就會違反此制約條件一次。

參考文獻

- 範繼淹，〈重慶方言「下」字的分化〉，《方言》，1979年，期2，頁88-92。
 石鋒，《實驗音系學探索》，北京：北京大學出版社，2008年。
 曾曉渝，《重慶方言詞解》，重慶：西南師範大學出版社，1996年，頁4。
 翟時雨，《重慶方言誌》，重慶：西南大學出版社，1996年，頁45-46。

朱曉農，〈演化比較法：如何進行聲調演化的研究？〉，《語言科學》，2018年，卷17，期2，頁113–132。

Durand, Jacques (1990) *Generative and Non-linear Phonology*. London: Longman.

McCarthy, John J. & Alan Prince (1993) Generalized Alignment. In Geert Booij & Jaap van Marle (eds.), *Yearbook of morphology 1993*, pp.79–153.

Wee, Lian-Hee (2019) *Phonological Tone*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Xu, Yi (2013) ProsodyPro—A Tool for Large-scale Systematic Prosody Analysis. *Proceedings of TRASP 2013*, Aix-en-Provence, France, pp.7–10.

鳴謝：

在此特別感謝黃良喜老師對這篇文章所提出的寶貴修改建議。同時，對那六位慷慨提供錄音的發音人表示感謝，由於倫理規定，無法公開他們的姓名，但他們的錄音對研究至關重要。也十分感謝 HKBU Phonology Laboratory 提供的場地和設備支持。最後，衷心感謝匿名評審專家為本篇文章提出的寶貴建議，這些建議對提升本文質量起到了非常積極的作用。若文中存在任何疏漏或不當之處，均由筆者本人負責。

The Phonological Study of Monosyllabic Tones and Reduplication Tone Sandhi in Chongqing Mandarin

SHEN Xinlei

Hong Kong Baptist University

22429069@life.hkbu.edu.hk

Abstract: Based on acoustic analysis, this study describes the four monosyllabic tones in Chongqing Mandarin as [lh], [hl], [lhl] and [hlh], and the AA reduplication form of each monosyllabic tone has the phenomenon of tone sandhi. This study argues that the underlying tone inventory of Chongqing Mandarin is /l/, /h/, /ll/, /hh/, and there is no requirement for any initial mapping between the tones and the moras. The underlying tone inventory will generate monosyllabic tones and reduplication tone sandhi under the action of some universal phonological rules.

Keywords: Chongqing Mandarin, Monosyllabic Tone, Tone Sandhi, Underlying Tone, Phonological Constraints

Copyright 2025. Xinlei Shen.

Date received: 09 December 2024

Date accepted: 14 February 2025

FLaP FIRST

Facebook

Website

To cite:

Shen, Xinlei (2025) 重慶方言單字調及重疊變調的音系分析 Chongqing fangyan danzidiao ji chongdie biandiao de yinxi fenxi [The Phonological Study of Monosyllabic Tones and Reduplication Tone Sandhi in Chongqing Mandarin]. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:56-62.

Phonological Profile of Gyersgang Tibetan: An Endangered Eastern Tibetic Language Spoken in Thebo, Western China

Sirui Du
The Chinese University of Hong Kong
du_sirui03@163.com

Daai-Syut Yeung
Lacito-CNRS-Paris 3
yeungdaaisyut@gmail.com

Abstract

Eastern Tibetic languages are renowned for their linguistic richness and low mutual intelligibility. While there has been some prior research on the Eastern section, many unique Tibetan dialects in this linguistically rich region remain underdocumented. Thebo, as an Eastern Tibetic language, can be divided into two mutually unintelligible dialects: Upper Thebo and Lower Thebo (The Gazetteers Committee 1998). However, the Gyersgang dialect, located between Upper and Lower Thebo, can be understood by speakers of both dialects. This paper, by illustrating the "intermediate" diachronic phonological changes of Gyersgang, alongside lexical and morphosyntactic evidence, seeks to unravel the puzzle of how it serves as a bridge between two mutually unintelligible dialects. Furthermore, it explores Gyersgang's genetic and contact relationships with surrounding dialects through a multidisciplinary synthesis of linguistic, anthropological, and historical evidence, clarifying its diachronic position within the Tibetic continuum.

Keywords: Tibetan, Tibetic languages, historical linguistics, sound change, chain shift

1. Introduction

As a significant branch of the Sino-Tibetan language family, the genetic classification of Tibetic languages has long been a subject of interest (Nishida 1970; Qu & Jin 1981; Jin 1983; van Driem 2001; Tournadre 2014; Sagart et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2019; Dhakal et al. 2024). Traditionally, Tibetic languages within China have been classified into three major groups: Ü-Tsang, Amdo, and Khams (GesangJumian & GesangYangjing 2002). Later, Jiang (2002), Tournadre (2014), and Bielmeier & Driem (2018) expanded the classification to include Tibetic languages spoken outside China, refining their grouping based on geographic distribution and shared linguistic features. Tournadre & Suzuki (2023) further adopted Tournadre (2014)'s eight-way classification of Tibetic languages: South-Eastern, Eastern, North-Eastern, Central, Southern, South-Western, Western, and North-Western. Thebo Tibetan belongs to the Eastern section in their classification, which covers southern Gansu and northern Sichuan. This region is known for its high dialectal diversity, low mutual intelligibility, and limited documentation (Lin 2014; Jacques 2014; Chirkova and Amelot 2013; Sun 2003; Yang et al. 2024; Du 2024; Yeung 2024; Ye forthcoming). Gyersgang, an endangered Tibetan dialect, is an unrecorded dialect from this area.

Gyersgang Tibetan (hereafter Gyersgang) is spoken in central Thebo County, Gannan Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Gansu Province, China. The Tibetan dialects in Thebo are generally divided into an Upper group and a Lower group, with the dialects of these groups being mutually unintelligible (The Gazetteer Committee 1998; RenzengWangmu 2013; Yang et al. 2024; Yeung 2024). However, Gyersgang, as a central Thebo Tibetan, is mutually intelligible with both Upper and Lower Thebo dialects. In Figure 1.1, the red region on the left represents the Upper Thebo area, while the yellow region on the right marks the Lower Thebo

area. The overlapping section, identified as the "Middle Thebo" area, indicates its mutual intelligibility with both Upper and Lower dialects.

This paper investigates the diachronic phonology of Gyersgang, analyzing its inherited stratum and non-inherited strata, while systematically comparing its developmental pathways with phonological changes in neighboring Tibetan dialects. By addressing these multilayered interactions, this paper offers an explanation of its unique status as a mutually intelligible bridge between two mutually unintelligible dialects. Furthermore, by drawing on evidence from historical phonology, lexicon, and morphosyntax, it offers a well-founded explanation for the dialect's mutual intelligibility and clarifies its historical position within the Tibetic linguistic landscape.

Figure 1.1 Location of Gyersgang and two dialects in Thebo County

The paper is structured into 7 main sections: Section 2 provides an overview of the synchronic phonology of Gyersgang. Building upon this foundation, Sections 3 through 5 explore the phonological history of Gyersgang through initial (Section 3), rhyme (Section 4), and tonal developments (Section 5). Section 6 establishes Gyersgang's intermediate status through convergent evidence from historical comparative, lexical and morphosyntactic evidence. Section 7 provides a summary of Gyersgang's diachronic sound changes and its intermediate status.

2. Synchronic phonology

2.1 Syllable canon

In Gyersgang, Classical Tibetan's (hereafter CT) preinitials and codas have been lost. Consequently, only simple onsets exist in Gyersgang. The syllable structure in Gyersgang is very simple, changed from (CC)C(M)V(CC) to (C)V(V), where C represents a consonant, V represents a vowel, the two vowel-symbol notation represents a diphthong, and parentheses indicate optional constituents.

Table 2.1 Gyersgang syllable structure

V	i ^H	⟨g.yis⟩	oil	油 (通名)
VV	yo ^N tei ^H	⟨yob.lcags⟩	stirrup	馬蹬
CV	k ^h e ^H	⟨kha⟩	mouth	嘴
CVV	ɕuo ^H	⟨sram⟩	otter	水獺
(CVr)	dze ^N k ^h ur ^H	⟨rgya.?-r⟩	Han region	漢地
(CVVr)	di ^N ɕuor ^N	⟨?.zhabs-r⟩	Below	底下

The so-called -r coda in Gyersgang can be pronounced in the exchangeable form /rə/. The pseudo-r coda is a trace of the locative marker ⟨la.don⟩ in CT.

2.2 Initials

Gyersgang has 33 initial consonants, all of which are simple consonants. These consonant phonemes represent four distinct places of articulation (bilabial/labio-dental, alveolar, alveolo-palatal, and velar/uvular) and six manners of articulation: stop, affricate, fricative, nasal, lateral approximant, and approximant.

Table 2.2 Gyersgang initials

Bilabial/Labio-dental	Alveolar	Alveolo-palatal	Velar/Uvular
p	t		k
p ^h	t ^h		k ^h
b	d		g
	ts	tɕ	
	ts ^h	tɕ ^h	
	dz	dʒ	
m	n	ɲ	ŋ
	s	ɕ	ç
	s ^h	ɕ ^h	ç ^h
	z	ʒ	ʝ
v (w)	l		
	r	j	

The realization of /r/ varies and exhibits a high degree of freedom in its articulation, including [r, ɹ, r̥].

The uvular voiceless fricative /ç/ has been selected regarding the actual pronunciation, rather than focusing on a neat-looking system (/x - x^h - /ɣ/).

The consonants [w] and [v] are in free variation.

2.3 Rhymes

Gyersgang has twenty rhymes, with twelve being single vowel phonemes and eight being diphthongs. There is a four-way contrast in front vowel height and a three-way contrast in back vowel height. The simple rhymes exhibit a three-way contrast in length, categorized as extra-short, short, and long, which is typologically rare (Kuznetsova 2025).

Table 2.3 Gyersgang rhymes

	extra-short			short			long		
simple	ĩ	ỹ	ũ	i	y	u	i:	y:	u:
	ě		ǎ	e		ə	e:		ə:
	ɛ			ɛ			ɛ:		
	ǎ		ǎ	a		ɐ	a:		ɐ:
complex								yo	uo
							iɛ	yɛ	
							ia	ya	ua
							ia		

The vowel /ə/ is realized as [ə, ɿ, ʊ]. /ə/ is pronounced as [ɿ] when it occurs after the alveolar consonants; and is pronounced as [ʊ] when it occurs after /r/.

Among the 8 diphthongs in Gyersgang, only /iɛ, uo/ exhibit relatively high frequency. Of the remaining 6 diphthongs, /yɛ/ appears exclusively in six words: ⟨ma.ma.chung⟩ /mo^Nmo:^Hte^Hyɛ^L/ "aunt 孀孀", ⟨a.khu.chung⟩ /a:^Hγə^Hte^Hyɛ^L/ "uncle 叔叔", ⟨lung.pa⟩ /lyɛ^L/ "valley 山谷", ⟨vdi.vdra⟩ /dyɛ^H/ "this way 這樣", ⟨de.ltar⟩ /tyɛ^H/ "that way 那樣", and ⟨snying.rje⟩ /ŋyɛ^Hte^Hi^N/ "pitiful 可憐". /yo/ occurs only in five words: ⟨yob.lcags⟩ /yo^Ntei:^H/ "stirrup 馬蹬", ⟨bzhon⟩ /yo^H/ "ride 騎", ⟨(?)⟩ /yo^Nmə^H/ "diligent 勤快", ⟨yu.ba⟩ /yo^Nbu^H/ "handle 把兒", and ⟨yang.po⟩ /yo^Nmə^H/ "light 輕的". /ia/ is restricted to two words: ⟨go.thal⟩ /t^hia^L/ "plant ash 草木灰" and ⟨(?)⟩ /t^hia^L/ "plane 鉋子". /ia/ appears solely in ⟨tshong.pa⟩ /k^hia^L/ "merchant 商人". /ya/ occurs exclusively in ⟨lci.ba⟩ /teya^H/ "cow dung 牛糞".

2.4 Tones

In tonemic terms, Gyersgang exhibits a two-way register contrast: high vs. low. The realization of these two tones varies depending on the type of rhyme to which they are assigned. In extra-short rhyme, the high tone is realized as 53, and the low tone is realized as 22. In short rhymes, the high tone is generally realized with a high falling contour 51, and the low tone is realized as 13. In lone rhymes, the high tone is realized as a high level tone 55, and the low tone is realized with a low rising contour 13.

Table 2.4 Gyersgang tones

	extra-short	short	long
High	22	51	55
Low	53	13	13

Gyiba and Ridang exhibit a partial tone system (Lin 2014; Yang et al. 2024; Yeung 2024), where tones contrast as high and low, but only after sonorant or voiceless unaspirated obstruent initials. Gyersgang exhibits a partial tone system where the register contrast is not restricted to syllables with voiced obstruent initials.

In polysyllabic words, a neutralized tone (N) appears as either 21 or 31, depending on its position. As neutralized boundary tones, 21 marks the beginning of a phonological word,

while 31 marks the end of a phonological word. 21 and 31 only appear at the last syllable in some polysyllabic words and are never found in a monosyllabic word.

3. Developments of initials

3.1 Inherited developments of initials

3.1.1 CT simple initials

Within Gyersgang, CT simple initials including voiceless stops and affricates, nasals, and laterals remain largely unchanged. Voiced stops and affricates undergo devoicing, with the approximant ⟨y-⟩ changing into /j-/ or /y-/, as shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Inherited developments of CT simple consonants

⟨k-⟩	k	⟨c-⟩	tɕ	⟨t-⟩	t	⟨p-⟩	p	⟨ts-⟩	ts
⟨kh-⟩	k^h	⟨ch-⟩	tɕ^h	⟨th-⟩	t^h	⟨ph-⟩	p^h	⟨tsh-⟩	ts^h
⟨g-⟩	k	⟨j-⟩	tɕ	⟨d-⟩	t	⟨b-⟩	p	⟨dz-⟩	-
⟨s-⟩	s^h	⟨z-⟩	s	⟨sh-⟩	ɕ^h	⟨zh-⟩	ɕ	⟨h-⟩	ɕ
⟨ng-⟩	ŋ	⟨ny-⟩	ŋ	⟨n-⟩	n	⟨m-⟩	m	⟨v-⟩	v
⟨r-⟩	r	⟨l-⟩	l	⟨y-⟩	j,y	⟨w-⟩	v	⟨ʔ-⟩	ʔ

Stops and affricates. In Gyersgang, all CT simple stops and affricates remain unchanged. Additionally, in the non-inherited stratum, examples of voicing in voiceless stops can be observed (refer to Section 3.2). This voicing phenomenon has also been in other dialects of Thebo (Yang et al. 2024; Yeung 2024).

Table 3.2 Inherited developments of CT simple voiceless stop and affricate initials

⟨k-⟩	⟨(rgya.) ku ⟩	kə^H	pear	梨
	⟨ ka .ba)⟩	ka^L	pillar	柱子
⟨c-⟩	⟨ cog .tse)⟩	tɕo^Htsiɛ^H	table	桌子
	⟨ cavo .tsi)⟩	tɕu^Htsə^H	Dumplings	餃子
⟨t-⟩	⟨me. tog ⟩	me^Ntu^H	flower	花
	⟨po. ta .la)⟩	pu^Lta^Hla^Ni^N	The Potala Palace	布達拉
⟨p-⟩	⟨lus. po ⟩	lə^Lpo^H	body	身體
	⟨thod. pa ⟩	the^Npe^H	forehead	額頭
⟨ts-⟩	⟨ tsong .ʔ)⟩	tsu^H	Chinese onion	蔥
	⟨cog. tsə ⟩	tɕo^Htsiɛ^H	table	桌子
⟨ʔ-⟩	⟨ ʔa .pha)⟩	a^Npa^H	father	父親
	⟨ ʔa .lu)⟩	a^Hlə^H	cat	貓

Table 3.3 Inherited developments of CT simple voiceless unaspirated stop and affricate initials

⟨kh-⟩	⟨kha⟩	$k^h e^H$	mouth	嘴
	⟨khal⟩	$k^h i \epsilon : H i : H$	twenty	二十
⟨ch-⟩	⟨chu⟩	$t \epsilon^h \partial^H$	water	水
	⟨cha.myed⟩	$t \epsilon^h \epsilon^N \eta i^H$	stranger	陌生人
⟨th-⟩	⟨thal⟩	$t^h i a^L$	plant ash	草木灰
	⟨thod.pa⟩	$t^h e^N p e^H$	forehead	額頭
⟨ph-⟩	⟨phag⟩	$p^h a^H$	pig	豬
	⟨phu.rung⟩	$p^h \partial^N r y : H$	gusset	衣袖
⟨tsh-⟩	⟨tsha.mo⟩	$t s^h e^N m \partial^H$	granddaughter	孫女
	⟨tshes.gcig⟩	$t s^h e^L t e i^H$	calends	初一

In Gyersgang, all CT simple voiced stops and affricates undergo devoicing (Table 3.4).

Table 3.4 Inherited developments of CT simple voiced stop and affricate initials

⟨g-⟩	⟨gug⟩	$k \partial^N r \partial^H$	bend	彎 (彎的)
⟨j-⟩	⟨jem.tse⟩	$t \epsilon e^N d z \epsilon : H$	scissor	剪子
	⟨ja⟩	$t \epsilon e^H$	tea	茶
⟨d-⟩	⟨dug⟩	$t y^L$	poison	毒
	⟨dom⟩	$t u :^L$	bear	熊
⟨b-⟩	⟨ba⟩	$p e^H$	cow	母黃牛
	⟨bu⟩	$p \partial^H$	son	兒子

Fricatives. For fricatives, voiceless fricative initials ⟨s-, sh-⟩ developed into voiceless aspirated fricatives /s^h-, χ^h-/ respectively, while ⟨h-⟩ developed into /χ-/ , merging with ⟨zh-⟩ (Table 3.5).

Table 3.5 Inherited developments of CT simple voiceless fricatives

⟨s-⟩	⟨sa⟩	$s^h e^H$	land	地
	⟨so⟩	$s^h o^H$	tooth	牙齒
⟨sh-⟩	⟨sha⟩	$\chi^h e^H$	meat	肉
	⟨shig⟩	$\chi^h i^H$	louse	虱
⟨h-⟩	⟨ha.go⟩	$\chi a :^H k o^N$	understand	明白

Voiced fricatives all undergo devoicing. The initials ⟨z-, zh-⟩ have changed into /s-, χ-/ respectively (Table 3.6).

Table 3.6 Inherited developments of CT simple voiced fricatives

⟨z-⟩	⟨zam.pa⟩	$s a^N b e^N$	bridge	橋
	⟨zil.pa⟩	$s i^N a :^H$	dew, dewdrop	露水
⟨zh-⟩	⟨zhu⟩	$\chi \partial^N$	melt	溶化

A chain shift sound change occurred in the fricatives.

Figure 3.1 The chain shift in CT simple fricatives

$$\begin{aligned} \langle z \rangle &\rightarrow s \\ \langle s \rangle &\rightarrow s^h \\ \langle sh \rangle &\rightarrow \chi^h \\ \langle zh \rangle \langle h \rangle &\rightarrow \chi \end{aligned}$$

The initial ⟨z-⟩ undergoes devoicing changing into /s-/, subsequently driving the development of ⟨s-⟩ into /s^h-/, and ⟨sh-⟩ into /χ^h-/; ⟨zh-⟩ merges with ⟨h-⟩, collectively changing into /χ-/.

Nasals and liquids. In the inherited development of Gyersgang, nasals and liquids have remained unchanged (Table 3.7). However, in nasals ⟨(C)ny-⟩ and ⟨(C)ng-⟩, there are instances of interchangeability between them. This phenomenon will be described in Section 3.2.

Table 3.7 Inherited developments of CT simple nasal initials

⟨ng-⟩	⟨nga⟩	ŋō ^H	I	我
	⟨lag.ngar⟩	la ^L ŋa ^H	arm	胳膊
⟨ny-⟩	⟨nya⟩	ɲẽ ^L	fish	魚
	⟨nyi.ma⟩	ɲə ^N mo ^H	sun	太陽
⟨n-⟩	⟨nags⟩	nǎ ^L	forest	森林
	⟨nad.pa⟩	ne ^N pə ^H	patient	病人
⟨m-⟩	⟨mar⟩	ma ^L	ghee	酥油 (黃油)
	⟨me.tog⟩	me ^N tu ^H	flower	花

Table 3.8 Inherited developments of CT simple liquid initials

⟨r-⟩	⟨ra⟩	rẽ ^L	goat	羊
	⟨ro⟩	rō ^L	corpse	屍體
⟨l-⟩	⟨a.lu⟩	a ^H lə ^H	cat	貓
	⟨lus.po⟩	lə ^L po ^H	body	身體

Approximants. The approximant ⟨y-⟩ became /y-/ or /j-/ depending on the words (Table 3.9). In other Tibetan dialects, the simple initial ⟨v-⟩ typically disappeared or developed into a glottal stop initial /ʔ-/. However, in Gyersgang, the unique development of ⟨v-⟩ has resulted in /v-/, merging with ⟨w-⟩.

Table 3.9 Inherited developments of CT simple approximant initials

⟨w-⟩	⟨wa.mo⟩	ve ^N mə ^H	fox	狐狸
⟨y-⟩>j	⟨so.ya.rkan⟩	s ^h o ^H jə ^N kɛ ^H	palate	齶
⟨y-⟩>y	⟨yob.lcags⟩	yo ^N tci ^H	stirrups	馬蹬子
⟨v-⟩	⟨von.pa⟩	ve ^N bə ^H	deaf person	聾子

3.1.2 Developments of CT preinitialed clusters ⟨(C)CC-⟩

In some Tibetic languages, CT preinitials prevent the main consonant from devoicing. In Gyersgang, however, only prenasals inhibit devoicing when the main consonant is a stop or affricate; non-nasal preinitials do not prevent devoicing (Table 3.10).

Table 3.10 Inherited developments of CT preinitialed clusters 1

⟨dk-⟩	k	⟨gc-⟩	tɕ	⟨gt-⟩	t	⟨dp-⟩	p	⟨gts-⟩	ts
⟨bk-⟩	k	⟨bc-⟩	tɕ	⟨bt-⟩	t			⟨bts-⟩	ts
⟨rk-⟩	k			⟨rt-⟩	t			⟨rts-⟩	ts
⟨lk-⟩	-	⟨lc-⟩	tɕ	⟨lt-⟩	t	⟨lp-⟩	-		
⟨sk-⟩	k			⟨st-⟩	t	⟨sp-⟩	p	⟨sts-⟩	-
⟨mkh-⟩	k^h	⟨mch-⟩	tɕ^h	⟨mth-⟩	t^h			⟨mtsh-⟩	ts^h
⟨vkh-⟩	k^h	⟨vch-⟩	tɕ^h	⟨vth-⟩	t^h	⟨vph-⟩	p^h	⟨vtsh-⟩	ts^h
⟨dg-⟩	k			⟨gd-⟩	t	⟨db-⟩	-		
⟨bg-⟩	k			⟨bd-⟩	t				
⟨mg-⟩	g	⟨mj-⟩	dz	⟨md-⟩	d			⟨mdz-⟩	dz
⟨vg-⟩	g	⟨vj-⟩	dz	⟨vd-⟩	d	⟨vb-⟩	b	⟨vdz-⟩	dz
⟨rg-⟩	j	⟨rj-⟩	tɕ	⟨rd-⟩	t	⟨rb-⟩	-	⟨rdz-⟩	ts
⟨lg-⟩	-	⟨lj-⟩	tɕ	⟨ld-⟩	t	⟨lb-⟩	-		
⟨sg-⟩	k					⟨sb-⟩	-		

For fricatives, the pattern differs from stops and affricates: both pre-nasal and non-nasal preinitials prevent devoicing of the main consonant, as shown in Table 3.11. The preinitial also prevents the chain shift of fricatives observed in CT simple initials. For instance, instead of shifting to /s^h-, ⟨gs-⟩ has developed into /s-/.

Table 3.11 Inherited developments of CT preinitialed clusters 2

⟨gs-⟩	s	⟨gsh-⟩	ɕ				
⟨bs-⟩	s	⟨bsh-⟩	ɕ				
⟨bz-⟩	z	⟨bzh-⟩	ɣ			⟨lh-⟩	l,ɕ
⟨dng-⟩	-	⟨gny-⟩	ɳ	⟨gn-⟩	n	⟨dm-⟩	m
⟨mng-⟩	ŋ	⟨mny-⟩	-	⟨mn-⟩	n		
⟨rng-⟩	ŋ	⟨rny-⟩	ɳ			⟨rm-⟩	m
⟨lng-⟩	ŋ			⟨rn-⟩	n		
⟨sng-⟩	ŋ	⟨sny-⟩	ɳ	⟨sn-⟩	n	⟨sm-⟩	m

Developments of voiceless stops and affricates with preinitials. The preinitials of voiceless stops and affricates have all dropped, and the main consonants remain unchanged (Table 3.12).

Table 3.12 Inherited developments of ⟨C + voiceless stops or affricates⟩

⟨Ck-⟩	⟨ dk av⟩	kɛ ^H	diffcult	難
	⟨ bk og⟩	ko ^H	hoe	鋤 (正在~草)
	⟨ rka ⟩	kɛ ^H	ditch	水渠
	⟨ sk ad⟩	kɛ ^H	sound	聲音
	⟨ bsk ams⟩	kuo ^H	dried up	乾 (正在變~)
⟨Ckh-⟩	⟨ mk har⟩	k^ha ^L	wall	牆
	⟨ vk hor.lo⟩	k^ho^Nlo ^H	wheel	輪子
⟨Cc-⟩	⟨ gc ig⟩	tɕi ^H	one	一
	⟨ bc ad⟩	tɕi ^H	to close	合上 (~書)
	⟨ lc ags⟩	tɕa ^H	iron	鐵
⟨Cch-⟩	⟨ mch od.me⟩	tɕ^ho^Nme ^H	butter lamp	酥油燈
	⟨ vch u⟩	tɕ^hə ^H	scoop	舀 (~水)
⟨Ct-⟩	⟨ gt am.po⟩	tɑ^Npe ^H	story	故事
	⟨kha. bt ags⟩	k^ha^Nta ^H	Khata	哈達
	⟨ rt a⟩	tɕ^h ^H	horse	馬
	⟨ lt ogs⟩	to ^H	hungry	餓
	⟨ st ag pa⟩	ta^Hpa ^H	birch	樺樹皮
	⟨窟. brt ol.brdal⟩	k^hy^Nta^Hta ^H	pierce	穿孔
⟨Cth-⟩	⟨ mth e.bo⟩	t^he^Nwu ^L	thumb	拇指
	⟨ vth ung⟩	t^hy ^H	drink	喝
⟨Cts-⟩	⟨ gts av⟩	tɕɛ ^H	rust	鏽
	⟨ bt sums⟩	tsy ^H	close	閉 (~口)
	⟨ rts a⟩	tɕɛ ^H	tendon	筋
⟨Ctsh-⟩	⟨ mt sho⟩	ts^ho ^H	lake	湖
	⟨kha. vt shig⟩	k^hɛ^Hts^hi ^H	spicy	辣

Developments of voiced stops and affricates with a preinitial. In Gyersgang, prenasals in CT prevent the main voiced stops and affricates from devoicing (Table 3.13), while non-nasal preinitials do not prevent the devoicing of voiced consonants (Table 3.14).

Table 3.13 Inherited developments of ⟨N + voiced stops or affricates⟩

⟨mg-⟩	⟨mgo⟩	g ō ^L	head	頭
	⟨mgar.ba⟩	g e ^N r ^r e ^H	blacksmith	鐵匠
⟨vg-⟩	⟨sa.vgul⟩	s ^h e ^H g i ^N	earthquake	地震
⟨mj-⟩	⟨mjal⟩	dz ε ^L	worship	拜 (~菩薩)
⟨vj-⟩	⟨vju⟩	dzi ^L	hold	扶 (~欄杆)
⟨md-⟩	⟨mdav⟩	d ǔ ^L	arrow	箭
	⟨mdog⟩	d ū ^L	colour	顏色
⟨vd-⟩	⟨vdi⟩	d ǎ ^L	this	這
	⟨vdon⟩	d e ^L	read	讀
⟨vb-⟩	⟨vbag⟩	ba ^L	mask	面具
	⟨vbu⟩	b ǎ ^L	worm	蟲
⟨mdz-⟩	⟨mdzo⟩	dz ō ^L	dzo (cattle-yak)	犏牛
	⟨mdzub.dkris⟩	dzu ^N e ⁱ ^H	ring	戒指
⟨vdz-⟩	⟨vdzugs⟩	dzy ^H	plant	栽 (~樹)
	⟨vdzul⟩	dzi ^L	drill	鑽 (~洞)

Table 3.14 Inherited developments of ⟨non-N + voiced stops or affricates⟩

⟨dg-⟩	⟨dgu⟩	k ǎ ^L	nine	九
	⟨dgav⟩	k e ^L	love	愛
⟨bg-⟩	⟨bgo⟩	k e ^L	to distribute	分 (~東西)
⟨rg-⟩	⟨phag.rgod⟩	p ^h a ^N k e ^H	wild boar	野豬
	⟨rgan.mo⟩	k ε ^N mə ^H	woman	婦女
⟨sg-⟩	⟨sgo.dwags⟩	ku ^N ta ^H	livestock	牲畜
	⟨sgug⟩	ky ^L	wait	等待
⟨rj-⟩	⟨rkang.rjen⟩	kuo ^H te ⁱ ^H	barefoot	赤腳
⟨brj-⟩	⟨brje⟩	te e ^L	exchange	交換
	⟨brjed⟩	te i ^L	forget	忘記
⟨lj-⟩	⟨lji.ba⟩	t uo ^L	flea	跳蚤
	⟨ljid⟩	te i ^N mə ^H	heavy	重
⟨gd-⟩	⟨kha.gdangs⟩	k ^h e ^H ta ^N	open	張 (~嘴)
	⟨mye.gdav⟩	ŋ e ^N ty ^H	live chrcoal	火炭
⟨bd-⟩	⟨bdun⟩	ti ^L	seven	七
	⟨bde.mo⟩	te ^N mə ^H	safety	平安
⟨rd-⟩	⟨rdo⟩	t ō ^L	rock	石頭
	⟨rdung⟩	ty ^L	knock	敲
⟨ld-⟩	⟨lde.myig⟩	te ^N ŋi ^H	key	鑰匙
	⟨ldag⟩	t ǎ ^L	lick	舔
⟨sd-⟩	⟨sdong⟩	t ū ^L	root	根
	⟨sdar.ga⟩	te ^H kə ^H	walnut	核桃
⟨rdz-⟩	⟨myig.rdzi⟩	ŋ i ^H tsə ^H	eyebrow	眉毛
	⟨kha.rdzun⟩	k ^h e ^H tsε ^N	feak	假

Developments of fricatives with a preinitial. In Gyersgang, preinitials inhibit both devoicing and the chain shift of aspiration in fricatives. As a result, clusters like ⟨Cs-, Cz-, Csh-, Czh-⟩ retain their unaspirated forms /s-, z-, χ-, ʎ-/ and do not undergo aspiration (Table 3.15 and Table 3.16).

Table 3.15 Inherited developments of ⟨C + voiceless fricatives⟩

⟨gs-⟩	⟨gsum⟩	sy: ^H	three	三
	⟨lo.gsar⟩	lo ^N sa: ^H	New Year	新年
⟨bs-⟩	⟨bsil⟩	si: ^H	cold	冷
	⟨bsad⟩	se: ^H	oufire	滅 (火~)
⟨gz-⟩	⟨gzi⟩	zǎ ^L	dzi beads	天珠
	⟨gzig⟩	zi ^H	leopard	豹子
⟨bz-⟩	⟨lham.bzo⟩	χa ^L zo ^L	cobbler	鞋匠

Table 3.16 Inherited developments of ⟨C + voiced fricatives⟩

⟨gsh-⟩	⟨gshog.rtsa⟩	χo ^N tca ^H	wing	翅膀
⟨bsh-⟩	⟨bshu⟩	χə: ^H	peel	剝 (~花生)
	⟨bshal⟩	χiɛ: ^H	flush	沖 (用水~)
⟨gzh-⟩	⟨gzhu⟩	ʎǎ ^L	bow, arc	弓
	⟨gzhes.nyin⟩	ʎi ^N ŋi ^H	three days from now	大後天
⟨bzh-⟩	⟨bzhi⟩	ʎǎ ^L	four	四
	⟨bzhag⟩	ʎa ^L	to place	放 (~置)

Developments of nasals with a preinitial. In the development of the inherited stratum, nasal consonants remain stable in their phonetic realization. While preinitials undergo deletion, the phonetic value of the nasals remains unchanged, as seen in Table 3.17.

Table 3.17 Inherited developments of ⟨C + nasals⟩

⟨mng-⟩	⟨ mng ar⟩	ŋɛ ^H mə ^H	sweet	甜
	⟨ mng ag⟩	ŋa ^H	dispatch	派 (~人)
⟨rng-⟩	⟨ rng a⟩	ŋo ^H	gong	鑼
	⟨ rng a.ma⟩	ŋo ^H mo ^H	tail	尾巴
⟨lng-⟩	⟨ lng a⟩	ŋo ^H	five	五
⟨sng-⟩	⟨ sng a.so⟩	ŋɛ ^H so ^H	front	前 (~邊)
	⟨kha. sng o⟩	k ^h o ^N ŋo ^H	face	臉
⟨gny-⟩	⟨ gny is⟩	ŋi ^H	two	二
	⟨ gny om.chung⟩	ŋo ^N tey ^H	polite	客氣
⟨rny-⟩	⟨ rny ing.pa⟩	ŋi ^H a ^H	old, auld	舊
⟨sny-⟩	⟨ sny ing.rje⟩	ŋyɛ ^H te ^h i ^N	pitiful	可憐
⟨gn-⟩	⟨ gn am⟩	na ^H	rain	雨
	⟨sha. gn ad⟩	χ ^h e ^N na ^H	muscle	肌肉
⟨mn-⟩	⟨ mn av.ma⟩	no ^H mo ^H	wife	妻子
⟨rn-⟩	⟨ rn a.lo⟩	na ^N lo ^H	leaf	葉子
	⟨ rn ag⟩	na ^H	pus	膿
⟨sn-⟩	⟨ sn ab⟩	na ^H	snot	鼻涕
	⟨mi. sn ang⟩	mə ^N na ^H	no, without	沒有
⟨dm-⟩	⟨ dm ag⟩	ma ^H	soldier	士兵
⟨rm-⟩	⟨ rm a⟩	muo ^H	wound	傷口, 疤
	⟨ rm o⟩	mo ^H	plough	耕
⟨sm-⟩	⟨ sm an⟩	mɛ ^H	medicine	藥

Developments of ⟨g·y-, lh-⟩. The cluster ⟨g·y-⟩ has developed into /j-/. The cluster ⟨lh-⟩ has become /l-/ (Table 3.18).

Table 3.18 Inherited developments of ⟨g·y-, lh-⟩

⟨g·y-⟩	⟨ g·y ag⟩	ja ^H	yak	犛牛
	⟨ g·y er.ma⟩	je ^H mo ^H	wild pepper	花椒
⟨lh-⟩>l	⟨ lh a⟩	lɛ ^L	buddha	神仙, 佛
	⟨ lh a.sa⟩	la ^N s ^h a ^H	lhasa	拉薩

3.1.3 Inherited developments of ⟨CM^l-, CCM-⟩

The cluster ⟨CM-⟩ indicates CT consonants with medials, and the cluster ⟨CCM-⟩ indicates CT consonants with preinitials and medials.

In the inherited development, ⟨(C)Cy-, (C)Cr-⟩ have merged into alveolar consonants, representing a significant shared innovation among Tibetan dialects spoken within Thebo County.

¹ The letter ⟨M⟩ represents medial in CT.

Table 3.19 Inherited developments of CT consonants with medials

y		r		l		w	
<ky->	-	<kr->	-	<kl->	-	<kw->	-
<khy->	ts^h	<khr->	ts^h			<khw->	-
<gy->	-	<gr->	ts	<gl->	l	<gw->	-
						<cw->	-
						<nyw->	ŋ
		<tr->	-			<tw->	-
		<thr->	-				
		<dr->	-			<dw->	t
<py->	-	<pr->	-			<tsw->	-
<phy->	-	<phr->	-			<tshw->	ts^h
<by->	-	<br->	-	<bl->	l		
<my->	ŋ	<mr->	-				
		<sr->	-	<sl->	l,s	<sw->	-
				<zl->	l	<zw->	s
		<shr->	-			<shw->	χ^h
		<hr->	-			<zhw->	χ
						<hw->	
						<lw->	j
		<grw->	-	<rl->	l	<rw->	r

Similar to the developments of <CC->, in <CCM->, only prenasals can prevent devoicing, while non-nasal preinitials fail to prevent this process (Table 3.20).

Table 3.20 Inherited developments of CT consonants with preinitials and medials

<bky->	ts	<bkr->	-				
<dky->	ts	<dkr->	-	<dpy->	-	<dpr->	-
<sky->	ts	<skr->	-	<spy->	-	<spr->	-
<bsky->	-	<bskr->	-				
<rky->	ts			<rtsw->	ts		
<brky->	-						
<mkhy->	-	<mkhr->	-				
<vkhy->	ts^h	<vkhr->	ts^h	<vphy->		<vphr->	ts^h
<bgy->	-	<bgr->	-				
<dgy->	-	<dgr->	-	<dby->	-	<dbr->	-
<sgy->	ts	<mgr->	ts	<sby->	-	<sbr->	-
<bsgy->	-	<bsgr->	-				
<rgy->	ts						
<brgy->	ts						
<mgy->	-	<mgr->	-				
<vgy->	-	<vgr->	dz	<vby->	dz	<vbr->	dz
<dmy->	-	<rmy->	-	<bkl->	-	<bgl->	-
<smgy->	ŋ	<smr->	-	<bsl->	-	<bzl->	l
				<brl->	l	<bsr->	-

In the inherited stratum of CT's <(C)Cy-, (C)Cr-> clusters, unaspirated obstruents with non-nasal preinitials develop into /ts-/, voiceless aspirated obstruents becomes /ts^h-/, and voiced obstruents with nasal preinitials become /dz-/, while all <(C)my-> clusters uniformly shift to /ŋ-/ (Table 3.21).

Table 3.21 Inherited developments of <(C)Cy-, (C)Cr->

>ts	<gro>	ts ^o L	wheat	小麥
	<rkyong>	tsu ^L	reach out	伸 (~手)
	<phag.skyag>	p ^h a ^N tsa ^H	pig manure	豬糞
	<dkiil>	tsi: ^H mo: ^H	middle	中間
	<rgyag>	tsa ^L	shoot (arrow)	射 (~箭)
	<brgyad>	tsiɛ ^L	eight	八
>ts ^h	<sgra>	tsɛ ^L	loud	響
	<khyi>	ts ^h ə ^H	dog	狗
	<vkhyag>	χɛ ^N ke: ^H ts ^h a ^H	cold	冷
	<khrag>	ts ^h a ^H	blood	血
>dz	<vkhrid>	ts ^h i ^H	lead	帶 (~路)
	<mgyogs>	dzu ^N be: ^H	fast	快
	<vbyar>	dze: ^L	paste	貼
	<yar.vgyog>	ja ^L dzu ^L	sustain	撐住
	<vgro>	dzo ^L	go	走
>ŋ	<mying>	ŋi: ^L	first name	名
	<smiyug.ma>	ŋi: ^H mo: ^H	bamboo	竹子

Regarding the remaining two medials, <-l-, -w->: all <(C)Cl-> becomes /l-/ (Table 3.22); Similarly to other Tibetic languages, the medial <-w-> in <(C)Cw-> does not affect the development of the main consonant and follows the same development as consonants without medials.

Table 3.22 Inherited development of <(C)Cl->

>l	<glu>	l ^o H	song	歌
	<bla>	lɛ ^H	soul	魂, 命根
	<sla>	lɛ: ^H	easy	容易
	<zla.ba>	la: ^H	month	月
	<rlangs.pa>	la ^N be: ^H	steam	蒸汽
	<bzos>	lo ^H	tell	告訴
	<brla.rkang>	lɛ: ^H kuo: ^H	thigh	大腿

3.2 Non-inherited developments of initials

3.2.1 Non-inherited developments of CT simple initials

Spirantization. In Gyersgang, some CT's obstruents undergo spirantization in the intervocalic position, such as <a.ce> /v:^Hze:^H/ “aunt 姑母”, <a.khu> /a:^Hyə^H/ “elder uncle 伯父”, <rwa.rtse> /rɛ^Nze:^H/ “corner, horn 犄角”, <c->, <kh-> and <rts-> has become /z/, /y/ and /z/ respectively.

Interchange between ⟨sh-⟩ and ⟨zh-⟩. The inherited development of ⟨sh-⟩ and ⟨zh-⟩ in Gyersgang is /χ^h-/ and /χ-/ respectively. However, in certain words, ⟨sh-⟩ developed into /χ-/ and ⟨zh-⟩ into /χ^h-/, as seen in examples like ⟨shing⟩ /χi^Nto:^H/ “wood 木頭”, ⟨zha⟩ /χ^hə^Nwu:^H/ “lameter 跛子”.

Interchange between ⟨r-⟩ and ⟨l-⟩. In Gyersgang, there are some cases of sporadic interchange between ⟨r-⟩ and ⟨l-⟩, as seen in examples like ⟨sha.rigs⟩ /χ^ha^Nlɛ:^H/ “beast 野獸”, where ⟨r-⟩ has become /l/, however, in the example ⟨nang.la⟩ /nɑ^Lrə^N/ “inside 裏 (~邊)”, ⟨l-⟩ has become /n/.

3.2.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨(C)CC-⟩

Initials' voicing. Yang et al. (2024) shows systematic consonant voicing in Gyiba, which they cite as evidence for Coblin's Law. This phonological development is similarly attested in Gyersgang. Examples include ⟨(skon)⟩ /gɛ:^H/ “hang 吊”, ⟨rka/rkas⟩ /gɛ^Nna:^H/ “old 老”, ⟨vthen)⟩ /de^L/ “sing 唱”, ⟨jon.tan)⟩ /jo^Ndɛ:^H/ “knowledge 學問”, ⟨rlangs.pa)⟩ /la^Nbɛ:^H/ “steam 蒸汽”, ⟨dung.dkar)⟩ /ty^Nga:^H/ “conch 海螺” etc.. The consonants that have undergone this voicing shift are listed in the table below.

Table 3.23 Initials' voicing

⟨dk-⟩	g	⟨gt-⟩	-	⟨gts-⟩	-
⟨bk-⟩	g	⟨bt-⟩	-	⟨bts-⟩	-
⟨rk-⟩	g	⟨rt-⟩	d	⟨rts-⟩	-
⟨sk-⟩	g	⟨st-⟩	-	⟨sts-⟩	-
⟨mkh-⟩	-	⟨mth-⟩	-	⟨mtsh-⟩	dz

Interchange between ⟨(C)ng-⟩ and ⟨(C)ny-⟩. As mentioned, nasal initials are generally stable and remain unchanged in most Tibetan dialects. However, the development of nasals with preinitials in Gyersgang is notably distinctive: ⟨dng-, rng-⟩ have evolved into /ŋ_ɿ-/, while ⟨gny-, mny-⟩ have developed into /ŋ-/. This interchange between /ŋ_ɿ-/ and /ŋ-/ in Gyersgang thus represents a particularly unique phenomenon. A significant portion of words with ⟨dng-, rng-⟩ in Gyersgang has developed into /ŋ_ɿ-/, while ⟨gny-, mny-⟩ have changed into /ŋ-/ in a considerable number of instances. Notably, these examples of interchange between ⟨Cng-⟩ and ⟨Cny-⟩ were predominantly nouns; conversely, in regular development, where ⟨Cng-⟩ remains as /ŋ-/ and ⟨Cny-⟩ as /ŋ_ɿ-/, are observed in approximately half of the verbs. Since verbs are more difficult to borrow than nouns, this interchange phenomenon is likely not in the inherited stratum.

Table 3.24 Interchange between ⟨(C)ng-⟩ and ⟨(C)ny-⟩

>ŋ	⟨nyan)⟩	ŋe^L	listen	聽
	⟨mnyed)⟩	ŋe:^H	tan	鞣 (~皮子)
	⟨brnyas.?.bjed)⟩	ŋie^Nŋo:^Htɕi^H	bully	欺負
>ŋ	⟨nya.ngog)⟩	ŋa^Nŋə^H	child	小孩兒
	⟨dngul)⟩	ŋi^H	silver	銀子
	⟨rngul.nag)⟩	ŋi:^Hna^H	perspiration	汗
	⟨rnga.mong)⟩	ŋe:^Hmo:^H	camel	駱駝

Failure of prenasals to prevent devoicing. While prenasals in CT would be expected

to prevent devoicing of main stops/affricates in inherited developments, Gyersgang's non-inherited stratum shows failure of this preventing effect (Table 3.25). as seen in examples ⟨vgor⟩ /kɛ^Nle:^H/ "slow 慢", ⟨bya.vdab⟩ /εɛ^Ntə:^H/ "eaves 房檐", ⟨vdzom⟩ /tsu^L/ "call together 聚齊", where prenasals do not preserve voicing.

Table 3.25 Failure of prenasals to prevent devoicing

⟨mg-⟩	k	⟨md-⟩	t	⟨mdz-⟩	ts
⟨vg-⟩	k	⟨vd-⟩	t	⟨vdz-⟩	-

Non-nasal preinitials prevented devoicing. In Gyersgang, non-nasal preinitials do not prevent the devoicing of voiced consonants. However, in this stratum, some non-nasal preinitials do prevent the devoicing of main stops and affricates (Table 3.26), such as ⟨sga⟩ /gɛ^L/ "saddle 馬鞍", ⟨brje⟩ /dze^L/ "change 換, 改變", ⟨lde⟩ /de^L/ "sunbathe 曬 (~太陽)", where ⟨sg-⟩ has become /g-/ , ⟨brj-⟩ has become /dz-/ , and ⟨lde⟩ has become /d-/ .

Table 3.26 Non-nasal preinitials prevented devoicing

⟨rg-⟩	-	⟨rj-⟩	dz	⟨rd-⟩	d
⟨lg-⟩	-	⟨lj-⟩	-	⟨ld-⟩	d
⟨sg-⟩	g				

Interchange between aspirated and unaspirated stops. In Gyersgang, some aspirated stop main consonants undergo deaspiration, as seen in ⟨vthen⟩ /te^L/ "weigh 稱 (~糧食)", where ⟨vth-⟩ has developed into /t-/ . Also, some unaspirated stop main consonants developed into aspirated ones, for example, ⟨gtong⟩ /t^hu^L/ "pee 撒 (~尿)", ⟨btsag⟩ /ts^ha^H/ "squeeze 榨 (~油)", where ⟨gt-⟩ has become /t^h-/ , ⟨bts-⟩ has become /ts^h-/ .

In both Ridang and Gyersgang, the word ⟨lham⟩ /χa:^L/ "shoes 鞋" exhibits the same exceptional pattern. In Ridang, ⟨lh-⟩ has also shifted to /l-/ at the inherited stratum. However, in the non-inherited stratum of both languages, ⟨lh-⟩ remains an exception: in Gyersgang, it has evolved into /χ-/ , while in Ridang, it has become /χa:^L/ .

3.2.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨CM-, CCM-⟩

The ⟨(C)CM-⟩ cluster plays a significant role in stratification. In Gyersgang, at least three distinct strata can be identified within these clusters, demonstrating their diachronic layering: (i) ⟨(C)Cy-, (C)Cr-⟩ shifting to alveolar (inherited development); (ii) alveolo-palatalization; and (iii) fricativization. Examples of the latter two strata are presented in this subsection.

Table 3.27 Alveolo-palatal developments of ⟨(C)CM-⟩

⟨sr-⟩	ɛ			⟨phy-⟩	ɛ^h		
				⟨by-⟩	ɛ		
⟨bky-⟩	-	⟨bkr-⟩	te				
⟨sky-⟩	te	⟨skr-⟩	-	⟨spy-⟩	ɛ	⟨spr-⟩	ɛ
⟨vkhy-⟩	te^h	⟨vkhr-⟩	-	⟨vphy-⟩	ɛ^h	⟨vphr-⟩	-
⟨rgy-⟩	te						
⟨mgy-⟩	-	⟨mgr-⟩	dz				
⟨vgy-⟩	-	⟨vgr-⟩	dz	⟨vby-⟩	-	⟨vbr-⟩	dz

Alveolo-palatal developments of ⟨CM-, CCM-⟩. Within this stratum, CT's ⟨(C)Cy-, (C)Cr-⟩ clusters change to alveolo-palatal. Specifically, unaspirated obstruent main consonant with non-nasal preinitials becomes /tɕ-/; voiceless aspirated obstruent main consonant becomes /tɕʰ-/; voiced obstruent main consonant with prenasals becomes /dz-/ (Table 3.28).

Table 3.28 Examples of alveolo-palatal developments of ⟨(C)CM-⟩

>tɕ	⟨gyo⟩	tɕo: ^H ba ^H	brick	磚
	⟨rgyal⟩	tɕa: ^L	win	贏
	⟨skyid.po⟩	tɕə: ^H po: ^H	happy	幸福
	⟨drug⟩	tɕỹ ^L	six	六
	⟨bkra.shis⟩	tɕə: ^N ei: ^H	propitious	吉祥
>tɕʰ	⟨khyod⟩	tɕʰu ^H	you	你
	⟨vkhyags.rom⟩	tɕʰu ^N ru: ^H	ice	冰
	⟨khri⟩	tɕʰə: ^H	ten thousand	萬
	⟨phrug⟩	tɕʰy ^H	Tibet wool	氍毹
	⟨vphrog⟩	tɕʰu ^H	rob, grab	搶
>dz	⟨mgron.pa⟩	dzɔ: ^H bo: ^H	guest	客人
	⟨vgrang⟩	dzɑ: ^L	be full	飽
	⟨vbrug⟩	dz̃ ^L	thunder	雷
	⟨vdrub⟩	dz̃ ^L	seam	縫

Additionally, most of the ⟨bilabial+medial⟩ clusters become fricatives, while ⟨vphr-⟩ has become affricate, /tɕʰ/, as shown in Table 3.28. ⟨sr-⟩ also developed into an alveolo-palatal fricative /-ɕ/ (Table 3.29).

Table 3.29 Examples of alveolo-palatal developments of ⟨bilabial+medial⟩

>ɕ	⟨bya⟩	ɕe ^H	chicken	雞
	⟨spyang.ku⟩	ɕo: ^H gə: ^H	wolf	狼
	⟨sprin⟩	ɕi: ^H	cloud	雲
	⟨srung⟩	ɕu: ^H	protect	保護
>ɕʰ	⟨phye⟩	ɕʰe ^H	flour	麵粉
	⟨vphyen⟩	ɕʰi ^L	fart	屁

Table 3.30 Fricativized developments of ⟨CM-, CCM-⟩

⟨bky-⟩	ɕ	⟨bkr-⟩	-
⟨dky-⟩	-	⟨dkr-⟩	ɕ
⟨sky-⟩	ɕ	⟨skr-⟩	ɕ
⟨dby-⟩	j	⟨sbr-⟩	r

Fricativized developments of ⟨CM-, CCM-⟩. In this stratum, CT's ⟨(C)CM-⟩ clusters change to voiceless fricatives when voiceless consonants are main consonants. When a voiced consonant is the main consonant, the medial becomes the main consonant, while the preinitial and main consonants in CT disappear, as in the examples "summer 夏" and "snake 蛇", the medial has become the main consonant (Table 3.31). This phenomenon has also been seen in

Ridang (Yeung 2024) and some western Tibetic languages (Tournadre & Suzuki 2023).

Table 3.31 Examples of fricativized developments of ⟨CM-, CCM-⟩

>ɕ	⟨ skya .ga) ɕv ^H kɕ ^H	magpie	喜鵲
	⟨ bky ag.to) ɕa ^N ty ^H	stool (to sit)	凳子
	⟨ skra) ɕv ^H	hair	頭髮
	⟨mdzub. dkris) dzu ^N ɕi ^H	ring	戒指
>j	⟨ dbyar .ngo) ja ^H ŋo ^H	summer	夏
>r	⟨ sbrul) ri ^H	snake	蛇

Interchange between aspirated and unaspirated stops. In the ⟨(C)CM-⟩ cluster, some aspirated stops developed into unaspirated ones, for example, ⟨lag.vphyid⟩ /lo^Nɕi^H/ "handkerchief 手帕", ⟨mkhris.pa⟩ /tsi^Npɕ^H/ "gallbladder 膽". Also, some unaspirated stops developed into aspirated ones, such as ⟨srog⟩ /ɕhu^H/ "life 生命". CT clusters undergoing this sound change pattern are listed in Table 3.32.

Table 3.32 Interchange between aspirated and naspirated stops

⟨phy-⟩	ɕ	⟨phr-⟩	ɕ ^h
		⟨sr-⟩	ɕ ^h
⟨bky-⟩		⟨bkr-⟩	ts ^h
⟨mkhy-⟩	-	⟨mkhr-⟩	ts
⟨vkhy-⟩		⟨vkhr-⟩	
⟨vphy-⟩	ɕ		

Interchange between voiced and voiceless stops. In Gyersgang, prenasals in CT prevent the main stops and affricates from devoicing, while non-nasal preinitials do not prevent the devoicing of voiced consonants. However, in some exceptions, the situation seems reversed: prenasals fail to prevent the devoicing of the main consonants, as exemplified by ⟨nang.la.vgro⟩ /na^Ltso^L/ "into 進 (~屋)" (⟨vgr-⟩>/ts-/), while some non-nasal preinitials do prevent the devoicing of main stops and affricates, such as ⟨rgya⟩ /dze^L/ "Han nationality 漢族" (⟨rgy-⟩>/dz-/), ⟨rgya.mtsho⟩ /dze^Ntsho^H/ "sea 海" (⟨rgy-⟩>/dz-/).

The initial ⟨gy-⟩ is expected to be devoiced and become /ts-/; however, in the word ⟨chu.gyang⟩ /tɕ^hə^Ndza^L/ "dam 堤", the second syllable is still voiced, even in its citation form.

Table 3.33 Interchange between voiced and voiceless stops

⟨gy-⟩	dz	⟨gr-⟩	ts
⟨dgy-⟩	-	⟨dgr-⟩	dz
⟨rgy-⟩	dz, dz	⟨vgr-⟩	ts, tɕ

The development of consonants in Gyersgang highlights its unique characteristics, particularly the mutual changes between the clusters ⟨(C)ng-⟩ and ⟨(C)ny-⟩, which illustrate the historical contacts it has experienced. In this section, we separate the inherited stratum of Gyersgang and at least two non-inherited strata. These two levels may come from the historical contact between Gyersgang and Ridang, and the contact between Gyersgang and Ridang as Lower Thebo and Cone.

Additionally, consonants reveal the rate of evolution within Gyersgang. In the <<(C)CM-> cluster, the prenasal /n/ is preserved in Gyiba, and all preinitial consonants prevent the main consonant from devoicing. In Ridang, all preinitials can also prevent this devoicing, but in Gyersgang, only the prenasal can do so. This comparison indicates that Gyersgang is evolving at a faster rate. This language offers us the opportunity to observe recent changes in directionality and trends within Tibetic languages, and we may also witness some ongoing sound changes.

4. Developments of rhymes

Table 4.1 presents the inherent development of rhymes from CT to Gyersgang. It illustrates the evolution of five CT vowels and nine CT codas,² along with open syllables in CT. The loss of certain codas has led to vowel length distinctions and the emergence of new monophthongs, such as /y/, alongside diphthongs.

Rhyme length. The loss of nasal codas, as well as <-l, -r>, resulted in long vowels, while open syllables and the loss of <-ug(s), -eg(s)> led to extra-short vowels.

New monophthongs. The merger of <i, u> gave rise to the new vowel /ǎ/, a common development in Tibetic dialects, also observed in the neighboring Gyiba dialect. Additionally, <u> shifted to /y/ before certain codas. The vowel <a>, depending on the syllabic context, evolved into /a/, /ǎ/, or /ɑ/, while its loss after alveolar codas resulted in /i)ɛ/.

Fronting and raising before alveolar codas. The alveolar codas can cause the main vowel’s fronting and raising change. This change is widely seen across Tibetic languages, e.g., in the central, eastern, and northern sections, <-a+alveolar> has fronted and raised to /ɛ/ or /e/; <-u+alveolar> has fronted to /y/ in those sections (Jiang 2002). This change is also seen in Thebo’s dialects, e.g., Gyiba (Yang et al. 2024) and Ridang (Yeung 2024). Though the exact value of the changed vowel is not the same, the tendency of fronting and raising are identical. Since the fronting and raising change in Gyersgang, <-i+alveolar>, and <-u+alveolar> have merged to /i/ sound, <-e+alveolar>, and <-o+alveolar> have merged to /e/ sound.

The chain shift. A Chain shift can be seen in the development of rhymes. CT’s <-o(C)> has become /u/ sound in the majority of cases, and CT’s <-u(C)> has fronted to /y/ sound in the majority of cases.

Table 4.1 Inherent developments of rhymes

	<∅>	<-b(s)>	<-m(s)>	<-g(s)>	<-ng(s)>	<-n>	<-d>	<-s>	<-l>	<-r>
<i>	ǎ	i	i:	ǐ	i:	i:	i	i:	i:	i:
<u>	ǎ	y	y:	ǎ	y:	i:	i	i:	i:	y:
<e>	ě	i	i:	ǎ	i:	e:	e	e:	e:	e:
<o>	ǒ	u	u:	u	u:	e:	e	e:	i:	u:
<a>	ǎ	ɑ	ɑ:	a	ɑ:	ɛ:	ɛ	ɛ:	iɛ	a:

4.1 Developments of <-i(C)>

The development of <-i> is shown in Table 4.2, with the first line being inherited development. "S1" represents the first non-inherited stratum, while "irregular" refers to scattered exceptions.

² The CT coda <-v> generally does not influence sound changes in Tibetic languages, and the same holds true for Gyersgang. As a result, it is not included in the table, as its development follows the same pattern as CT open syllables.

Table 4.2 Developments of ⟨-i(C)⟩

	⟨-i⟩	⟨-ib(s)⟩	⟨-id⟩	⟨-ig(s)⟩	⟨-im⟩	⟨-in⟩	⟨-ing⟩	⟨-is⟩	⟨-il⟩	⟨-ir⟩
Inherited	ǎ	i	i	i	i:	i:	i:	i:	i:	i:
S1	i				e		e			
Irregular		y,e								

4.1.1 Inherited developments of ⟨-i(C)⟩

Inherited development of ⟨-i⟩. The rhyme ⟨-i⟩ in CT changed to /-ǎ/ in Gyersgang (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3 Inherited development of ⟨-i⟩

>ə	⟨gzi⟩	zǎ ^L	dzi beads	天珠
	⟨myi⟩	ŋǎ ^L	People	人
	⟨ri⟩	rǎ ^L	mountain	山
	⟨khyi⟩	ts ^h ǎ ^H [ts ^h ǎ ^H]	dog	狗

Inherited development of ⟨-ib(s), -id, -ig(s)⟩. The loss of the codas ⟨-ib(s), -id, -ig(s)⟩ results in the formation of short rhymes (Table 4.4).

Table 4.4 Inherited development of ⟨-ib(s), -id, -ig(s)⟩

⟨-ib⟩	⟨grib.ma⟩	tsi ^N mo ^H	shadow	影子
⟨-id⟩	⟨vkhrid⟩	ts ^h i ^H	lead	帶 (~路)
	⟨gnyid⟩	ŋi ^H	asleep	睡著
⟨-ig(s)⟩	⟨myig⟩	ŋi ^H	eye	眼睛
	⟨gzig⟩	zi ^L	leopard	豹子
	⟨skyes.rigs⟩	ei ^H ri ^H	man	男人

Inherited development of ⟨-iN,³ -is, -il, -ir⟩. The vowel ⟨-i⟩ with a nasal coda, together with ⟨-is, -il, -ir⟩ have all developed into /-i/, and the loss of the codas results in the formation of long rhymes (Table 4.5).

Table 4.5 Inherited development of ⟨-im, -in, -ing, -is, -il, -ir⟩

⟨-im⟩	⟨zhim.ʔ⟩	xi ^N bo ^H	appetizing	香 (味道~)
⟨-in⟩	⟨sprin⟩	ei ^H	cloud	雲
	⟨knangs.nyin⟩	na ^H ŋi ^H	the day after tomorrow	後天
⟨-ing⟩	⟨sring.mo⟩	ei ^H mə ^H	sister (male call)	姐妹 (男性稱呼)
	⟨mying⟩	ŋi ^L	name	名字
⟨-is⟩	⟨gnyis⟩	ŋi ^H	two	二
	⟨mkhris.pa⟩	tsi ^N pe ^H	gallbladder	膽
⟨-il⟩	⟨tshil⟩	ts ^h i ^L	fatty oil	脂肪
	⟨bsil⟩	si ^H	cold	冷
⟨-ir⟩	⟨btsir⟩	tsi ^H	squeeze	擠 (~牙膏)
	⟨lbu.ba.phyir⟩	wa ^L ei ^H	talk	聊天

³ In this study, the letter ⟨-N⟩ within angle brackets denotes nasal phonemes.

4.1.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-i(C)⟩

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-i⟩. There are a few instances where ⟨-i⟩ remains as /-i/ (Table 4.6).

Table 4.6 Non-inherited development of ⟨-i⟩

>i	⟨rmi.lam⟩	ŋi ^H la ^H	dream	夢
	⟨myi.skya⟩	ŋi ^N ɕe ^H	secular person	俗人
	⟨dri⟩	ɕ ^H i ^L	fart	屁

Based on the development of CT consonants with medials, we can infer that in Gyersgang, CT's ⟨(C)Cy-, (C)Cr-⟩ developed into alveolar sounds within the inherited stratum, while at a non-inherited stratum, they change to alveolo-palatal sounds. The initials of ⟨mi.skya⟩ "secular person" and ⟨dri⟩ "fart" have both developed into alveolo-palatal sounds, possibly influenced by neighboring Tibetan dialects. Therefore, the development of ⟨-i⟩ into /-i/ in Gyersgang is of external origin. For instance, in Ridang, ⟨-i⟩ developed into /-i/ when combined with initials ⟨bilabial + y⟩. Linguistic evidence suggests Ridang as a probable origin for this stratum in Gyersgang.

Non-inherited development of ⟨-im, -ing⟩. In the non-inherited stratum, ⟨-im, -ing⟩ have developed into /-e/ (Table 4.7).

Table 4.7 Non-inherited development of ⟨-im, -ing⟩

>e	⟨gzim⟩	se ^H	close	關 (~電視)
	⟨gling.bu⟩	le ^H	flute	笛子

4.2 Developments of ⟨-u(C)⟩

The rhyme ⟨-u(C)⟩ undergoes fronting, where the back vowel shifts to a front vowel after the coda is lost. Before an alveolar coda, it becomes the unrounded front vowel /i(:)/, whereas before other codas, it shifts to the rounded front vowel /y/, as shown in Table 4.8.

Table 4.8 Developments of ⟨-u(C)⟩

	⟨-u⟩	⟨-ub(s)⟩	⟨-um(s)⟩	⟨-ug(s)⟩	⟨-ung⟩	⟨-un⟩	⟨-ud⟩	⟨-us⟩	⟨-ul⟩	⟨-ur⟩
Inherited	ǔ	y	y:	ǚ	y:	i:	i	i:	i:	y:
S1		u		u	u		u			u
S2				i			y	y	y	i
Irregular	o	e								e

4.2.1 Inherited developments of ⟨-u(C)⟩

Inherited development of ⟨-u⟩. In Gyersgang, CT's ⟨-u, -i⟩ are merged to /-ǔ/, as shown in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9 Inherited development of ⟨-u⟩

>ə	⟨bu⟩	p ^ə H	son	兒子
	⟨chu⟩	tɕ ^h ɿ ^H	water	水
	⟨vbu⟩	b ^ə L	worm	蟲
	⟨bru⟩	dz ^ə L	grain	糧食

Inherited development of ⟨-ub(s), -ug(s)⟩. In Gyersgang, the rhyme ⟨-ub(s)⟩ has become a short rhyme /-y/, and ⟨-ug(s)⟩ has developed into an extra-short rhyme /-ỹ/ (Table 4.10).

Table 4.10 Inherited development of ⟨-ub, -ug(s)⟩

⟨-ub(s)⟩	⟨shubs⟩	ɕy ^H	scabbard	刀鞘
	⟨mun.rub⟩	mi ^L ry ^L	get dark	天黑
⟨-ug(s)⟩	⟨vphrugs⟩	tɕ ^h ỹ ^H	tickle	撓 (~癢)
	⟨rgyug⟩	dz̃ỹ ^L	run	跑

Inherited development of ⟨-um(s), -ung, -ur⟩. The rhymes ⟨-um(s), -ung, -ur⟩ have become a long rhyme /-y/ in Gyersgang, and the loss of the nasal codas ⟨-m, -ng⟩ and coda ⟨-r⟩ results in the formation of long rhymes (Table 4.11).

Table 4.11 Inherited development of ⟨-um(s), -ung, -ur⟩

⟨-um(s)⟩	⟨gsum⟩	sy ^H	three	三
	⟨btsums⟩	tsy ^H	close	閉 (~口)
⟨-ung⟩	⟨vthung⟩	t ^h y ^L	drink	喝
	⟨tho.chung⟩	t ^h o ^N tɕy ^H	small hammer	小錘子
⟨-ur⟩	⟨vphur⟩	p ^h y ^L	fly	飛
	⟨skad.skur⟩	kɛ ^N ky ^H	information	資訊

Inherited development of ⟨-ud, -un, -us, -ul⟩. The vowel ⟨-u-⟩ with alveolar codas ⟨-d, -n, -s, -l⟩ has undergone vowel fronting. The stop coda ⟨-d⟩ forms a short rhyme /-i/, ⟨-un, -us, -ul⟩ have all developed into long rhymes /i:/, as shown in Table 4.12.

Table 4.12 Inherited development of ⟨-ud, -un, -us, -ul⟩

⟨-ud⟩	⟨mthud⟩	t ^h i ^H	connect	連接
	⟨phud⟩	p ^h i ^L	push	推
	⟨vkhrud⟩	ts ^h i ^H	wash	洗 (~衣)
⟨-un⟩	⟨bdun⟩	ti ^L	seven	七
	⟨dgun.ngo⟩	ki ^N ŋo ^H	winter	冬
	⟨mun.rub⟩	mi ^L ry ^L	get dark	天黑
⟨-us⟩	⟨dus.tshod⟩	ti ^N ts ^h ɛ ^H	time	時間
	⟨brgjus⟩	tsi ^L	thread	穿 (~針)
⟨-ul⟩	⟨dngul⟩	ŋi ^H	silver	銀子
	⟨sbrul⟩	ri ^H	snake	蛇
	⟨pha.jul⟩	p ^h a ^N ji ^N	hometown	家鄉

4.2.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-u(C)⟩

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ub(s), -ug(s)⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ub(s), -ug(s)⟩ have lost their codas, and the vowel remains as /-u/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ug(s)⟩ has developed into /-i/ (Table 4.13).

Table 4.13 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ub(s), -ug(s)⟩

>u	⟨mdz ub .dkris⟩	dz u ^N ei: ^H	ring	戒指
	⟨bts ugs ⟩	ts u ^L	insert	插 (~牌子)
>i	⟨smy ug .ma⟩	ŋ i: ^H mo: ^H	bamboo	竹子

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ung, -ur⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ung, -ur⟩ undergo coda deletion, with the nasal coda forming a long rhyme /u:/ and ⟨-ur⟩ becoming a short /u/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ur⟩ has developed into /-i/ (Table 4.14).

Table 4.14 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ung, -ur⟩

>u	⟨mth ur .rta⟩	du ^N ta ^H	headstall	馬籠頭
	⟨s rung ⟩	ɛ u: ^H	protect	保護
>i	⟨s dur ⟩	ti ^H	compare	比

Non-inherited development of ⟨-ud, -us, -ul⟩. In the second non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ud⟩ has become a short rhyme /-y/; ⟨-us, -ul⟩ have developed into a long rhyme /-y:/ (Table 4.15).

Table 4.15 Non-inherited development of ⟨-ud, -us, -ul⟩

>y	⟨ph ud .gos⟩	p^hy ^N kɛ: ^H	quilt	被子
	⟨l us ⟩	ly : ^L	leave behind	落 (遺漏)
	⟨dran.tsh ul ⟩	tɕɕ ^N ts ^h y: ^H	idea, thought	想法

4.3 Developments of ⟨-e(C)⟩

The phonetic value of ⟨-e(C)⟩ remains unchanged when it is without a coda or before alveolar codas, shifts to /ǎ/ before ⟨-g⟩, and raises to the high front vowel /i(:)/ before other codas, as shown in Table 4.16.

Table 4.16 Developments of ⟨-e(C)⟩

	⟨-e⟩	⟨-eb(s)⟩	⟨-em(s)⟩	⟨-eg⟩	⟨-eng(s)⟩	⟨-en⟩	⟨-ed⟩	⟨-es⟩	⟨-el⟩	⟨-er⟩
Inherited	ě	i	i:	ǎ	i:	e:	e	e:	e:	e:
S1						i	i	i	i	
S2			e		ɛ	ɛ	ɛ	ɛ		ɛ
Irregular	ə, o									

4.3.1 *Inherited developments of <-e(C)>*

Inherited development of <-e>. In Gyersgang, <-e> has become an extra-short rhyme /-ē/, as shown in Table 4.17.

Table 4.17 Inherited development of <-e>

>e	<ske>	kē ^H	neck	脖子
	<phye>	ɸ ^h ē ^H	flour	麵粉
	<mye>	ŋē ^L	fire	火

Inherited development of <-eg>. In Gyersgang, <-eg> has become an extra-short rhyme /-ǎ/ (Table 4.18).

Table 4.18 Inherited development of <-eg>

<-eg>	<vbreg>	dzǎ ^L	mow	割 (割~)
	<sreg>	ɸǎ ^H	hot	燙 (~手)

Inherited development of <-eb(s), -em(s), -eng(s)>. The rhyme <-eb(s)> has become a short rhyme /-i/; <-em(s), -eng(s)> have developed into a long rhyme /-i:/, as shown in Table 4.19.

Table 4.19 Inherited development of <-eb(s), -em(s), -eng>

<-eb(s)>	<gleb>	li ^H	press	按
	<slebs>	li ^L	arrive	到達
<-em(s)>	<sems>	s ^h i: ^L	heart	心臟
<-eng(s)>	<vkhengs>	k ^h i: ^H	freeze	凍 (肉~)
	<de.reng>	tə: ^H ri: ^H	today	今天

Inherited development of <-ed, -en, -es, -el, -er>. In Gyersgang, <-e> with alveolar codas <-n, -s, -l, -r> all remain a long rhyme /-e:/, <-ed> remain as a short rhyme /-e/ (Table 4.20).

Table 4.20 Inherited development of <-ed, -en, -es, -el, -er>

<-ed>	<vthen>	t ^h e ^H	pull	拉
	<sen.mo>	s ^h e ^L mə ^H	finger nail	指甲
<-en>	<rked.pa>	ke: ^H pə: ^H	waist	腰
	<rtsed.mo.rtse>	tse: ^H mə ^H tse: ^H	play	玩耍
<-es>	<a.myes>	ɸ: ^H ŋe: ^H	grandfather	爺爺
	<ngo.shes>	ŋo ^L ɸe: ^N	recognize	認得
<-el>	<breel>	tse: ^H	flee	逃跑
	<shel>	ɸi: ^H me: ^H	glass	玻璃
<-er>	<gzer>	ze: ^L	nail	釘子
	<ga.ler>	kɸ ^N le: ^H	slow	慢

4.3.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-e(C)⟩

Non-inherited development of ⟨-em(s), -eng(s)⟩. In the second non-inherited stratum, the rhyme ⟨-em(s)⟩ undergo coda deletion, becoming a short /-e/; the rhyme ⟨-eng(s)⟩ developed into /-ɛ/, as seen in ⟨jem.tse⟩ /tɕe^Ndze:^H/ "scissor 剪子", ⟨sems.la⟩ /she:^Hrə:^H/ "remember 記得" and ⟨seng.ke⟩ /s^hɛ:^Hge:^H/ "lion 獅子".

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ed, -en, -es, -el, -er⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-ed, -en, -es, -el⟩ have all developed into /-i(:)/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-ed, -en, -es, -er⟩ have all developed into /-ɛ(:)/. These two developments are shown in Table 4.21.

Table 4.21 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ed, -en, -es, -el(d), -el)⟩

>i	⟨dred.mong⟩	tɕi ^N mo: ^H	Ursus pruinusos	人熊, 馬熊
	⟨vphyen⟩	ɕ ^h i ^L	fart	屁
	⟨rnam.shes⟩	na ^N ɕi: ^H	soul, mind	靈魂, 心識
	⟨drel⟩	tɕi ^L	mule	騾子
>ɛ	⟨dgod.byed⟩	kɛ ^N ɕɛ ^H	joke, jape	笑話
	⟨len⟩	lɛ: ^H	take	拿
	⟨nyes.pa⟩	ŋɛ: ^H ɕa: ^H	sin	罪
	⟨gyer.ma⟩	je: ^H mo: ^H	wild pepper	花椒

4.4 Developments of ⟨-o(C)⟩

The rhyme ⟨-o(C)⟩ retains as an extra-short rhyme /õ/ in open syllables; raises to /u(:)/ when followed by labial, velar, or ⟨-r⟩ codas; fronts to /e(:)/ before alveolar codas ⟨-on, -od, -os⟩; and fronts to a long rhyme /i:/ before ⟨-ol⟩, as seen in Table 4.22.

Table 4.22 Developments of ⟨-o(C)⟩

	⟨-o⟩	⟨-ob(s)⟩	⟨-om(s)⟩	⟨-og(s)⟩	⟨-ong⟩	⟨-on⟩	⟨-od⟩	⟨-os⟩	⟨-ol⟩	⟨-or⟩
Inherited	õ	u	u:	u	u:	e:	e	e:	i:	u:
S1		o	o	o	o	o	o			o
S2	u			y	y		u	y	u	
S3							ɛ	ɛ	iɛ	e
Irregular								i		

4.4.1 Inherited developments of ⟨-o(C)⟩

Inherited development of ⟨-o⟩. The rhyme ⟨-o⟩ remains as an extra-short rhyme /-õ/, as shown in Table 4.23.

Table 4.23 Inherited development of ⟨-o⟩

>o	⟨so⟩	s ^h õ ^H	tooth	牙齒
	⟨glo⟩	l ^{õ} ^H	girth	馬肚帶
	⟨rdo⟩	t ^{õ} ^L	rock	石頭
	⟨mgo⟩	g ^{õ} ^L	head	頭
	⟨mtsho⟩	ts ^h õ ^H	lake	湖

Inherited development of ⟨-ob(s), -og(s)⟩. The rhymes ⟨-ob(s), -og(s)⟩ have developed into a short rhyme /-u/ in Gyersgang (Table 4.24).

Table 4.24 Inherited development of ⟨-ob(s), -og(s)⟩

⟨-ob(s)⟩	⟨th ob s⟩	tu ^H	add (salt)	放 (~鹽)
	⟨s ob ⟩	lu ^L	teach	教 (~給)
⟨-og(s)⟩	⟨g og ⟩	lu ^H	lightning	閃電
	⟨v phog ⟩	p^hu ^H	shoot	射中
	⟨ log . log ⟩	lu ^N lu ^H	circle, round	圓

Inherited development of ⟨-om, -ong, -or⟩. The rhymes ⟨-om, -ong, -or⟩ have all developed into long /-u:/ in Gyersgang (Table 4.25).

Table 4.25 Inherited development of ⟨-om, -ong, -or⟩

⟨-om⟩	⟨ dom ⟩	tu ^L	bear	熊
	⟨s kom ⟩	ku ^H	thirsty	渴
	⟨s dom ⟩	tu ^L	bind	綁
⟨-ong⟩	⟨s dong ⟩	tu ^H	tree	樹
	⟨r kyong ⟩	tsu ^L	reach out	伸 (~手)
⟨-or⟩	⟨ nor ⟩	nu ^L	cattle	牛
	⟨g tor ⟩	tu ^H	sow	撒 (~種)

Inherited development of ⟨-od, -on, -os, -ol⟩. The vowel ⟨-o-⟩ with codas ⟨-n, -s⟩ have developed into a long rhyme /-e:/; ⟨-od⟩ has become a short rhyme /-e/ (Table 4.26).

Table 4.26 Inherited development of ⟨-od, -on, -os⟩

⟨-on⟩	⟨t shon ⟩	ts^he ^L	pigment	染料, 顏料
	⟨g son .po⟩	se ^H bo ^H	lived	活 (活的)
⟨-od⟩	⟨ bod ⟩	pe ^L	Tibetan	藏族
	⟨g sod ⟩	se ^H	kill	殺
⟨-os⟩	⟨s pos .ril⟩	pe ^H	incense	香 (燒的香)
	⟨ bgos ⟩	ke ^L	separate	分開
	⟨ zos ⟩	se ^L	eat	吃

Different from the aforementioned three alveolar codas, ⟨-ol⟩ has become a front vowel /-i:/, merging with ⟨-ul⟩. The development of ⟨-ol⟩>/-i/ illustrates that in the rhymes' evolution, ⟨-ol, -ul⟩ initially merged into ⟨-ul⟩, and then ⟨-ul⟩ has become /-i/. The occurrence of these two rules follows a specific sequential order.

Table 4.27 Inherited development of ⟨-ol⟩

⟨-ol⟩	⟨ dkar.yol ⟩	ke ^H i ^H	bowl	碗
	⟨s kol ⟩	ki ^H	boil	熬

4.4.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-o(C)⟩

Non-inherited development of ⟨-ob(s), -og(s)⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ob(s), -og(s)⟩ developed into /-o/, such as ⟨yob.lcags⟩ /yo^Ntei:^H/ "stirrups 馬蹬子", ⟨gshog.rtsa⟩ /χo^Ntea^H/ "wing 翅膀".

In the second non-inherited stratum, ⟨-og(s)⟩ undergoes the development of ⟨-og(s)⟩ > /-y/, such as ⟨vbrog.pa⟩ /dzy^Npə^H/ "shepherd 牧民".

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-om(s), -ong, -or⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-om(s), -ong, -or⟩ lost their codas and developed into /-o(:)/, such as ⟨rnga.mong⟩ /ŋe:^Hmo:^H/ "camel 駱駝", ⟨gnyom.chung⟩ /ŋo^Ntɛy:^H/ "polite 客氣" and ⟨zor.ba⟩ /so^L/ "sickle 鐮刀".

In the second non-inherited stratum, ⟨-ong⟩ has developed into /-y:/, as seen in ⟨rna.long⟩ /nə:^Hly:^H/ "earrings 耳環".

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-od, -on, -os, -ol⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-od, -on⟩ have lost their codas and developed into /-o(:)/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-od, -ol⟩ have become /-u(:)/, while the rhyme ⟨-os⟩ has developed into /-y:/.

In the third non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-od, -os, -ol⟩ have developed into /-(i)ɛ/. All of these developments are shown in Table 4.28.

Table 4.28 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-od, -on, -os, -ol⟩

>o	⟨smy on .pa⟩	ŋo: ^H ba ^H	madman	瘋子
	⟨mtch od .me⟩	te ^h o ^N me ^H	butter lamp	酥油燈
>(i)ɛ	⟨dus.t shod ⟩	ti ^N ts ^h ɛ ^H	time	時間
	⟨phud. gos ⟩	p ^h y ^N ke: ^H	quilt	被子
	⟨vt shol ⟩	ts ^h iɛ: ^L	find	尋找
>u	⟨khy od ⟩	te ^h u ^H	you	你
	⟨tɛhu.k hol ⟩	te ^h ə ^N ku: ^H	hot spring	溫泉
>y	⟨g·y os ?⟩	zy: ^L	mix	摻 (~水)

4.5 Developments of ⟨-a(C)⟩

The rhyme ⟨-a(C)⟩ developed into an extra-short /ǝ/ in open syllables, and shifts to the back vowel /ɑ(:)/ with nasal codas and becomes a short /ɑ/ in ⟨-ab(s)⟩; maintains as /ɑ(:)/ before ⟨-g(s), -r⟩; fronts to /-(i)ɛ/ with alveolar stops and lateral codas, as shown in Table 4.29.

Table 4.29 Developments of ⟨-a(C)⟩

	⟨-a⟩	⟨-ab(s)⟩	⟨-am⟩	⟨-ag(s)⟩	⟨-ang⟩	⟨-an⟩	⟨-ad⟩	⟨-as⟩	⟨-al⟩	⟨-ar⟩
inherited	ǝ	ɑ	ɑ:	ɑ	ɑ:	ɛ:	ɛ, iɛ	ɛ:	ɛ, iɛ	ɑ:
S1		ɑ	o	ɐ	o		ɑ		ɑ	ɐ
S2			uo	ɑ	uo	e	e		e	ɛ
Irregular	a, ɑ, o, ɛ	o, u	ɐ	u, o						o, iɛ

4.5.1 Inherited developments of ⟨-a(C)⟩

Inherited development of ⟨-a⟩. In Gyersgang, ⟨-a⟩ developed into an extra-short /-ǝ/, as shown in Table 4.30.

Table 4.30 Inherited development of ⟨-a⟩

>ɐ	⟨kha⟩	k^hǝ^H	mouth	嘴
	⟨ja⟩	tɛǝ^H	tea	茶
	⟨skra⟩	ɕǝ^H	hair	頭髮
	⟨rta⟩	tǝ^H	horse	馬
	⟨khra⟩	ts^hǝ^H	sparrow hawk	鷓子
	⟨rgya⟩	dzǝ^L	ethnic Han	漢族

Inherited development of ⟨-ab(s), -am, -ang⟩. In Gyersgang, the rhymes ⟨-am, -ang⟩ developed into a long rhyme /a(:)/, while the rhyme ⟨-ab(s)⟩ becomes a short /ǎ/ (Table 4.31).

Table 4.31 Inherited development of ⟨-ab(s), -am, -ang⟩

⟨-ab(s)⟩	⟨snabs⟩	na^H	snot	鼻涕
	⟨chu.rlabs⟩	tɕ^hǎ^Nla^H	wave	波浪
⟨-am⟩	⟨lam⟩	la^L	road	路
	⟨lham⟩	χa^L	shoes	鞋
⟨-ang⟩	⟨chang⟩	tɕ^ha^L	alcohol	酒
	⟨glang⟩	la^H	ox	公黃牛
	⟨vgrang⟩	dza^L	be full	飽

Inherited development of ⟨-ag(s), -ar⟩. The loss of the coda ⟨-g(s)⟩ results in the formation of a short rhyme /ǎ/, and the loss of the ⟨-r⟩ results in a long rhyme /a:/ (Table 4.32).

Table 4.32 Inherited development of ⟨-ag(s), -ar⟩

⟨-ag(s)⟩	⟨phag⟩	p^ha^H	pig	豬
	⟨lcags⟩	tɕa^H	iron	鐵
⟨-ar⟩	⟨mar⟩	ma^L	ghee	酥油
	⟨mkhar⟩	k^ha^L	wall	牆

Inherited development of ⟨-ad, -an, -as, -al⟩. The rhymes ⟨-ad, -an, -as, -al⟩ become /-(i)ɛ/ (Table 4.33).

Table 4.33 Inherited development of ⟨-ad, -an, -as, -al⟩

>ɛ	⟨sman⟩	mɛ^H	medicine	藥
	⟨vbras⟩	dzɛ^L	rice	大米
>iɛ	⟨brgyad⟩	tsiɛ^L	eight	八
	⟨bal⟩	piɛ^L	wool	捲綿羊毛

4.5.2 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-a(C)⟩

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ab(s), -am, -ang⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, the rhyme ⟨-ab(s)⟩ has developed into /-a/; while ⟨-am, -ang⟩ have become a long /-o:/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-am, -ang⟩ have developed into /-uo/. These two developments are shown in Table 4.34.

Table 4.34 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ab(s), -am, -ang⟩

>a	⟨th ab .ka⟩	th ^N ky: ^H	oven	灶
	⟨rgyal.kh ab ⟩	dza ^N ka ^H	nation	國家
>o	⟨sk am .po⟩	ko: ^H po: ^H	dry	乾
	⟨spy ang .khu⟩	eo: ^H gə ^H	wolf	狼
>uo	⟨s ram ⟩	ɕuo ^H	otter	水獺
	⟨sp ang ⟩	puo ^H	lawn, meadow	草坪

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ag(s), -ar⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-ag(s), -ar⟩ have developed into /-ɛ/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, the rhyme ⟨-ar⟩ has developed into /-ɛ/, while ⟨-ag(s)⟩ has become /-ɑ(:)/. These developments are shown in Table 4.35.

Table 4.35 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ag(s), -ar⟩

>ɛ	⟨sk ar .ma⟩	kɛ: ^H mo: ^H	star	星星
	⟨sd ar .ga⟩	tɛ: ^H kə: ^H	walnut	核桃
>ɛ	⟨gr ags ⟩	tɕɛ ^L	loud	響
	⟨z ags ⟩	sɛ ^L	leak	漏 (~水)
	⟨dk ar .yol⟩	kɛ: ^H i: ^H	bowl	碗
>ɑ	⟨rgy ag .?⟩	tɕɑ: ^L	windy	颯 (~風)
	⟨mdung.rgy ag ⟩	dy ^N tɕɑ ^H	sting	蟄 (馬蜂~)

Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ad, -an, -as, -al⟩. In the first non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-ad, -al⟩ have developed into /-a/.

In the second non-inherited stratum, the rhymes ⟨-ad, -an, -al⟩ have all developed into a short /-ɛ/. All these developments can be seen in Table 4.36.

Table 4.36 Non-inherited developments of ⟨-ad, -an, -al⟩

>ɛ	⟨sh ad ⟩	ɕɛ ^H	comb (v.)	梳
	⟨rk an .po⟩	kɛ ^N po: ^H	old man	老頭兒
	⟨mt shal ⟩	tɕ ^h ɛ ^L	cinnabar	硃砂
>a	⟨sha.g nad ⟩	ɕhɛ ^N na ^H	muscle	肌肉
	⟨rg al .myig⟩	ka ^N ŋi ^H	spine	脊椎骨

4.6 Exceptions of rhyme developments

Some sporadic exceptions remain that require further investigation and explanation, with examples provided in Table 4.37.

Table 4.37 Irregular developments of rhymes

<-ib(s)>	>e	<rd ib >	de ^L	sagged	下陷
	>y	<sky ibs >	sy ^H	block	堵塞
<-u>	>o	<y u .ba>	yo ^N bu ^H	handle	把兒
<-ub>	>e	<gd ub .ba>	te ^N ə ^H	bracelet	手鐲
<-ur>	>ɐ	<bc ur >	tse ^N no ^H	pinch	擠 (~腳)
<-e>	>ə	<de>	tə ^L	s/he	她/他
	>o	<sog. le >	s^ho ^N lo ^H	saw	鋸子
<-os>	>i	<g. yos >	ji ^H	cook	炒
<-a>	>o	<nga>	ŋō ^H	I	我
	>a	<a. pha >	a ^N pa ^H	father	父親
	>ɑ	<rn a .lo>	nɑ ^N lo ^H	leaf	葉子
	>ɛ	<ma. ne >	mɛ ^L ge ^H	jaw, chin	下巴
<-am>	>ɐ	<th am .pa>	t^he ^N be ^H	ten	十
<-ar>	>o	<rdo.d kar >	ko ^N ŋo ^H	egg	蛋
	>ie	<ng ar .?>	ŋie ^N ŋə ^H	fierce, powerful	厲害
<-ab>	>o	<gnam.v ab >	nɑ ^H bo ^N	to rain	下 (~雨)
	>u	<rd ab >	tu ^L	drive	釘 (~釘子)
<-ag(s)>	>u	<vkhy ags .pa>	tɛ ^h u ^N ru ^H	ice	冰
	>o	<lag.ph is >	lo ^N ɛi ^H	headscarf	頭帕

5. Inherited tonal development

The tonal development of Gyersgang, as well as other Tibetan dialects in Thebo County, follows a similar pattern and consists of two tone registers, each characterized by five distinct tonal values that vary based on the length of the rhyme. The inherited development of tonal registers is primarily conditioned by the voicing status of CT initials, where voiced obstruents consistently develop into low register tones while voiceless obstruents yield high register tones. Sonorants exhibit a split pattern: simple sonorants uniformly acquire low register, whereas preinitialled nasals or preinitialled ⟨l-⟩ develop high register tones.

Table 5.1 Inherited tonal development

Tones		CT origin	High	Low
Rhyme type				
CT origin			<<(C)voiceless(M)-> <<CN(M)-> <<Cl->	<<(C)voice(M)-> <<N(M)-> <<l-), <r->
Extra-short simple		<∅, -ug(s), -eg>	53	22
Short simple & complex		<-b, -d, -ig(s), -og(s), -ag(s)>	51	13
Long simple & complex		<-N, -s, -l, -r, <σ.σ>	55	13

In Table 5.2, the syllable with <<(C)voiceless(M)-, CN(M)-, Cl-> clusters result in a high tone.

Table 5.2 Development of high tone

⟨(C)voiceless(M)-⟩	⟨ja⟩	tẽ^H	tea	茶
	⟨spos.ril⟩	pe:^H	incense	香 (燒的香)
⟨CN(M)-⟩	⟨gnyis⟩	ŋi:^H	two	二
	⟨rnag⟩	na^H	pus	膿
⟨Cl-⟩	⟨zla.ba⟩	la:^H	month	月
	⟨glu⟩	lə^H	song	歌

In Table 5.3, syllables with ⟨(C)voiced(M)-, N(M)-⟩ clusters and syllables with simple initials ⟨l-, r-⟩ yield a low tone.

Table 5.3 Development of low tone

⟨(C)voice(M)-⟩	⟨vbreg⟩	dzǎ^L	mow	割 (割~)
	⟨drug⟩	tey^L	six	六
	⟨zos⟩	se:^L	eat	吃
⟨N(M)-⟩	⟨nya⟩	ŋe^L	fish	魚
	⟨nags⟩	nǎ^L	forest	森林
⟨l-⟩, ⟨r-⟩	⟨ro⟩	rō^L	corpse	屍體
	⟨lam⟩	la:^L	road	路

6. The intermediate status of Gyersgang

This section compares Gyersgang, the "Middle Thebo" dialect, with the westernmost Upper Thebo dialect, Gyiba, and the easternmost Lower Thebo dialect, Ridang. Through this comparison, it seeks to clarify Gyersgang's intermediate status and uncover the factors that enable its mutual intelligibility with both neighboring dialects.

Unless otherwise specified, the sound changes in Gyiba discussed in this section follow Yang et al. (2024), while those in Ridang follow Yeung (2024).

6.1 Historical comparative evidence

In the evolution of initial consonants, Tibetan dialects within Thebo exhibit a shared innovation in which ⟨(C)CM-⟩ clusters in the inherited stratum consistently develop into alveolar consonants. The two subsequent developments, the alveolo-palatal and fricativized strata, are also observed in Ridang. This suggests that after the migration of Central Tibetan speakers to Ridang Township, Gyersgang and Ridang experienced a similar contact history. Additionally, Cone also exhibits the alveolo-palatal stratum, and given that the Cone Tusi once ruled this region, the shared alveolo-palatal stratum in Gyersgang and Ridang may have originated from Cone.

The following page presents three tables of the inherited developments of the rhymes in Gyiba, Gyersgang and Ridang.

In the evolution of open syllables, the merger of ⟨i, u⟩ into /ə/ is a shared innovation between Gyersgang and Gyiba, a pattern also observed in Amdo dialects. Meanwhile, the shift of ⟨a⟩ to /ɛ/ represents a shared development between Gyersgang and Ridang.

In closed syllables, the change of ⟨o + alveolar⟩ to /e/ and ⟨a + alveolar⟩ to /ɛ/ preserves the contrast between these two vowels, marking a shared innovation between Gyersgang and Gyiba. The development of ⟨ol⟩ into /i:/ is another common feature of these two dialects, as is

the retention of ⟨i + alveolar⟩ as /i/, whereas in Ridang, it has shifted to /ə/. Thus, in terms of vowel development, Gyersgang aligns more closely with Gyiba and diverges from Ridang.

Table 6.1 Gyiba inherent rhyme development (from Yang et al. 2024)

	⟨∅⟩	⟨-b(s)⟩	⟨-m(s)⟩	⟨-g(s)⟩	⟨-ng(s)⟩	⟨-n⟩	⟨-d⟩	⟨-s⟩	⟨-l⟩	⟨-r⟩
⟨i⟩	ə	iʔ	ĩ	iʔ	ẽ	ĩ	iʔ	i:	i:	u:
⟨u⟩	ə	oʔ	õ	oʔ	õ	ĩ	iʔ	i:	i:,o:	u:
⟨e⟩	e	eʔ	ẽ	aʔ	ẽ	ẽ	eʔ	e:	i:	e:
⟨o⟩	o	oʔ	ũ	uʔ	ũ	ẽ	eʔ	e:	i:	u:
⟨a⟩	a	oʔ	õ	aʔ	õ	ẽ	ɛʔ	ɛ:	ɛ:	a:

Table 6.2 Gyersgang inherent rhyme development

	⟨∅⟩	⟨-b(s)⟩	⟨-m(s)⟩	⟨-g(s)⟩	⟨-ng(s)⟩	⟨-n⟩	⟨-d⟩	⟨-s⟩	⟨-l⟩	⟨-r⟩
⟨i⟩	ǎ	i	i:	i	i:	i:	i	i:	i:	i:
⟨u⟩	ǎ	y	y:	ǎ	y:	i:	i	i:	i:	y:
⟨e⟩	ẽ	i	i:	ǎ	i:	e:	e	e:	e:	e:
⟨o⟩	õ	u	u:	u	u:	e:	e	e:	i:	u:
⟨a⟩	ě	ɑ	ɑ:	a	ɑ:	ɛ:	ɛ	ɛ:	iɛ	a:

Table 6.3 Ridang inherent rhyme development (from Yeung 2024)

	⟨∅⟩	⟨-b(s)⟩	⟨-m(s)⟩	⟨-g(s)⟩	⟨-ng(s)⟩	⟨-n⟩	⟨-d⟩	⟨-s⟩	⟨-l⟩	⟨-r⟩
⟨i⟩	ǎ	i	i:	ə	ɛ:	-	ə	ə:	ə:	i
		iɛ	iɛ	a/⟨y-⟩_	iɛ	i/⟨y-⟩_		ɛ/⟨y-⟩_		
⟨u⟩	ũ	u	u:	ũ	u:	i:	i	i:	i:	u:
		o/σ_								
⟨e⟩	ǎ	ɛ	ɛ:	ẽ	ɛ:	ɛ:	ɛ	ɛ:	ɛ:	ɛ:
		ui/⟨dp-⟩_								a/⟨y-⟩_
⟨eu⟩	iɛ									
⟨o⟩	ǎ	u	o:	õ	o:	ɛ:	ɛ	ɛ:	ɛ:	o
			uo	uo	uo		ə	o/⟨y-⟩_	u/⟨y-⟩_	ɛ
⟨a⟩	ě	a	ɑ:	ua	ɑ:	a:	ɛ	ɛ:	iɛ	(u)ɑ:
		ɑ			ə			ə	ɑ	(u)ɑ
		ua		ua					ia	ɛ/⟨y-⟩_

By comparing the three tables above, notable shared innovations between Gyersgang and Gyiba/Ridang are listed below. The higher number of shared innovations between Gyersgang and Gyiba suggests a closer genetic relationship. These shared innovations primarily target vowel quality parameters, with length distinctions being treated as secondary in the following Table 6.4.

Furthermore, Gyersgang shares two critical shared innovations with Lower Thebo dialects, Rdora and Azha:⁴ the emergence of a new monophthong /y/, and the devoicing of CT consonants with non-nasal preinitials (⟨non-N+voiced stops and affricates⟩>voiceless).

⁴The location of Azha and Rdora are shown in Figure 6.1.

Table 6.4 Shared innovations between Gyersgang and Gyiba or Ridang

shared with Gyiba	shared with Ridang
<v>>v (w)	<h>>χ
<dp>>p	<bk>>k
<gy>>dz	<bt>>t
<shw>>χ ^h (x ^h)	<bts>>ts
<e>>e	loss of prenasal ⁿ in <N+voiced>
<o>>o	<(b)zl>>l
<i, u>>ə	<bky, sky>>ts
<ig(s), id, is, il>>i	<vgr, vby>>dz
<in, id, is, il>>i (and its merge with <un, ud, us, ul>)	<a>>ǝ
<om, og(s), ong, or>>u	<ir>>i:
<eg>>a	<ob(s)>>u
<en, ed, es, er, on, od, os>>e	<am, ang>>a
<an>>ɛ	<al>>ie
<ar>>a:	<un, ul>>i

6.2 Lexical evidence

Lexicon is also a crucial factor in linguistic subgrouping (Hoffmann et al. 2021). In Gyersgang, certain lexical items have two variants. One aligns with the Upper dialect and the other with the Lower dialect. This phenomenon further facilitates Gyersgang's mutual intelligibility with both neighboring dialects.

The word "father 父親" has two forms within Thebo's dialects, <a.pha> and *(je.je). The form <a.pha> is used in Upper Thebo; the form *(je.je) is used in Lower Thebo, and both forms can be used in Gyersgang, which are <a.pha> /a^Npa^H/ and (jo.jo) (*(je.je)) /tɕa:^Htɕə^H/ respectively. Therefore, Gyersgang, along with Dbangbzang, can be regarded as a language intelligible to both the Upper and Lower Thebo languages.

Figure 6.1 Development of "father 父親"

Furthermore, Gyersgang exhibits dual lexical variants for "stomach 胃": /p^ha^Na.^H/ and /tsə^Nə^L/. Comparative data from neighboring dialects show divergent forms: Gyiba employs <pho.ba> /p^ho/ while Ridang utilizes <grod.pa> /tsu^Npa.^H/ for this lexical item.

6.3 Morphosyntactic evidence

Morphosyntactic evidence has become increasingly significant in linguistic subgrouping (Hoffmann et al. 2021). The TAME system (tense, aspect, modality, and evidentiality) is one of the most complex and widely studied aspects of Tibetan morphosyntax (Tournadre & LaPolla 2014; Gawne & Hill 2017). Table 6.5 compares the TAME systems of Gyiba, Gyersgang, and Ridang, showing a strong lexical alignment between Gyersgang and Ridang, while Gyiba exhibits notable differences. Tournadre & Jiatso (2001) identify the choice of factual existential verbs as a key distinction between Upper and Lower Thebo dialects, with Upper Thebo using ⟨red⟩ and Lower Thebo using ⟨vgi⟩. Morphosyntactic evidence suggests a similarity between Gyersgang and the Lower Thebo dialects.

Comparative analysis reveals that Gyersgang exhibits significantly deeper penetration of grammatical borrowing than phonetic borrowing in contact-induced changes.

Table 6.5 A comparison of TAME systems in Thebo dialects (from Yeung 2024)

	PRS			PST			PRF		
	EGO	FACT	SENS	EGO	FACT	SENS	EGO	FACT	SENS
Gyiba	a	le.reʔ	i	ŋə	nə.red	rɛ/ RESINFR ^{zə}	jeʔ	ʔ	nã
Gyersgang	te	i	to.tsie	bə.le	bi	pu.tsie	ʔsi:	ʔsi:	na:
Ridang	to	i	to.ts ^h ɛ:	pu.li/ li	pi	pu.ts ^h ɛ:	ta.ji:	si:	se: ta.na:
	FUT			EXV			COP		
	EGO	FACT	SENS	EGO	FACT	SENS	EGO	FACT	SENS
Gyiba	tsɛ̃(tsə.ji)/ a	tsə.reʔ/ i		jeʔ	jeʔ.le.reʔ	nã	ʃi	reʔ	
Gyersgang	zi	i		ʔji.tsie	na:	na:	ji:	gi	gi.ko.ɐ
Ridang	tsi	gi		na:	da:.gi	na:	ji:	gi	gi.dɛ.i

6.4 The historical status of Gyersgang

Oral histories suggest that the Ridang people settled in the region alongside the Baima during the Tibetan Empire's eastern expansion, whereas the Upper Thebo residents are likely indigenous Tibetans. In contrast, Gyersgang's oral traditions do not include narratives of migration.

In terms of traditional attire, the women of Ridang, Lazar, and Byavbab wear short tunics and trousers, differing from the traditional Tibetan robes. In Upper Thebo, however, women wear long robes, and Gyersgang women share this style, aligning them with Upper Thebo rather than Ridang.

The evidence from shared innovations, oral history, and costume anthropology mutually reinforce the conclusion that Gyersgang is likely indigenous, much like the Upper Thebo Tibetans. However, due to its geographical proximity to Ridang, extensive and deep contact occurred after Ridang's migration, leading to significant similarities between the two and ultimately shaping Gyersgang's intermediate status.

7. Summary

The syllable structure of Gyersgang has undergone significant simplification compared to CT. Both preinitials and medials have been lost, leaving only simple onsets. Notably, a typologically rare aspirated fricative has emerged due to a chain shift, and the acoustic properties of this consonant set are of particular interest for experimental phonetic research (Du forthcoming). Additionally, the complete loss of CT codas has led to vowel length distinctions and the

development of new monophthongs and diphthongs. The resulting three-way length contrast in rhymes is typologically significant (Kuznetsova 2025). The tonal development of Tibetan reveals ongoing tonogenesis (Wee 2019; Chirkova 2025), and the partial tone system of Gyersgang is also crucial for research on tonal emergence.

In Section 7, historical comparative, lexical, and morphosyntactic evidence alongside multidisciplinary observation to account for Gyersgang's intermediate linguistic status. Additionally, it demonstrates Gyersgang's most recent common ancestry with the Upper Thebo dialects as part of the indigenous Tibetan population. This section also provides a methodological approach to distinguishing shared innovations due to common inheritance from similarities arising through contact.

The Tibetic language family, as a major branch of the Sino-Tibetan language family, harbors many mysterious phenomena awaiting exploration and discovery. On the vast and boundless Tibetan Plateau, countless Tibetic languages remain unexplored by field linguists with pioneering spirits, contributing further to humanity's understanding of language.

ABBREVIATIONS

C	Consonant	PRS	Present
CT	Classical Tibetan	PST	Past
COP	Copulative verb	PRF	Perfect
EGO	Egophoric	M	Medial
EXV	Existential verb	SENS	Sensory
FACT	Factual	V	Vowel
FUT	Future		

APPENDIXES

Appendix 1: Development of CT simple consonants

<k->	<c->	<t->	<p->	<ts->
k	te,z,j	t,d	p,b	ts,dz
<kh->	<ch->	<th->	<ph->	<tsh->
k^h,k,y	te^h,te,dz,ɕ,z,j	t^h,t	p^h,p	ts^h,ts,s,z
<g->	<j->	<d->	<b->	<dz->
k	te	t	p	-
<s->	<z->	<sh->	<zh->	<h->
s^h	s	ʃ^h,ʃ	ʒ,ʒ^h	ʒ
<ng->	<ny->	<n->	<m->	<v->
ŋ	ŋ,ŋ	n	m	v
<r->	<l->	<y->	<w->	<ʔ->
r,z,l	l,z,r	j,y	v	ʔ

Appendix 2: Development of CT consonants with the preinitial 1

⟨dk-⟩	k,g,y	⟨gc-⟩	te	⟨gt-⟩	t,t^h	⟨dp-⟩	p	⟨gts-⟩	ts
⟨bk-⟩	k,g	⟨bc-⟩	te	⟨bt-⟩	t			⟨bts-⟩	ts
⟨rk-⟩	k,g			⟨rt-⟩	t,d			⟨rts-⟩	ts
⟨lk-⟩		⟨lc-⟩	te, l	⟨lt-⟩	t	⟨lp-⟩			
⟨sk-⟩	k,g			⟨st-⟩	t	⟨sp-⟩	p	⟨sts-⟩	
⟨mkh-⟩	k^h	⟨mch-⟩	te^h,te	⟨mth-⟩	t^h			⟨mtsh-⟩	ts^h,dz
⟨vkh-⟩	k^h	⟨vch-⟩	te^h	⟨vth-⟩	t^h	⟨vph-⟩	p^h,p	⟨vtsh-⟩	ts^h
⟨dg-⟩	k			⟨gd-⟩	t	⟨db-⟩			
⟨bg-⟩	k			⟨bd-⟩	t				
⟨mg-⟩	g,k	⟨mj-⟩	dz	⟨md-⟩	d,t			⟨mdz-⟩	dz,ts
⟨vg-⟩	g,k	⟨vj-⟩	dz	⟨vd-⟩	d,t	⟨vb-⟩	b	⟨vdz-⟩	dz
⟨rg-⟩	j	⟨rj-⟩	te,dz,te^h	⟨rd-⟩	t,d	⟨rb-⟩		⟨rdz-⟩	ts
⟨lg-⟩		⟨lj-⟩	te	⟨ld-⟩	t,d	⟨lb-⟩			
⟨sg-⟩	k,g			⟨sd-⟩		⟨sb-⟩			

Appendix 3: Development of CT consonants with the preinitial 2

⟨gs-⟩	s	⟨gsh-⟩	χ						
⟨bs-⟩	s	⟨bsh-⟩	χ						
⟨gz-⟩	z	⟨gzh-⟩	ʏ			⟨g·y-⟩	j,z		
⟨bz-⟩	z	⟨bzh-⟩	ʏ			⟨lh-⟩	l,χ		
⟨dng-⟩	ŋ	⟨gny-⟩	ŋ,ŋ	⟨gn-⟩	n	⟨dm-⟩	m		
⟨mng-⟩	ŋ	⟨mny-⟩	ŋ	⟨mn-⟩	n				
⟨rng-⟩	ŋ,ŋ	⟨rny-⟩	ŋ			⟨rm-⟩	m		
⟨lng-⟩	ŋ			⟨rn-⟩	n				
⟨sng-⟩	ŋ	⟨sny-⟩	ŋ	⟨sn-⟩	n	⟨sm-⟩	m		

Appendix 4: Development of CT consonants with the medials

y		r		l		w	
⟨ky-⟩	-	⟨kr-⟩	-	⟨kl-⟩	-	⟨kw-⟩	-
⟨khy-⟩	ts^h,te^h	⟨khr-⟩	ts^h,te^h			⟨khw-⟩	-
⟨gy-⟩	dz,te	⟨gr-⟩	ts	⟨gl-⟩	l	⟨gw-⟩	-
						⟨cw-⟩	-
						⟨nyw-⟩	ŋ
		⟨tr-⟩	-			⟨tw-⟩	-
		⟨thr-⟩	-				
		⟨dr-⟩	te			⟨dw-⟩	t
⟨py-⟩	-	⟨pr-⟩	-				
⟨phy-⟩	ɛ,ɛ^h	⟨phr-⟩	te^h,te			⟨tsw-⟩	-
⟨by-⟩	ɛ	⟨br-⟩	te	⟨bl-⟩	l	⟨tshw-⟩	ts^h
⟨my-⟩	ŋ	⟨mr-⟩	-				
		⟨sr-⟩	ɛ,ɛ^h	⟨sl-⟩	l,s	⟨sw-⟩	-
				⟨zl-⟩	l	⟨zw-⟩	s
		⟨shr-⟩	-			⟨shw-⟩	χ^h
						⟨zhw-⟩	χ
		⟨hr-⟩	-			⟨hw-⟩	-
						⟨lw-⟩	-
		⟨grw-⟩	-	⟨rl-⟩	l	⟨rw-⟩	r

Appendix 5: Development of CT consonants with preinitials and medials

⟨bky-⟩	ts,ɕ	⟨bkr-⟩	ts^h,tɕ				
⟨dky-⟩	ts	⟨dkr-⟩	ɕ	⟨dpy-⟩	-	⟨dpr-⟩	-
⟨sky-⟩	ts,tɕ,ɕ	⟨skr-⟩	ɕ	⟨spy-⟩	ɕ	⟨spr-⟩	ɕ
⟨bsky-⟩	-	⟨bskr-⟩	-				
⟨rky-⟩	-			⟨rtsw-⟩	ts		
⟨brky-⟩	-						
⟨mkhy-⟩	-	⟨mkhr-⟩	ts				
⟨vkhy-⟩	tɕ^h,ts^h	⟨vkhr-⟩	ts^h	⟨vphy-⟩	ɕ^h,ɕ	⟨vphr-⟩	ts^h
⟨bgy-⟩	-	⟨bgr-⟩	-				
⟨dgy-⟩	-	⟨dgr-⟩	dz	⟨dby-⟩	j	⟨dbr-⟩	-
⟨sgy-⟩	ts	⟨sgr-⟩	-	⟨sby-⟩	-	⟨sbr-⟩	r
⟨bsgy-⟩	-	⟨bsgr-⟩	-				
⟨rgy-⟩	ts,dz,dz,tɕ						
⟨brgy-⟩	ts						
⟨mgy-⟩	dz	⟨mgr-⟩	-				
⟨vgy-⟩	dz	⟨vgr-⟩	dz,ts,dz,tɕ	⟨vby-⟩	dz	⟨vbr-⟩	dz
						⟨vdr-⟩	dz
⟨dmy-⟩	-	⟨rmy-⟩	-	⟨bkl-⟩	-	⟨bgl-⟩	-
⟨smy-⟩	ŋ	⟨smr-⟩	-	⟨bsl-⟩	-	⟨bzl-⟩	l
				⟨brl-⟩	l	⟨bsr-⟩	-

REFERENCES

- Bielmeier, R., & Driem, G. V. (2018). *Comparative dictionary of Tibetan dialects (CDTD)*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Chirkova, K. (2025). Pitch, vowel duration, and phonation in Baima and neighboring languages. *Language and Linguistics*, 26(2), 224-261.
- Chirkova, K., & Amelot, A. (2013). Baima (Illustrations of the IPA). *Journal of the International Phonetic Association*, 53(2), 547-576.
- Dhakal, D. N., List, J. M., & Roberts, S. G. (2024). A phylogenetic study of South-Western Tibetic. *Journal of Language Evolution*, 9(1-2), 14-28.
- Du, S. R. (2024). *Diebuxian zangyu huayuanhua yinxi tanjiu* [A phonetic and phonological profile of Gyersgang Tibetan in Thebo]. B.A. Dissertation, Capital Normal University.
- Du, S. R. (Forthcoming). An Acoustic Exploration of Fricatives in Gyersgang Tibetan. M.A. Thesis, The Chinese University of Hong Kong.
- GesangJumian & GesangYangjing. (2002). *Zangyu fangyan gailun* [an introduction to tibetan dialects]. Minzu chubanshe.
- Hoffmann, K., Bouckaert, R., Greenhill, S. J., & Kühnert, D. (2021). Bayesian phylogenetic analysis of linguistic data using BEAST. *Journal of Language Evolution*, 6(2), 119-135.
- Jacques, G. (2014). Cone. In Jackson T.-S. Sun (ed.), *Phonological profiles of little-studied Tibetic varieties*, 269-375. Taipei: Academia Sinica.
- Jiang, D. (2002). *Zangyu yuyinshi yanjiu* [a study of the Tibetan phonetic history]. Beijing: Minzu chubanshe.
- Jin, P. (ed.). (1983). *Zangyu jianzhi* [Concise of the Tibetan Language]. Beijing: Minzu chubanshe.

- Kuznetsova, N. (2025). The rise of ternary quantity and its alignment with laryngeal articulations. *Linguistic Typology*, (0).
- Lin, Y. J. (2014). Thebo. In Jackson T.-S. Sun (ed.), *Phonological profiles of little-studied tibetic varieties*, 269-375. Taipei: Academia Sinica.
- Nishida, T. (1970). *Seibankan Yakugo no Kenkyuu: Tibet Gengogaku Zyosetu* [Study on Xifanguan Yiyu]. Kyoto: Shokado.
- Qu, A. T., & Jin, X. J. (1981). *Zangyu fangyan de yanjiu fangfa* [Methods in the study of the Tibetan dialects]. *Xinan Minyuan Xuebao*, 76-83.
- Renzeng Wangmu (2013). *Diebu zangyu yanjiu* [A study of Thebo Tibetan dialects]. Beijing: Zhongyang minzu daxue chubanshe.
- Sagart, L., Jacques, G., Lai, Y., Ryder, R. J., Thouzeau, V., Greenhill, S. J., & List, J. M. (2019). Dated language phylogenies shed light on the ancestry of Sino-Tibetan. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(21), 10317-10322.
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. (2003). Phonological profile of Zhongu: A new Tibetan dialect of Northern Sichuan. *Language and linguistics*, 4(4), 769-836.
- The Gazetteers Committee. (1998). *Diebu Xianzhi* [Gazetteers of Thebo county]. Lanzhou: Lanzhou daxue chubanshe.
- Tournadre, N. & Suzuki, H. (2023). *The Tibetic languages - an introduction to the family of languages derived from old Tibetan*. LACITO Publications (CNRS) Linguistic diversity series.
- Tournadre, N. (2014). The Tibetic languages and their classification. In Thomas Owen-Smith & Nathan W. Hill (eds.), *Trans-Himalayan linguistics: Historical and descriptive linguistics of the Himalayan area*, 105-129.
- Tournadre, N., & Jiatso, K. (2001). Final auxiliary verbs in literary Tibetan and in the dialects. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area*, 24(1), 49-111.
- Tournadre, N., & LaPolla, R. J. (2014). Towards a new approach to evidentiality: Issues and directions for research. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman area*, 37(2), 240-263.
- van Driem, G. (2001). *Languages of the Himalayas*. Leiden: Brill.
- Wee, L. H. (2019). *Phonological tone*. Cambridge University Press.
- Yang, D. X., Tshering, S., & Gates, J. P. (2024). A voicing rule for non-continuant obstruents in Thebo Tibetan. *Language and Linguistics*, 25(4), 710-746.
- Ye, G. Y. (Forthcoming). *Diebuxian zangyu shangdalahua yinxi tanjiu* [A phonetic and phonological profile of Upper Stagra Tibetan in Thebo]. B.A. Dissertation, Guangzhou University.
- Yeung, D. S. (2024). A comparative study of the phonology and morphosyntax of Ridang: an eastern Tibetic language. PhD. Thesis, Université Sorbonne Nouvelle - Paris 3.
- Zhang, M., Yan, S., Pan, W., & Jin, L. (2019). Phylogenetic evidence for Sino-Tibetan origin in northern China in the late Neolithic. *Nature*, 569(7754), 112-115.

Copyright 2025. Sirui Du and Daai-Syut Yeung.

Date received: 07 March 2025

Date accepted: 05 Apr 2025

To cite:

Du, Sirui & Daai-Syut Yeung (2025) Phonological Profile of Gyersgang Tibetan: An Endangered Eastern Tibetic Language Spoken in Thebo, Western China. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:63-100.

The Prosodic Status of the Sentence Final Particle in Hong Kong Cantonese

Lian-Hee Wee

Hong Kong Baptist University

lianhee@hkbu.edu.hk

Abstract

Although common in Chinese languages, sentence-final particles (SFPs) are perhaps most prevalent in Hong Kong Cantonese (more than 30 according to Wakefield 2010:iv). This squib argues that the SFP forms a prosodic unit of its own as a foot derived by phonological augmentation. This foot then forms a larger prosodic unit with its left-adjacent Intonation Phrase. This view is consistent with the prosodic hierarchy offered in Nespor & Vogel (2007).

Keywords: Sentence-final particles, prosody, Cantonese

1. Syntactic/semantic scope

Syntactically, the SFP is likely to c-command its immediate dominating clause since it determines the construction type and much of the corresponding meanings. For instance, SFPs signal question, doubt, among other many subtler possibilities.

(1) Examples of HK Cantonese SFPs

- a. 張三喜歡李四。
zoeng₁ saam₁ hei₂ fun₁ lei₅ sei₃
Zeong Saam likes/liked Lei Sei.
- b. 張三喜歡李四 maa₁?
zoeng₁ saam₁ hei₂ fun₁ lei₅ sei₃ maa₁
Does ZS like LS?
- c. 張三喜歡李四 gwaa₃?
zoeng₁ saam₁ hei₂ fun₁ lei₅ sei₃ gwaa₃
ZS probably likes LS
- d. 張三喜歡李四 bo₆?
zoeng₁ saam₁ hei₂ fun₁ lei₅ sei₃ bo₆
ZS likes LS (contrary to what had been implied)
- e. 張三喜歡李四 ze₁ maa₃?
zoeng₁ saam₁ hei₂ fun₁ lei₅ sei₃ ze₁ maa₁
ZS likes LS(, that's merely it).

A canonical SVO Cantonese sentence (1a) is shown with a sample of SFPs. I avoided providing Chinese characters for SFPs because they are highly colloquial and characters in use are varied, mostly selected as phonetic stand-ins. The transcription is given in Jyutping, with the subscripted numbers indicative of the tone categories (LSHK 2002:20). As is reflected through the glosses, the SFPs determine much of the syntactico-semantic-pragmatic properties of the clauses. Thus, in any or all of these dimensions, it seems most reasonable to conclude a structure akin to (2) which would reflect the scope of the SFP (see Simpson 2014, Cheng & Tang 2022 for discussions across Chinese languages).

(2) Scope of SFP

This squib argues that the structure in (2) is also reflected prosodically, particularly because pauses when placed in the boundary between the sentence S and the SFP are most natural and faithful to the semantic interpretation of the canonical sentence. Further, the fact that all SFPs have a CV sequence corroborates this interpretation rather than challenge it.

2. Distribution of pauses

Consider now the following facts about pause insertion.

(3) Pause insertions

- a. zoeng₁ saam₁ #A# hei₂ fun₁ #B# lei₅ sei₃ (cf. (1a))
- b. zoeng₁ saam₁ #A# hei₂ fun₁ #B# lei₅ sei₃ #C# maa₁/gwaa₃/bo₆/ze₁ maa₃
(cf. (1b-e))

In (3), pauses can be inserted in the positions marked #...#. At first blush, the pauses are simply allowed at phonological phrase boundaries (Nespor & Vogel 2007: chapter 6), corresponding to the left edge of a lexical XP. Closer inspection, however, reveals something more stunning.

As it turns out, pauses in #A# or in #B#, actually affects semantics. With #A#, what one gets is an interpretation that the preverbal NP *Zeong Saam* is a topic. Like many Chinese languages, Cantonese is topic prominent; constituents may move to the topic position (spec CP, if you like) leaving the source site empty. #A# is a prosodic reflection of topicalization. This syntactic distance is reflected in how topicalized items in other Chinese languages that share syntactic properties with Cantonese become exempted from obligatory tone sandhi.¹ Strictly speaking pause insertion at #A# is therefore not semantically faithful to the sentence in (1b-e). This is because the topicalized reading would have adjusted the semantic focus.

Similar adjustments of semantic focus are found also with pauses in #B#. To understand this, let us consider (3a) first. Pause at #B# in (3a) yields something called the right-dislocation construction. One can think of right-dislocation pragmatically as an afterthought and hence more performative than grammatical (but see Cheung 1997 et seq. for syntactic discussions). The effect of #B# is a redistribution of semantic focus (see Cheung 1997: 106ff, also Lee 2017 and references cited therein). Right dislocation is syntactically like topicalization, except that things move rightwards rather than leftwards,² see (4).

(4) Possible structures (cf. (3a))

- a. Topicalization
[topic_i #A# [sentence ___i [VP...]]]
- b. Right dislocation
[[[sentence ... [VP ___j]] #B# right dislocate_j]]

¹ Collocation of syllables in Cantonese does not trigger tone sandhi, hence such evidence is unavailable internal to this language.

² In a SVO language. In right dislocation, the dislocated elements are not necessarily a syntactic constituent, but must necessarily be a contiguous string. A syntactic account is certainly challenging, but prosodically, the dislocated string would form a unit (most likely an intonational phrase) and the remnant string another.

- c. Topicalization and right dislocation
 [topic_i #A# [sentence ____i [VP ____j]] #B# right dislocate_j]]

We now move on to (3b). Like (3a), the position of #C# in (3b) reflects a certain syntactic-semantic structural distance that one sees in #A#. What is important and interesting is that with #C#, (3b) would **have the same meanings as given in (1b-e)**. The scope of the SFP is wide. Another important observation is that in (3b), #A# without #B# or #C# is possible, just as #C# without the other two is possible. However, #B# without either #A# or #C# would be very odd.³ That one can pause at #C# without a pause at #A# similarly indicates how high up it is in the syntactic structure, and the prosody reflects that. The analysis of (3b), to remain logically consistent and congruent, would yield (5).

- (5) Possible structures (cf. (3b))
- a. Topicalization of subject
 [topic SUBJ_i] #A# [s [___]_i + VP] [SFP]
 - b. Topicalization of sentence
 [topic [SENTENCE]_j] #C# [___]_j + SFP_j]
 - c. Right dislocation of SFP
 [s ... ____j] #C# [right dislocate SFP_j]
 - d.?? Right dislocation of VP and SFP
 [s [SUBJ] #B# [right dislocate VP + SFP]

With (5), interpretations can be rather complicated. The point is that, unlike (4), the SFP is structurally higher (recall (2)). This is the main thrust of (5b, c). With a SFP sentence, having #B# prosodically would require having pauses at the higher syntactic boundaries as well, otherwise, the VP and the SFP would be the dislocated string, but they do not form a constituency without the subject. This is why, without #C#, #B# will be very odd in (3b). The semantic distinctions of (5b) and (5c) may be very subtle, and fall beyond the scope of the present paper.

The data from pauses thus suggests the prosodic unit of the SFP to be external to the preceding sentence, at least equivalent to whatever prosodic unit one would propose for separating topics from comments, or right dislocates from their source sentences.

3. Connecting to the prosodic hierarchy

I believe that the HK Cantonese SFP⁴ forms a prosodic utterance with its preceding intonational phrase (Nespor & Vogel: chapters 7 and 8), given in (6).

³ If at all possible, that would necessitate distortion in the semantics, presumably creating focus. Semantically, such focus would change the set of presuppositions. Consider for instance *Susan didn't buy Joey a car*, which contains only a set of existential presuppositions. But *Susan didn't buy Joey a car* would presuppose Susan did something for Joey regarding a car. Similarly with *Susan didn't buy...*, *Susan didn't buy Joey...*, *Susan didn't buy Joey a car*, and *...buy a car*. The effect of #B# when forced into (3b) is similar, but a study of semantics falls outside the purview of this paper.

⁴ I fudge for want of resources to explore other Chinese SFPs. Let me know if you wish to fund me. Packages range from HK\$150k to HK\$2m. Write for meeting times with a promissory note to pay for my beer please.

(6) Prosodic membership of HK Cantonese SFP

I shall explain what kind of prosodic unit the SFP itself is later (section 4).

The intonation phrase (InP) appears to be the most obvious starting point for the simple reason that one is looking at sentences. It is also a fact that SFPs do not attach to what appears to be de facto NPs, as in (7).

- (7) a.?? [lei₅ sei₃] maa₁/gwaa₃/bo₆/ze₁ maa₁
 b. [IP hai₂ [lei₅ sei₃]] maa₁/gwaa₃/bo₆/ze₁ maa₃
 c.? [VP hei₂ fun₁ lei₅ sei₃] maa₁/gwaa₃/bo₆/ze₁ maa₃

It is very odd to say (7a), and when done, the hearer must implicate various kinds of contexts, such as a sentence fragment response to a fuller question. In contrast, (7b) with a copula verb is okay. This suggests that SFPs are actually interpreted to be attached to items larger than lexical XPs. VPs are slightly better than just NPs, as is seen in (7c), since VPs are more pliable to be interpreted as IPs. The point here is that for (7a, c), the pre-SFP constituents are likely to be perceived as NP or VP respectively, rather than IPs. As such, they are less likely to be interpreted as InP (which typically is associated with clausal constituents). This can be more clearly seen in (8), where conjunction makes it unambiguous that one is dealing with VPs.⁵

- (8)?? 張三建議.....[conjoined VP [VP 食芝士] 同 [VP 飲紅酒]] SFP
 zoeng₁ saam₁ gin₃ ji₅[conjoined VP [VP sik₆ zi₁ si₆] tung₄ [VP jam₂ hung₄ zau₂]] SFP
 ZS suggests eat cheese and drink wine SFP

Although syntactically well-formed, the pause after *gin₃ ji₅* “suggest” creates the syntactic structural interpretation that the two conjoined items are VPs (thus a higher recursive VP from conjunction). In this case, the attachment of any SFP is again very odd, similar to (7a). Acceptability improves if the SFP is preceded by a pause.

Given the arguments that IPs (or sentences) are typically InP, and the data in (7) and (8), the safest conclusion leans to a prosodic structure given in (6). Further support becomes evident when one revisits the distribution of pauses in (3). There is a tendency for multiple InPs within a phonological utterance to be roughly equal in length (Nespor & Vogel 2007:194). Although I did not state this overtly earlier, many Cantonese speakers do find it odd to say (3b) with only #C#. The preference for articulating (3b) is (i) without pause, (ii) to have all #A#, #B# and #C#, thus pauses signal phonological phrasing rather than intonation, and (iii) to have only #C#. The order of preference reflects the tendency for InPs to be roughly equal in length.⁶ If a redistribution of semantic focus is allowed or intended, speakers feel it rhythmically more natural to use #B# in (3b), than #A#, although the meanings will be different depending on the position of the pause.

⁵ The pre-review version was unclear and led to the reviewer’s query if there are InPs that do not accept SFPs.

⁶ The preference to have just #A# than just #C# is probably due to the fact that the subject is a lexical projection, but the SFP is functional. In any case, having just #A# also affects the semantic focus. To be fully faithful to the original utterance without pauses, #C# is really the only option if only one pause is to be inserted.

4. Curious CV structure of the SFP

Of all the HK Cantonese SFPs discovered, none have a CVX structure. All of them are CVs, although phonetically they are usually CV:. The IPA transcription of those discussed in this squib are given (9).⁷

- (9)
- | | | | | |
|----|---|-------|-----------------------|--|
| a. | S | maa1 | [maa ⁵⁵] | S? |
| b. | S | gwaa3 | [kwaa ³³] | indicating some measure of uncertainty to S |
| c. | S | bo6 | [pɔɔ ²²] | indicating S as evidence inconsistent with given claim |
| d. | S | ze1 | [tsɛɛ ⁵⁵] | merely S |

The vowels are long enough so that each syllable can be considered a bimoraic foot. In fact, the syllable length of a SFP is indistinguishable from those of monosyllabic lexical words. In English, for instance, function words like *a* or *the* cannot be articulated as standalone words without lengthening. For instance, the two underlined *the*-s in *The word*, “*the*” ... have different vowel lengths. This kind of length alternation is not found in HK Cantonese SFPs.⁸

That all monosyllabic SFPs are CV: presents a curious asymmetry, which is deepened when one notices how in disyllabic SFPs such as *ze1 maa3*, the *ze1* is phonetically much shorter. The second syllable *maa3* has the option of being short too. Neither syllable is closed by a consonant, which is noteworthy because Cantonese does have unreleased [p, t, k] codas. These ones do not; they are simply short. Further, SFPs in Cantonese may be stacked so that one may have a sequence of SFPs, e.g. *ge-la-bo*.⁹ There are syntactic constraints on the ordering of how SFPs are stacked, but these do not concern us here (see Cheng & Tang 2022 and references cited therein). When polysyllabic, my observations are that SFPs have V rather than V: for the syllable nucleus.¹⁰

I suggest that the underlying forms of all SFPs are CV. They lengthen because as a monosyllable, foot binary demands bimoraicity. At this point, they may then form some kind of prosodic word (i.e. a prosodic foot that is a morphosyntactic word) that can then adjoin to the preceding InP to form utterances.

(10) Vowel augmentation for monosyllabic SFPs in Cantonese

⁷ Thanks to the reviewer for requesting for the IPA transcriptions.

⁸ Although found in Putonghua SFPs. Different Chinese languages have different prosodic properties.

⁹ This is trimoraic. One would have to either say that the final here is extrametrical or else to have it parsed into a ternary foot, overriding bimoraicity. Whichever one chooses, there is enough here to make a foot.

¹⁰ At the risk of complication, note that the SFPs in (9) can be short even if they are the only SFP in a sentence, i.e. no stacking of SFP. When that happens, the utterance comes across as sarcastic or unnatural. I see this as additional evidence that the underlying form is CV.

This view is supported by the fact that polysyllabic SFPs no longer need the vowel lengthening. They are large enough to form a binary foot, as in (11).

(11) Polysyllabic SFPs in Cantonese

Beyond the foot, I really have no strong opinions. Proponents or opponents of strict layering in the prosodic hierarchy may have their arguments, but evidence one way or another presently eludes me.

A last word, somewhat less relevant, is that my analysis takes the position that the minimal foot in Cantonese is a bimoraic syllable. This may not go well with those who believe that bisyllabicity is the minimal word requirement. While I am familiar with their evidence, I remain skeptical because such a position requires a claim that some 5000 syllables (the entire inventory of HK Cantonese) are all degenerate, yet all, without exception, are standalone words. Since a prosodic word can have more than one foot, the prevalence of bisyllabic words in Cantonese (and even other Chinese languages) do not need to be founded on such a strained conception of Chinese bisyllabic word minimality. The discussion, however, belongs to a different paper.

REFERENCES

- Cheng, Siu-Pong & Sze-Wing Tang (2022) Syntax of Sentence-Final Particles in Chinese. In Chu-Ren Huang, Yen-Hwei Lin, I-Hsuan Chen & Yu-Yin Hsu (eds.), *Cambridge Handbook on Chinese Linguistics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp.578-596.
- Cheung, Lawrence YL (1997) A Study of Right Dislocation in Cantonese. MPhil thesis, Chinese University of Hong Kong.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/35994918_A_study_of_right_dislocation_in_Cantonese
- Lee, Tsz Ming (2017) Defocalization in Cantonese Right Dislocation. *Gengo Kenkyu*, vol. 152:59-87. https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/gengo/152/0/152_59/_pdf
- Linguistic Society of Hong Kong (LSHK, 2002) 《粵語拼音字表》 *Yueyu pinyin zibiao* [Guide to LSHK Cantonese Romanization of Chinese Characters]. Hong Kong: Linguistic Society of Hong Kong, 2nd edition. (In Chinese.)
- Nespor, Marina and Irene Vogel (2007) *Prosodic Phonology* (with a new foreword). De Gruyter Mouton. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110977790>
- Simpson, Andrew (2014) Sentence Final Particles. In CT James Huang, YH Audrey Li, and Andrew Simpson (eds.), *The Handbook of Chinese Linguistics*. Oxford: John Wiley and Sons, Inc, pp.156-179.

Wakefield, John (2010) The English equivalents of Cantonese sentence-final particles: a contrastive analysis. PhD dissertation, Hong Kong Polytechnic University. <https://theses.lib.polyu.edu.hk/bitstream/200/6084/1/b24415571.pdf>

Acknowledgement

Although the question of the prosodic status of the Cantonese SFP has been in mind for decades since I started learning Cantonese, I never found motivation to try to address it. Yap Foong Ha prompted Winnie Chor to bug me with the question. I thank them both, especially Foong Ha for incisive comments on earlier drafts of this piece.

Thanks also to the lively audience for their attention and comments at the Institute of Linguistics, National Tsing Hua University on 14 Oct 2024. They observed that Taiwanese Min SFP [hɔ̃] (a solicitation of agreement) may surface in isolation as a full falling tone [51], in which case there is an implied covert sentence. If following an overt sentence, the tone is more commonly a lower, shorter falling [21].

Changes have been made to my squib on the basis of comments and suggestions from Miss Yi Zhen Chen who reviewed the paper. I send her many thanks!

I dedicate this to the students of the prosodic phonology class at the Linguistic Institute of China, summer 2024.

Copyright 2025. Lian-Hee Wee.

Date received: 29 Oct 2024

Date accepted: 09 Jan 2025

To cite:

Wee, Lian-Hee (2025) The Prosodic Status of the Sentence Final Particle in Hong Kong Cantonese. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:101-107.

FLaP FIRST

Facebook

Website

**Comments for Wee's
"The Prosodic Status of the Sentence Final Particle"**

Yi Jen Chen
National Chengchi University
106555501@nccu.edu.tw

This paper proposes that HK Cantonese SFPs form a prosodic word or foot, which is left-adjoined to the preceding Intonational Phrase (InP) to form a phonological utterance. Two main supporting arguments are given. First, pauses are considered most natural when placed between a sentence and its following SFP, so the preceding prosodic unit is an InP. Second, phonetically, all monosyllabic SFPs are CV:, and disyllabic SFPs are CV.CV, conforming to the bimoraicity requirement of a foot. This indicates that the prosodic unit of an SFP is at least a prosodic foot.

In general, the arguments are presented clearly, coherently, and friendly for non-speakers of Cantonese. Below are some questions and suggestions for the author's consideration.

1. InPs

Given that not all InPs can naturally form a phonological utterance with SFP, how does one rule out the InPs that cannot be adjoined by SFP? Do SFPs only attach to IPs/sentences?

If SFPs can still be attached in (7a-c) under particular circumstances, my questions would be:

- i. Does it mean that the [lei5 sei3], [hai2 [lei5 sei3]], and [hei2 fun1 lei5 sei3] are individual InPs?
- ii. If they are not InPs, what prosodic structures do they have?
- iii. If they are InPs, how does one distinguish the InPs that SFPs cannot naturally attach to from the InPs that they can naturally attach to?

On the other hand, if SFPs are only legal in (7b), then I guess my questions are moot.

2. Bimoraicity of SFPs

How does a string of SFPs, e.g., "ge-la-bo," conform to bimoraicity?

3. Jyutping transcription of SFPs

In Jyutping transcription, some SFPs are transcribed as CV:, like maa₁ and gwaa₃, while other SFPs are transcribed as CV, like bo₂ and ze₁, which does not reflect their phonetic CV: structure. Perhaps their IPAs may also be given for non-speakers of Cantonese?

4. Reference

At the beginning of Section 3 on p. 3, chapters 9 (Prosodic Constituents and Disambiguation) and 10 (Prosodic Domains and the Meter of the Commedia) of Nespor & Vogel (2007) was given as reference for the prosodic structure formation in (6). Perhaps the author wanted the readers to refer to chapters 7 (The Intonational Phrase) and 8 (The Phonological Utterance) instead?

Copyright 2025. Yi Jen CHEN.

Date received: 09 Jan 2025

To cite:

CHEN, Yi Jen (2025) Comments for Wee's "The Prosodic Status of the Sentence Final Particle".
FLaP FIRST, vol.1:108.

[Review Article]

On Progress in Physics and Subjectivity Theory: An Amateur's Meanderings as Inspiration for Actual Physicists. By N. Otre Le Vant. 2024. ISBN: 979-8876516510.

Reviewed by Tommy Yuk-Cheung WONG
Hong Kong Baptist University
wongyc.tommy@gmail.com

“The only thing I can truly be certain of is subjective experience, everything else should be taken with a grain of salt.” This idea is taken to its extreme in N. Otre Le Vant’s Subjectivity Theory (hereafter, ST), which states that a Subject’s brain creates their reality according to certain cognitive rules.¹ In ST, understanding planetary movement is not discovering a property of an objective world. Rather, it is an inward quest of how the Subject (sub-)consciously creates the world. The idea is hardly original. ST’s style of reasoning aligns with that of René Descartes and Immanuel Kant. However, instead of inquiring into the structure of human cognition, N. Otre Le Vant’s central thesis is on removing the bias and noise in human judgments that impedes progress in physics. His suggestion is to “forget everything we think we know” (p.30) and start from subjective experience as the certain mark of truth.

No new paradigm has emerged since the advent of relativity theory and quantum physics. N. Otre Le Vant interpreted this as a stagnation of progress in fundamental physics. ST is proposed as a new paradigm. According to N. Otre Le Vant, ST is a falsifiable theory because its prediction can be verified experimentally. ST predicts time dilation occurs exclusively for other objects because the Subject created everything, including their accelerations relative to the Subject; time dilation affects only accelerating objects. N. Otre Le Vant claimed that a modified version of the experiment in Hafele and Keating (1972) can verify ST’s prediction: by having the Subject on the plane, time dilation should only happen for the clocks on the ground.

ST’s verification can only be performed by the Subject, since its presence affects how other objects experience time. This makes the verification non-replicable by anyone else. Although the Subject can repeat the experiment, the verification of ST is not replicable in the traditional sense that allows peer review. Independent discoveries of the same phenomenon have reinforced empirical claims (e.g. for the discovery of Higgs boson, see The ATLAS Collaboration, 2012; The CMS Collaboration, 2013). Such experiment replicability is lacking in ST’s verification.

Replicability regardless, it is not clear how ST is compatible with the original findings of the Hafele-Keating experiment. To recap the original experiment: three identical atomic clocks are used. One remained on the ground in Washington DC, one was put on an eastward-flying plane, and one was put on a westward-flying plane. Moving with the Earth’s rotation, the clock on the eastward-flying plane had the fastest speed, followed by the clock on the ground. The clock on the westward-flying plane was the slowest, as it moved against the direction of Earth’s rotation. The three clocks were compared after the round-Earth flights. Hafele and Keating (1972) found that the clock on the eastward flight *lost* approximately 59 ± 10 nanoseconds, while the clock on the westward flight *gained* approximately 273 ± 7 nanoseconds relative to the clock on the ground. N. Otre Le Vant did not seem to recognize there were two planes, one of which gained time while the other lost time (p.44).

The logic remains unclear on how ST’s prediction is compatible with the findings in the Hafele-Keating experiment. According to ST, if the Subject is on the ground, then the Subject created both the eastward-flying and westward flying planes and their acceleration with

¹ These rules include arbitrary categorization (e.g. dividing a continuous spectrum of wavelengths into distinct color categories) and manipulation (e.g. representing the world in spatio-temporal perception).

respect to the Subject. Since ST agrees that time dilation occurs on accelerating bodies only, it would predict that time moves slower for the two planes due to their acceleration; both clocks should lose time. However, the Hafele-Keating experiment found that one clock lost time while the other gained time. The results are incompatible with ST's prediction.

Verification non-replicability and findings incompatibility make ST an inadequate empirical theory. Moreover, ST—proposed as a Kuhnian paradigm—does not seem to address pressing anomalies. According to Kuhn (1962), paradigms emerge in response to a crisis in science. That is when confidence in current paradigm is lost as anomalies arise. Current paradigms such as relativity theory and quantum physics addressed previous anomalies that arose when an object gets very fast or gets very small respectively, thereby replacing Newtonian mechanics and Maxwellian electromagnetism. However, many of the explanations provided by ST either introduce unfalsifiable solipsism or regress the questions,² without adequately solving an anomaly that calls for a paradigm shift.

Additionally, there seems to be no crisis necessitating a scientific revolution. As far as I know, scientists' confidence in current paradigms remains intact. The recent discovery of gravitational waves (Abbott et al., 2016) and Higgs boson (The ATLAS Collaboration, 2012; The CMS Collaboration, 2013) reinforced the credence of relativity theory and the Standard Model of particle physics as functional paradigms. Physics has been making cumulative progress in verifying current theories without encountering significant anomalies. There may not be a need for a new paradigm yet.

Proposing ST is a questionable move when N. Otre Le Vant's main thesis is on facilitating scientific progress. Progress is rarely made by discarding previous efforts and starting anew. N. Otre Le Vant prioritizes removing thinking errors in human judgments, but I wonder why it is “best to assume that *everything we think we know about the world is wrong*” (emphasis original) (p.5). Moreover, I am doubtful of what could be gained by adopting ST in understanding the world. Whether the world exists subjectively or objectively has rarely concerned scientists. Modern physics made progress in explaining phenomena regardless of their ontological status.

Despite my critique on ST, N. Otre Le Vant was insightful in compiling a near-manual for achieving progress in chapter three. Heuristics such as questioning established assumptions, embracing fresh perspectives, and striving for simplification and unification are key to any advancement in physics. However, given that the book aims to be “straightforward and accessible to everyone” (p.ii), it is puzzling why N. Otre Le Vant did not begin with chapter three—‘Achieving Progress in Physics’—as it offers the most value to the intended layperson reader. The first two chapters would benefit from a more detailed discussion, especially in areas such as the criteria for empirical theories, Kuhnian paradigms, and time dilation. The use of Socratic dialogue throughout the chapters creates a stimulating read, though at times the interlocutor serves more as a mouthpiece than as a committed critic.

REFERENCES

Abbott, Benjamin P., Richard Abbott, Thomas D. Abbott, Matthew R Abernathy, Fausto Acernese, Kendall Ackley, Charles Adams, Thomas Adams, Paolo Addesso, Jordan B. Camp, & Leo P. Singer (2016). Observation of gravitational waves from a binary black hole merger. *Physical review letters*, 116(6), 061102–061102.

² For questions such as: why are there laws of nature and why is the universe comprehensible (p.34)? Why mathematics explain nature so well (p.35)? How are particles entangled without violating the rule of locality (p.36)? ST's explanations come down to: because the Subject “create[s] the world according to certain rules...[following] logical, mathematical principles” (p.34-35). ST proposed no falsifiable claim to address the regressed question “why does the Subject's brain create the world that way?”

<https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevlett.116.061102>

Hafele, Joseph C., & Richard E. Keating (1972). Around-the-world atomic clocks: Predicted relativistic time gains. *Science (American Association for the Advancement of Science)*, 177(4044), 166–168. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.177.4044.166>

Kuhn, Thomas S. (1962). *The structure of scientific revolution*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

The ATLAS Collaboration. (2012). Observation of a new particle in the search for the Standard Model Higgs boson with the ATLAS detector at the LHC. *arXiv.Org*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1207.7214>

The CMS Collaboration. (2013). Observation of a new boson at a mass of 125 GeV with the CMS experiment at the LHC. *arXiv.Org*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1207.7235>

Copyright 2025. Tommy YC Wong.

Date received: 25 November 2024

To cite:

Wong, Tommy YC (2025) Review of N. Otre Le Vant's *On Progress in Physics and Subjectivity Theory: An Amateur's Meanderings as Inspiration for Actual Physicists*. *FLaP FIRST*, vol.1:109-111.

FLaP FIRST

Facebook

Website

About *FLaP FIRST*

簡介

Founded 2024 成立

Format 格式:	PDF
Frequency 頻次:	Up to 2 issues per year 至多每年 2 期
Email 郵箱:	FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com
Editorial team 編輯部:	Kaixin ZHAO 趙凱欣 (founding chief 創刊主編 2024 –) Yoyo PY TSANG 曾霽銚 Tommy YC WONG 黃昱翔
Advisory board 諮詢委員會:	Lian-Hee WEE (chair) 黃良喜 (主席) <i>Hong Kong Baptist University</i> 香港浸會大學 Yuchau E. HSIAO 蕭宇超 <i>National Chengchi University</i> 國立政治大學 Eri IWAGAMI 岩上惠梨 <i>University College London</i> 倫敦大學學院 František KRATOCHVÍL <i>Palacký University Olomouc</i> 帕拉茨基大學 Mingxing LI 李明興 <i>Hong Kong Baptist University</i> 香港浸會大學 Zihe LI 李子鶴 <i>Peking University</i> 北京大學 Yu-Leng LIN 林育稜 <i>National Chung Cheng University</i> 國立中正大學 Jing SHAO 邵晶 <i>Hong Kong Baptist University</i> 香港浸會大學 Joanna U.S SIO 蕭月嫦 <i>Palacký University Olomouc</i> 帕拉茨基大學 THAM, Shiao Wei 譚曉微 <i>National University of Singapore</i> 新加坡國立大學 Janice WS WONG 黃穎思 <i>Hong Kong Baptist University</i> 香港浸會大學 Yang LIU 劉洋 <i>Hong Kong Baptist University</i> 香港浸會大學

1. *FLaP FIRST* is a journal created in celebration of the 12th year of the founding of the HKBU Phonology Lab (which was 2012). It is intended to give academic leadership and service experience to postgraduate students.

FLaP FIRST 創刊是為香港浸會大學音系實驗室成立 12 周年（2012 年成立）誌慶，旨在給碩博生提供學術領導和服務的機會。

2. *FLaP* is acronym for “Formal Linguistics and Philosophy” a reading group founded in 2017 by students of Prof. Lian-Hee Wee who served as consultant professor. *FLaP* has since met

at the HKBU Phonology Lab. *FIRST* is acronym for “frank, initial, raw, surprising thoughts”, which is intended to describe the nature of the papers this journal will publish. This journal is not intended to be just a collection of working papers.

FLaP 是英文“形式語言學及哲學”的縮寫，是 2017 由黃良喜教授的學生成立的閱讀小組，並以香港浸會大學音系實驗室為活動地點。*FIRST* 代表“坦誠、初步、未經雕琢、出人意表的想法”，描述了本刊希望錄取的文章種類。

3. *FLaP FIRST Papers* welcome submissions globally. Submissions should relate broadly to the fields of formal linguistics and philosophy. Types of papers *FLaP FIRST* aims to attract are:

- a. original manuscripts and/or working papers,
- b. squibs,
- c. unabridged and/or unmutated manuscripts of papers published elsewhere
- d. critical viewpoints
- e. reviews of monographs, papers, or anything due for a review

FLaP FIRST 向全球徵集與“形式語言學及哲學”的領域相關的稿件，類型包括：

- a. 研究手稿
- b. 研究小品
- c. 已發表文章的原始（未經不良評審破壞）手稿
- d. 評論性觀點
- e. 對專著、文章等進行綜述

4. Authors will not be required to revise their submissions before publication. Papers submitted are either rejected or accepted, although typographical editing and grammar fixes may be requested before final acceptance. This is in keeping with the concept implied by *FIRST*.

作者不會被要求修改所提交的文章。提交的文章只會被拒絕或接受。不過，在最終收稿前可能會要求作者對排版及語法進行修改。這與 *FIRST* 的理念一致。

5. *FLaP FIRST* does not have a fixed style or format, but must follow the template provided in “*FLaP 1st-Template4author-EN.docx*” or “*FLaP 1st-Template4Author-CH.docx*”. These are files that authors can directly use when preparing their papers. Papers may be in English or Chinese. Chinese papers must provide title of submission and abstract in both languages. This is also recommended/expected for English papers. Any use of Chinese must be written in traditional characters.

The author(s) determine what format is best suited for publication. Any submission should be in WORD, and camera-ready. A PDF may be included for reference.

Poorly edited and poorly formatted work are grounds of rejection.

FLaP FIRST 沒有固定的體系或格式，但是必須遵循“*FLaP 1st-Template4Author-EN.docx*”或“*FLaP 1st-Template4Author-CH.docx*”所提供的模板。這些文件作者在準備文章時可直接使用。文章可以用英文或中文撰寫。中文文章必須提供雙語版的題目與摘要。英文文章也建議並希望作者能提供中文題目與摘要。中文用繁體書寫。

作者自行決定文章格式，提交 Word 格式的見刊清樣。為方便編輯參考，作者也可以考慮提供 PDF 版本。

嚴重的編輯和格式問題會導致文章被拒收。

6. There is no set length requirement, but submissions should be as tersely written as possible. Our editors and reviewers are very busy and they are not paid.

文章沒有長度局限，要盡可能簡潔。請體恤編輯和評審無薪賣命。

7. Except for cases of desk rejection, editor(s) will invite up to 3 reviewers for each paper. The review process is single-blind (i.e. authors are known to the reviewers). Reviewers will be informed that their duties are:

- a. To only either recommend publication or rejection.
- b. To provide helpful constructive commentary within 2 pages, which will be supplied to authors anonymously in cases of rejection.
- c. To indicate if they allow their reviews to be published alongside the paper. In this case, at the point of publication, the identities of the reviewers will be revealed to the author(s).

文章除非直接被編輯部拒審，一般來說會考慮至多 3 位評審的意見。評審：

- a. 僅建議是否接受文章進行發表。
- b. 提供 2 頁內建設性評論。如果文章被拒，評審意見會匿名反饋給作者。
- c. 表明是否允許將自己的評論隨文章一併發表。如果允許，在發表時，評審的身份將隨即公開。

8. *FLaP FIRST* issues will be archived. We have no funding and are experimenting with the website (<https://flapfirstjournal.wordpress.com/>) and Facebook group (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1010853150414893>) in this early stage of our journal. Please support us through our teething pains.

FLaP FIRST 每期存檔。囊中羞澀，無法負擔伺服器。創刊初期，嘗試使用網站 (<https://flapfirstjournal.wordpress.com/>) 以及 Facebook 群組 (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1010853150414893>)。請支持我們成長。

9. All copyright of the submissions remain with the authors. Authors retain rights to use their article(s) in original forms or with modifications at other venues at any time (although see (10) below).

In making a submission, the author(s) affirm ownership of the content and material contained therein or have obtained any requisite copyright permissions, obeying all relevant intellectual property laws.

Author(s) should ensure the legality of the content they submit.

Authors are responsible for any costs, penalties or lawsuits incurred by legal and/or intellectual property violations.

Where there are disputes or doubts after a paper is published, *FLaP FIRST* will immediately redact any article in question and will reinstate it only when the matter is resolved.

文章的所有版權歸作者。作者可隨時以原始形式或經修改後在其他場合使用文章（見下文第（10）條）。

提交文章時，作者已確認對所提交內容和材料的所有權，或已獲得任何必要的版權許可，並遵守所有相關的知識產權法律。

作者應確保所提交內容的合法性。

因違反法律和/或知識產權而產生的任何費用、處罰或訴訟均由作者負責。

若在文章發表后出現爭議或疑問，*FLaP FIRST* 將立即撤回，直至問題得到解決。

10. By submitting to *FLaP FIRST*, the author(s) grant *FLaP FIRST* all requisite permissions for publication and dissemination of the submitted work in any form and format that *FLaP FIRST* deems suitable. The authors also grant eternal gratis use of the submission and its contents for **non-profit** *FLaP FIRST* publicity, publications, and, products. *FLaP FIRST* will make every reasonable effort to inform authors of any such use of their work. Where in doubt, *FLaP FIRST* will make every reasonable effort to seek permissions from authors.

向 *FLaP FIRST* 投稿的作者即授予 *FLaP FIRST* 所有必要的權限：允許以 *FLaP FIRST* 認為合適的任何形式和格式出版和傳播所提交的作品。作者允許 *FLaP FIRST* 永久免費在非謀利宣傳、出版及產品中，使用其提交的作品及內容。如有此類使用，*FLaP FIRST* 將盡力通知作者。有疑問處，*FLaP FIRST* 也將盡力向作者尋求許可。

Contra tyrannidem per veritatem

Call for Papers: *FLaP FIRST*

FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com

*F*LaP *FIRST*, a postgraduate student-led journal to present “Frank, Initial, Raw, Surprising Thoughts” broadly related to **Formal Linguistics and Philosophy**, is now making a global call for papers. For more information, please scan this QR code to access issues, materials and resources at our website.

Journal website

We welcome:

- a. original manuscripts and/or working papers
- b. squibs
- c. unabridged and/or unmutilated manuscripts of papers published elsewhere
- d. critical viewpoints
- e. reviews of monographs, papers, or anything due for a review

Papers may be in English or Chinese. Chinese papers **must** provide title of submission and abstract in both languages. This is also recommended/expected for English papers. Chinese characters must be written in **traditional Chinese**. Authors’ templates are available at our [website](#) and [Facebook Group](#) (<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1010853150414893>) for reference.

Submissions should be written as **tersely** as possible.

Each paper will be reviewed by up to three anonymous reviewers. Review is single-blind. Papers are **either accepted or rejected**. There will be **no revisions**.

Please send submissions to FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com. A submission is a single WORD file, containing abstract and keywords. Since revision is not an option, the submission should be camera-ready. A PDF may be included for reference.

Submission constitutes confirmation by authors that (i) they are owners of the material submitted and/or have obtained rights to use content contained therein; and (ii) they grant non-exclusive gratis use to *FLaP FIRST*. Authors retain all rights of their papers.

Join our FB group!

We are working without funding and resources. Please support us by joining our Facebook Group and inviting your friends to follow us. Please also share our website (<https://flapfirstjournal.wordpress.com/>) to as many people as possible, so that we may grow in service of free and accessible scholarship.

徵稿: *FLaP FIRST*
FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com

 FLaP FIRST 是一份由碩博生領航的學刊，現向全球徵稿。凡涉獵形式語言學或哲學領域的研究都歡迎。請掃描右側二維碼，前往學刊網站，獲取往期文章、投稿指南等更多資訊。

學刊網站

我們徵羅以下各稿件類型：

- a. 研究手稿
- b. 研究小品
- c. 已發表文章的原始（未經不良評審破壞）手稿
- d. 評論性觀點
- e. 對專著、文章等進行綜述

文章可以**繁體**中文或英文撰寫。投稿**必須**提供英譯題目及摘要。請注意行文簡潔精練。稿例詳情可於**學刊網站**或 *FLaP FIRST* Facebook 群組（<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1010853150414893>）查閱。

本刊採取單向匿名評審制，至多考慮 3 份評審意見。評審結果**僅限接納或拒絕**，不會要求作者修改稿件。

請以單一 WORD 文檔（包含摘要及關鍵詞）投稿至：FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com。因不設修改，所備稿件須為付梓清樣。作者也可另外提供 PDF 版本作為排版參考。

提交文章即表示作者已經確認 (i) 對所提交內容和材料的所有權，或已獲得任何必要的版權許可，並遵守所有相關的知識產權法律；(ii) 無條件授予 *FLaP FIRST* 所有必要的權限。文章版權屬於作者。

目前學刊營運沒有經費及資源。誠邀大家加入我們的 Facebook 群組，持續關注學刊最新消息；亦懇請大家廣泛分享學刊網站：<https://flapfirstjournal.wordpress.com/>，襄助自由公開的學術交流。

加入我們 FB 群組！

Do not write anything in the header

Template and Example for Authors

Kaixin Zhao	2 nd author	n th author
Hong Kong Baptist University	Affiliation	Affiliation
FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com	Author2@email.com	AuthorN@email.com

Abstract

Please write your abstract here in about 50 to 100 words. Abstracts must be informative, which means it doesn't just say what your paper plans to achieve. State explicitly your arguments and conclusions tersely. That way your readers would know immediately why your work should be cited. Avoid citations here since your abstract may be used to introduce your work independently of the list of references.

Keywords: list, maximally, five, keywords, here

1. Content

FLaP FIRST welcomes papers, squibs, reviews, working ideas that broadly relate to formal linguistics and philosophy. This also includes various sub-fields of literature, although we are unable to accept creative writing. We also welcome manuscripts of papers that have been published but may have been severely mutilated by reviewer 2. If you have such a traumatic experience, we might be a conduit to recovery. For such submissions, please provide information of the published version in the acknowledgement of some suitable place. That way, our readers can compare both versions.

2. Specific styles and sections

You are free to write your paper in any of the commonly accepted styles in your specific field. This includes how you use sections, sub-sections, and if these are numbered. You are also free to decide if you wish to use footnotes or endnotes. However, please follow the margins in this template strictly.

Everything must fit within the margins, including diagrams, pictures, graphs, tables, and figures. Everything! If they don't fit, we would be compelled to reject your paper.

Single line spacing please.

3. Font and sizes

For the main text and notes, please use Times New Roman 12pt for the main text. Footnotes may be 10pt. If data and illustration require other fonts, that's fine. For traditional Chinese characters, please use “宋體” following the same size specifications.

4. Language

We accept English and Chinese articles. Whichever language you choose to write in, please ensure that your work, including, data and references, is readable to a monolingual reader of that language you chose to write in.

For instance, if writing in English, and I need to use 中文字 *zhōngwénzì* “Chinese characters”, please ensure that it's meaning and pronunciation are transparent, as illustrated above. Since this journal is transdisciplinary and accepts articles from different epistemological traditions, we rely on you to decide how best to do this in the format and style most relevant to

Do not write anything in the header

your field. Syntacticians would certainly do this differently from philosophers.

5. Length

We do not have a length restriction. Your work should be as long as absolutely necessary, and as tersely written as humanly possible. We are sure you know that long papers rarely get read, so why waste efforts? Shorter papers are more likely to be read and cited.

APPENDIXES

Please number your appendixes and give them suitable headings. Avoid appendixes where possible please.

REFERENCES

Please use a style consistent with your main text for listing references. There is no need to be excessive, and no need to show off your scholarship. Cite only those that you actually discuss.

Acknowledgement

Please write any general acknowledgments here as briefly as possible. Otherwise, if you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us at FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com. Thank you for considering us as a venue for your important work.

中文題目

請提供大概 200 字內的摘要。這樣無法讀懂英語的讀者也可以理解文章的價值，甚至引用。字體使用宋體，小四號字。

請提供大概 200 字內的摘要。這樣無法讀懂英語的讀者也可以理解文章的價值，甚至引用。字體使用宋體，小四號字。

請提供大概 200 字內的摘要。這樣無法讀懂英語的讀者也可以理解文章的價值，甚至引用。字體使用宋體，小四號字。

Reviewers the author would like to suggest to the editorial:

Name of proposed reviewer	Email	Relationship with author(s) (if any)
1.		
2.		
3.		

投稿模板及範例

趙凱欣 香港浸會大學 FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com	第二作者 所屬單位 Author2@email.com	第 n 作者 所屬單位 AuthorN@email.com
---	-----------------------------------	-------------------------------------

摘要

請在這裏書寫摘要，大約 200 字內。摘要內容要詳實，切勿僅說明文章計劃與目標。請簡明扼要地陳述文章的觀點和結論。這樣可以更好協助讀者判斷是否引用您的文章。

關鍵詞：請，列出，最多，五個，關鍵詞

1. 內容

FLaP FIRST 歡迎涉獵形式語言學或哲學各領域的論文、研究小品、綜述型文章以及初步的研究構思，也歡迎文學的不同分支領域來稿，創意寫作除外。如果您曾經歷佳作被不良評審破壞，也懇請將該作原稿交付我們，讓世界看到它光輝的原貌。此類稿件，請在鳴謝處標明文章已發表版本的相關信息。這樣，讀者可以對文章的兩個版本進行比較。

2. 具體格式及章節

您可以自由選擇您領域認可的任何一種格式來撰寫文章，包括是否使用章節、小節，是否進行編號，以及使用腳注或是尾注。但是，請嚴格遵守本模板設置的頁邊距。

所有內容都應置於該頁邊距內，包括圖表、圖片、表格等任何內容。如果不符合頁面佈局，我們將不得不拒絕您的投稿。

請使用單倍行距。

3. 字體和字號

文章主體部分和注釋請用宋體，小四號字書寫。腳注可用五號字。如有需要，數據及其說明可以使用其他字體。如果需要使用拉丁文字請用 Times New Roman，字號 12pt，腳註則 10pt。其他文字類推。

4. 語言

我們接受中文或英文投稿。無論使用哪種語言撰寫文章，請確保該語言使用者，能輕鬆無阻地理解該文中任何外語的表述（包括數據和參考文獻）。

例如，用中文書寫的文章需要使用 한글 *hangul* “韓語”時，請清楚準確提供發音以及釋義。本刊為跨學科刊物，接受來自不同知識體系的文章。我們仰賴您的專業知識，選擇最適合所屬領域的格式及文風。例如，句法學者的做法一定與哲學家不同。

5. 長度

我們對文章長度沒有限制，但請惜墨如金。文章應簡潔精煉，足夠表達所需內容就好，不要浪費筆墨和精力。長且臭的稿件誰稀罕，短而精的文章萬人贊！我們都希望

頁眉請留空白，不可書寫。

您的文章會獲得讀者青睞。

附錄

若有多個附錄，請為它們編號，並提供標題。如果可以，請盡量避免使用附錄。

參考文獻

請使用與文章主體一致的格式列出參考文獻。不要過量，也無需賣弄。只引用文章確實討論過的文獻即可。

鳴謝：

請在此盡量簡潔地寫下您的致謝。如果您有任何疑問，請隨時通過 FLaPFIRSTJournal@gmail.com 與我們聯絡。承賜大作，不勝感激！

English Title

Your name in English or Latin alphabetic writing

Please provide an abstract in about 50-100 words. In this way, readers who cannot read Chinese can understand the value of your article and even cite it.

Please provide an abstract in about 50-100 words. In this way, readers who cannot read Chinese can understand the value of your article and even cite it.

歡迎作者建議合適的評審人

建議評審人	通訊電郵	評審人與作者的關係 (如有)
1.		
2.		
3.		

FLaP FIRST
Volume 1, May 2025

FLaP FIRST is a student-led journal of Formal Linguistics and Philosophy (*FLaP*) dedicated to publishing Frank, Initial, Raw, Surprising Thoughts (*FIRST*).

Contra tyrannidem per veritatem.

CC-by
FLaP FIRST 2025, volume 1.
Rights of individual papers retained
by their respective authors.

Scan to support us!

Website

Facebook

